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**Information Communication Technologies in Teaching English as a Foreign Language:
Teacher Perspective**

Doctoral Dissertation

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Declaration

Hereby, I declare that this dissertation is my original work which I have worked out own my own. All sources, references and literature used or excerpted during elaboration of this work are properly cited and listed in complete reference to the due source.

Dev Raj Paneru

Dedication

I dedicate this thesis to my loving mother Mrs.Hari Priya Devi Paneru and my physically late, yet spiritually inspiring and immortal father Padam Nav Paneru for begetting me and to the creative and constructive work I believe this research should stand as one example.

Acknowledgement

In writing this thesis, I have followed American psychological association style for citation and bibliography and referred theoretical, political and research literature, data and official manuscripts accordingly. There are numerous people involved in supporting me throughout this research whom it will be impossible to mention all, but some have been so invaluable that they must be sincerely named. First and foremost, my doctoral supervisor Doc. Jiri Zounek, Ph.D. from the Department of Educational Sciences, MU, Brno and co-supervisor Prof. Lotar Rasinski, Ph.D. from the Faculty of Education, ULS, Wroclaw deserve my sincere acknowledgement for guiding, encouraging and constructively critiquing my work far beyond the call of duty! In addition, I have benefitted in abundance from the research board members at the Department of Educational Sciences, MU, Faculty of Education, ULS and European Doctorate in Teacher Education (EDiTE) consortium with constructive feedback and support on project level. I also thank the EDiTE researchers for learning collaborations and my fellow researchers at MU for sharing their insightful ideas. I sincerely commend the EDiTE technical secretariat Mgr. Ondrej Barta and Mgr. Zuzana Smidekova for excellent coordination throughout. My sincere thanks to Dr. Khagendra Prasad Ojha and colleagues at Professional Educators Limited, Kathmandu for providing moral as well as institutional support. I too commend all research participants and four case teachers from the Czech Elementary Schools for their active participation and data regarding technology in teaching English. The research presented in this thesis along with four publications and my entire study-stay as well as participation in learning programs were fully funded by European Union's Horizon-2020 programme of research and innovation under Marie-Sklodowska-Curie Grant-676452. Finally, I express very special thanks to Prof. Milan Pol. Last but not the least, I thank my wife Aruna for plentiful encouragement and my lovely son Joyas for bearing with me despite not talking to him over many hours.

Summary

This phenomenological case study explores the status of information communication technology integration in teaching English as a foreign language in Czech elementary schools from teacher perspective. Technologies are significantly emerged educational components in European school, yet, little is known how these affect the process of teaching-learning linking teacher practices in class considering the development of learning English upon communication skills as defined by intercultural dimension.

Due to the persisting inconsistencies between educational perspectives and teachers' practices in response to an ever-increasing need of achieving educational significance of modern information technologies, the phenomenon i.e. technology integration in teaching English with a goal of learning upon skills of communication scopes interactive research participation on comprehensive focus. The research on comprehensive focus is idealized on the scheme of exploring this phenomenon on constructing learning as a better substitute of the one limitedly designed to reporting the increasing use of technologies with mechanical educational focus.

Studies on phenomenological concept that lends subjectivity epistemology in (social) construction do bring some comprehensive ideas in this regard as, teachers under such model develop competences and practice technology integration on constructing learning within 21st century school classroom on the interface of multiple contexts. However, along with existing research approaching this phenomenon in an inconsistent perspective, phenomenological studies exploring educational potentials of technologies in teacher's qualitative pedagogical perceptions, skills and practices of using technologies on comprehensive focus, are still very few in the European setting.

Thus, this phenomenological case study explored how technologies are part of the exemplary English teachers everyday teaching in the selected Czech Elementary Schools. The

study found the exemplary (teacher) practitioners significantly interactive in their pedagogical perceptions, skills of use and reflections regarding their practice of technology integration in teaching English within the intercultural theme of communication upon developing the phenomenon as a learning process. Though differences of stimuli and barriers as encountered by each teacher regarding the use of individual technologies in class were individually contextualized.

Key words: Information communication technology, English as a foreign language, Exemplary teacher, Communicative approach, Educational significance.

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INTRODUCTION

After more than 15 years using computers as an aid to teaching English as a Foreign Language (EFL), apart from experiencing enormous changes in teaching patterns that come along associated to the presence of digital technologies entering the field of teaching practices that bring forth numerous possibilities of encounters, I began to wonder how Information Communication Technologies (ICT) come to affect the process of teaching, as well as learning English¹ as a discipline of the school system. This quest directly concerns the teacher's daily practices. This primary encounter linking to teachers' practices gradually embodied into a major quest: How do technologies come to teachers² on their daily professional encounters with the teaching of a class? This doctoral thesis, focused on exploring technology integration into teaching EFL in selected Czech elementary schools as a case study prioritizing the teacher's perspective, develops around this quest, exploring such phenomenon by analyzing teachers' qualitative practices considering technology integration in classroom on constructing learning.

There are some genuine reasons due to which the above quest generates, and these are related to the changes in education and technologies entering the teaching of English right at the work-place, or classroom, in the 21st century school environment in its interface of the fast digitalizing global educational cultures in a network mode. For example, general instrument devices, black boards etc. in a school class in these last 20 years have been either on the verge of extinction or replaced by digital, online and ubiquitous technologies. Thus, as has become common these days, teachers' work place has been functioning largely supported by smart computers, laptops and mobiles, providing convergent and ubiquitous technological services as also sociocultural information of highly educational significance, therefore bringing mixed educational experiences and impacts.

¹ English in this entire thesis stands for EFL, in other cases, it means English as a native language

² Teacher/s in this thesis mainly denotes EFL teacher except when the term is used to mean teacher in general

In association to the changes caused by technologies entering the classroom, come an increasingly variety of types of changes simultaneously occurring in educational systems at different levels e.g. institutional structures and classroom practices. It is a common sight that in the fast digitalizing global socio-economies as in the European context, structural educational practices as confined within the classroom walls are eventually shifting beyond as ongoing learning practices that develop on, or as integrated with computer/online systems. Associated to the latter, we see the learner's realities growing smarter as the digital generations also bring along 21st century learning expectations. As such, new encounters enlighten, along with educational technological changes, a wide range of professional challenges aligned with new opportunities which have come to school teachers.

On the backdrop of these mixed encounters, I began to realize that technologies not only innovated in changing school education but also variously affected the process of teaching and learning, and teacher³ practices on the everyday basis. Yet, I was not sure on what basis, levels or reasons such technologies would affect, or likewise, how their educational potential would become realized, nor was I sure whether teachers as practitioners, or only technologies alone, were the primary source in the role of achieving unsteadily multiplying learning expectations. These new conflicts added to my basic quest of which eventually triggered a research interest to explore the educational potentials of technologies comprehensively with further question: How can, or do teachers integrate technologies concerning their didactic use into the English⁴ classroom on developing learning? Masaryk University, Department of Educational Sciences in partnership with European Union's European Doctorate in Teacher Education (EDiTE) research program set on a theme e.g. transformative teacher learning for better student learning within the emerging Europe agreed to provide an opportunity for doctoral study on this very issue.

³ Teacher in this thesis stands for EFL teacher except when used to mean teacher in general

⁴ EFL

Upon getting this opportunity of my interest with a quest yet to be refined, while developing research on literature base new encounters were added to my conflict. Amongst some, the conflicts rose primarily due to research communications as drawing on various perspectives mostly with quantitative focus representing a wide range of inconsistencies in practices regarding not only the role but also the meaning of technology and integration in class⁵ linking teacher practices. Moreover, in many cases technology integration is represented as still limited to different structural paradigms. In contrast, in innovative situations, literature on comprehensive focus also on accounts for teachers' interactive pedagogical approaches and skills of technology use contributing to the development of this phenomenon as a learning process. Such studies report teachers using technologies as innovative educational tools on creating learning motivation.

Further, exploring theory, policy and practice discourse representing the phenomenon in European schools in the Czech school context where this research was staged, I got even more increasingly worried. This was due to increasing contradictions between the potential of technologies, educational policy discourse surrounding them, efforts at making technologies work in classroom and suggestions and expectations regarding teachers' competence in integrating them into the classroom in order to achieve educational significance. In this regard, educational perspectives and practices were identified as moving in counter directions widening the gaps between policies and implementations along with increasing gaps between theoretical claims and field experiences. In connection with the gaps more serious issues were identified, and these were related to the research international communications also linking Czech educational research⁶ which is increasingly digital education policy-oriented. So, instead of learning, digital oriented communications rather limit achieving technology integration

⁵ Class in this thesis stands for EFL class except when used to mean class of teaching any subject in general

⁶ EFL educational research

instrumentally in teachers' mechanical knowledge of using technology, leading to mechanical educational outcomes.

Whereas, in contrast, teaching English⁷ in the Czech schools context within the common European framework means enhancing classroom practices on constructing learning for communication skills defined by intercultural dimensions. As such, technology integration is defined and develops in teachers' interactive pedagogical approaches and skills of using new technologies for enhancing classroom activities in a framework of knowledge construction as opposed to teaching that stands limited to replicating theory in a granted manner.

Following the contextual changes in teaching English in Czech schools within the fast digitalizing European educational system, that have triggered a need to change conventional pedagogical perspectives and practices, it has also become essential that teachers' classroom practices must provide 21st century learners technological enriching learning experiences. In the light of such contextual changes and emerging necessities, this study forms a fundamental and recurring assumption of how our knowledge is extended by the interaction with our social and cultural environment, artifacts, tools, technologies, media, thoughts, approaches, skills etc. as different forms of language on construction. Studies on phenomenological concept that lends subjectivity epistemology in (social) construction do bring some comprehensive ideas in this regard as, teachers under such model develop competences and practice technology integration on increasing learning interactions within 21st century school classroom on the interface of multiple contexts. However, along with existing research approaching this phenomenon in an inconsistent perspective, phenomenological studies exploring educational potentials of technologies in teacher's qualitative practices and cultural themes of using technologies on comprehensive focus, are still very few in the European setting. As such, achieving technology integration by exploring teachers' innovative pedagogical approaches, knowledge and skills for

⁷ EFL

using technology in the English class on developing learning, remains still an under-researched phenomenon at both international and Czech educational level. Due to existing inconsistencies as well as lack of focused research exploring educational potentials of technologies in teachers' pedagogical skills of using them on constructing learning, several questions, remain unaddressed. Amongst some, these questions need to be answered in a comprehensive manner e.g. how teachers perceive and appropriate the use of different types of technologies in class, upon which learning focus and activities are organized; how they use technologies and for which purposes, functions and educational outcomes; how teachers' individual factors are associated to their use in class and so on. These questions, seeking complex understanding of the phenomenon, can be answered comprehensively with phenomenological research such as case-studies. Such study allows to explore the phenomenon by exploring exemplary teachers' pedagogical perceptions, approaches, interpretations, skills, reflections regarding the use of technologies in class for developing learning, which in the case of English teaching in Czech educational research context, is nearly null.

Thus, this study is designed within a qualitative phenomenological case-study framework with an overarching objective to: explore and describe how ICT are part of exemplary EFL teachers' teaching class on developing learning in the case of Czech elementary schools. To this end, I analyze the selected teachers' exemplary practices of technology integration by focusing on their pedagogical perceptions, motivations, skills, experiences, practices, interpretations, reflections regarding technology use in class for constructing learning.

The given central research questions below guide the analysis:

1) How the exemplary English teachers use ICT in EFL class?

This question helps exploring teachers' decisions regarding the use of technology in class, its use as such, its functions, and the teachers' reflections. Connecting the role of phenomenological context, the second sub-question is formulated to understand:

2) How do exemplary teachers' individual factors contribute to use ICT in EFL class?

In short, these questions (discussed in chapter 3) allow to identify motivations, and conversely barriers as experienced by the exemplary study teachers, relating use of technology in the English classroom for constructing learning. Regarding these qualitative analytical bases, in this phenomenological case-study research, I thus, anticipate exploring and describing how technologies are part of exemplary teachers' practices of teaching English regarding the development of learning. This becomes relevant to understanding how technology integration in teaching English in Czech schools has been influencing the learning process. The exemplary study of English teachers' practices of technology integration should be worth emulating for other areas of teaching, too.

Below follows a summary for each chapter of the thesis.

In *chapter one* I describe the different range of technologies available in European schools, further linking them to the Czech school context identifying its relevance to teaching English⁸ in relation to teachers' practices of technology integration focused on constructing learning.

In *chapter two*, I describe English as a subject and its teaching in the European school context along with teacher's practice of technology integration in class, an extended phenomenological concept. Under this concept, the teacher integrates technology and EFL as new literacy skills on interaction in designing instruction as a knowledge constructing model. This concept accounts for teacher's interactive approaches and practices of technology use in class achieving technology integration practiced to enhancing didactic approach to be

⁸ EFL

developed as a transformative learning process. In this chapter I, too state issues and knowledge gaps as identified both in international and Czech EFL research context concluding the research framework for empirical analysis.

In *chapter three* I discuss the qualitative research methodology. Here I introduce the case study and the methodological foundations of a phenomenological case study design. I specify the procedures e.g. data gathering, and analysis which are based on variable oriented qualitative theme analysis method.

In *chapter four* I elaborate the findings sourced from the study teachers' practices of ICT integration in class. The findings are reported in four exemplary teachers' perceptions regarding their decision whether to use (or not) individual technologies, practices, reflections and individual factors as associated to classroom use of technologies. I synthesize the exemplary teachers' practices on a common framework considering the use of technologies in teaching English within communicative approach on a blended-learning model. Despite common representations, their individual differences are identified in perceptions, practices, reflections and individual factors. In this regard, each case exemplifies her/his practice of technology integration as based on individual approaches, skills, techniques, purposes and functions and thereby differing in principles of learning. I identify exemplary teachers' technology practices primarily based upon these key principles characterized within the communicative approach framework e.g. learning by doing, learning by inquiry, learning by collaborated action and learning by game on trial and error method.

In *chapter five* I discuss the empirical findings in the case studies and conclude the thesis. The findings are discussed in triangulation with the existing research regarding technology in teaching English focused on constructing learning. By presenting exemplary teachers' practices, I inform that limiting technology integration in teaching English in schools of global circles considering the Czech context on transmission of native linguistic system is not an

adequate model. Alternatively, I forward teachers' qualitative pedagogical skills of using technologies as significant to enhancing classroom practices on developing learning skills of communication defined by an intercultural dimension. As such, based on the exemplary teachers' interactive practices, I advocate a possibility of a pattern change in teaching English emphasizing the purpose of addressing intercultural skills learning goals for global citizenship. In conclusion, I suggest the idea of blended approaches which does not restrict technology use merely with CALL on cognition but extends it on phenomenological social construction of knowledge in the English class, developing it as a comprehensive learning process upon meta-cognitive skills

CHAPTER ONE

Information Communication Technologies in European School Context

Regarding technology integration in the teaching of English, from the teacher's perspective, the theory presented in the literature (in chapter two) informs that the intersection of technology⁹ and EFL appear integrated by the teacher therefore leading to didactic practice as a knowledge constructing model. In this regard, these two knowledge elements are inseparable from a teacher's practices. As suggested, chapters one and two are designed to understand technology and the teaching of the English language in the European school education as relevant in order to link it to the Czech context, relating teachers' practice of technology integration for research relevance. Following this plan, in this first chapter, I present technologies as part of the European school educational policy, its concept and the available research literature. The description brings into accounts the context which concisely draw relevance, meaning and practices of technologies in teaching associated to teacher's practice of technology¹⁰ integrated in the English classroom environment concerning Czech schools.

1.1 Definition and Relevance

In the fast developing global cultures, and so in European socio-economies also linking the Czech context as an emerging knowledge-based economy (Brusis, 2005) through increasing digitalization, modern technologies come to people in general and professional encounters with a range of diverse impacts (Kampylis, Punie, & Devine, 2015). In education, technology advances, as a globally enriching sociocultural knowledge media, enters the teaching domain as well as the learning domain for learners, and teachers use them for enhancing the practices

⁹ Technology in this thesis is a collective noun when used in singular form except in other places used in plural form

¹⁰ ICT used as collective noun

(Tour, 2015). As technologies concern directly to subject teachers in their daily encounters on the level of didactic practices, some focused studies have identified them as a scope to exploring their educational potentials in innovative teacher practices. On such pedagogical focus and schemes however, technologies get defined and described in inconsistent ways. Variations come represented in educational concept, policy and research perspectives since each level draws technology integration in teaching and learning a defined school subject linking the teacher's practices in multiple and diverse ways. "Among several anomalies (Arnesen, 2010, p.5)," yet, the main descriptions in this chapter are elaborated with an emphasis on understanding how the European educational policy, concept and research in practice come to define, perceive and suggest the technology integration for the teachers, when teaching a school subject¹¹, as main users or actors to signify, appropriate and use them in classroom teaching.

Among various concepts, for a first definition of information technologies, I cite the given literature as in *Pedagogicky Slovník* (2003) cited in Sedova and Zounek (2008, p.1):

Modern didactic audiovisual technological tools (video, television, data projector) and technologies based on computers and modern telecommunication services enabling their users' maximum access to information and handling information in digitalized/electronic form especially computers, computer software, local computer networks, internet, educational multimedia software distributed on heterogeneous data media.

As listed out in the above extract, technologies are different digital and online devices and tools involved as educational media containing global information which teachers are to use for educational purposes e.g. in teaching a school subject for constructing learning. At this point, though the given definition projects technologies on the scheme of pedagogical use, it still relates basic components only. Apart from these, current literature that brings new pedagogical perspectives has explored various new components, applications, media etc.

¹¹ School subject in this thesis stands for EFL as a school subject in European context unless otherwise referred in other contexts

included in the definition of “technology upon increasing their educational relevance (Selwyn, 2012, p.14-15).” In this regard, in line with Selwyn, I select the below given elements for defining technologies of educational relevance which enter the domain of teaching English. The new editions are as outlined:

Computer hardware systems, simulation systems, personal computing devices, audio-visual devices, games, content-free computer software packages, content-related computer software packages, world wide web content services, internet applications and so on...

From the listed items, it is again specified that technologies are not merely digital devices, but expanded as multi-dimensional knowledge content, items, tools, games, simulations, services, applications, skills etc. which might have a wide range of educational relevance.

Moving a step further, current literature defines technologies as advanced multiple educational forms with multiple functions. In this regard, Harasim (2012), among others, introduces technologies as multidimensional educational components. The author incorporates not only general devices and tools but various new digital, online, and ubiquitous simulations and media that bring global social and cultural thoughts, contexts, skills etc. embedded in education on mediating learning with convergent applications and uses. With the emergence of technologies developed as convergent media, comes associated changing school education systems which trigger multidimensional shifts in the process of school subject teaching and learning as getting through digital pace. Voogt and Knezek (2008) assert, with information technologies evolved as ubiquitous media, structural educational patterns that have been fast shifting into digital and ubiquitous learning systems. This assumption is largely supported in American and European literature and it is evident in their educational reports that inform increasing use of technology in school teaching. Voogt and Knezek (2008) further argue that information technologies in school teaching have been widely spreaded, engaging

developments and, alongside, increasing the role of teachers as crucial to materializing their educational significance in bringing transformation in learning. Adding to such communications one finds educational policy and research reports seeking technology and their use in teachers' classroom practices though adding increasing inconsistencies. Since policy research levels position technologies and issues of integration in teaching a school subject¹² in a wide range of perspectives, understandings, and concepts and that it surfaces due to diverse interests or purposes, on the other hand each one agrees upon the primary role of the teacher.

At this point, as teacher practices are centrally influenced by educational policy, concept and research perspectives, the following descriptions are attempts that draw European educational policy and practices discourses linking Czech educational perspectives involving technologies and integration in teaching a school subject considering the teacher's perspective.

1.2 European Educational Perspectives and Practices on Technology

Grown in significance in digitalizing global cultures, European socio-economic systems, including here the Czech context, are changing fast due to liberalizing knowledge-oriented economic patterns (Brusis, 2005). In these socio-economic cultural milieus, technologies come to people as basic literacy needs. Besides, these components impact people inconsistently in their daily professional encounters, such as teaching professionals engaged in developing school education in the information age (Lawson, Comber, & Taylor, 2016). Several educational manuscripts report that in different ways, as also in different fields, technologies affect the teaching-learning process and teachers' everyday practices in the 21st century digital generations, bringing along the diversity of educational cultures which innovate in today's "knowledge society (Anderson, 2008,p.5)." Despite inconsistent impacts, however,

¹² School subject in this study is interchangeably used to mean general subjects as taught in school from which EFL as a school subject can't be isolated

European educational policy, concept and research levels also linked to Czech educational perspectives bring increasing advocacy upon technology integration in school teaching and one key intent, among others, is to transform teaching-learning process into digital system (Law, Pelgrum, & Plomp, 2006). On this purpose, the issue i.e. technology integration in school education linking teaching a school subject significantly engages European educational policy, concept and research levels which together account for teacher (digital) competence as a major component for increasing technology practice. The different educational policy levels additionally emphasize teacher's digital competence as major element to attain educational potentials of technology use in real class teaching upon enhancing the learning process in addressing digital generations' 21st century learning skills and expectations (Ainley, Enger, & Searle, 2008). 21st century skills are defined in these terms, e.g. communication, collaboration, critical and creativity, employability etc. (Potter, 2016), that a subject teacher addresses, with the technology skills coming embedded in teachers' actions hence innovating educational practices.

In meeting with the changes which come associated with digital education, systems evolved with multiplying needs of multi-skilled digital generations attending European school through digital pace (Glover, 2016), policy and research levels bestow upon growing digital priority. The educational levels also involve increasingly the issue of how to develop technology integration in school education (OECD, 2010; Bates, 2015; Commission, 2013; Carstens & Pelgrum, 2009; OECD, 2014; Tondeur, Braak, & Valcke, 2006; Net, 2013; Grečnerová, 2015; Sedova & Zounek, 2008; Kamylylis et al., 2015). In this regard, the policy and research reports inform of an increasing technology support to European schools in order to develop digital infra-structure and support systems that would help innovating didactic practices. For instance, the European and Czech educational policy documents e.g. Commission

(2013), Commission (2011, p.3) mention, along with structural support, PCs¹³, laptops, tablets, netbooks etc. availed to schools, educators and students. The key intent, as their reports emphasize, is to promote user's competence in achieving technology integration into teaching of a subject, in order to "modernize the learning process for better educational outcomes (Commission, 2013, p.9)."

The educational literature, as concurrent with digital policy perspective alongside, comes adding a notion that growing digital priority is a key element to improving teaching-learning process of school education. In this regard, despite some pedagogical literature, e.g. Tondeur, Braaka, Ertmer, Peggy and Ottenbreit-Leftwich (2017) that sheds light on different components as accountable to developing technology integration in school teaching, digital educational strategy perspective projects this digital system priority as key to innovating educational practices of school teaching-learning systems. The communications in general join Carstens and Pelgrum (2009) who claim, technology use in teaching a school subject as significantly associated to multiplying teacher roles, activating learners, and influencing educational outcomes. Among others, their study maintains that, in innovative school situations, technology use changes the ways of teaching. In such situations, teachers integrate technologies in real class context upon focusing on increasing learning interactions. As a matter of fact, technology integration in school education as aimed at promoting teaching to develop innovative learning process, is a widely engaging phenomenon associated to the fast digitalizing school system in the emerging Europe including Czech educational context (Grečnerová, 2015).

Connected with the increasing digital priorities upon developing digital integration in school system alongside comes linked the issue of teacher competence for a crucial role to effectively practice technologies in class teaching on constructing learning and it is to addressing 21st century learning skills for global citizens (Ba, 2006). The educational research

¹³ Personal computers

papers in general reflect the concept that teachers are to teach digital generations growing with smart-skills in the fast digitalizing school cultures (Dcokstader, 1999). In this regard, pointing at increasing educational transition into digital systems that necessitate technologies in school teaching (Kampylis et al., 2015), is the emphasis of this educational research. Teachers must practice with technologies, not merely to transfer knowledge but also to bring along innovations in the process of teaching and learning a subject. The opinions confer with Anrdroulla Vassiliou in Commission, (2011, p.3), “ICT in school education avail learners and teachers with global skills to attaining better learning outcomes, provided teachers use technologies to enable students with ample exposures and learning opportunities.” As revealed, educational policy and research levels upon growing digital priorities highlight the teacher’s competence as a major role for effectively implementing technology in class and addressing digital generations’ learning skills or aspirations.

Upon growing digital priorities, yet studies report a wide range of inconsistencies regarding teachers’ practices of technology integration in subject teaching, and also in European school contexts, which are described as based on different technological paradigms (Harasim, 2012). In some cases, studies inform teachers’ practices of technology in class as traditionally limited to behaviorist or cognitivist computer-assisted instruction (CAI) paradigms. Whereas in others, teachers in an interactive background are presented as engaged in implementing technologies based on the scheme of improving pedagogical skills that contribute to enhancing classroom practices in exemplary ways (Chigona & Chigona, 2010). In these, teachers don’t only use only general technologies for quantitatively increasing volume of information but integrate interactive media in designing classroom practices that form upon the skills of learning collaboration in which use of technology engages learners in authentic or problem-based activities (Drossel, Eickelmann, & Schulz-Zander, 2017). In such practices, researchers in line with Hauck, Fuchs and Müller-Hartmann (2012) report subject teachers making use of multiple

innovative digital, online and/or ubiquitous media, building upon skills-learning instructions beyond conventional technological paradigms. In this way, with instances of inconsistent teacher practices of technology integration in real class teaching as based on different paradigms and beyond, European educational research then directs attention signaling significance of teacher's digital competence.

Emphasizing the significance of the teacher's role in effectively implementing technology in classroom to enhance teaching-learning practice, educational digital policy literature expresses a growing priority on developing teacher competence(digital), albeit in various oblique ways. The digital priority discourse confers teacher's digital competence as a highly crucial component in achieving technology integration as a tool to develop the process of teaching school subjects (Instefjord & Munthe, 2017). In general, opinions line up with Ferrari (2012) who conforms, digitally skilled teachers use multiple technologies in enhancing access and bring into practice new literacy skills that teaching-learning practices for better learning outcomes. Following the given opinions join European national educational policies such as Czech digital strategy level e.g. Grečnerová (2015,p.7) articulates high priority on "development of teacher-digital competence." The priority discourse as this however, according to Dcokstader (1999) that merely concerns teacher's technological knowledge but ignores educational and pedagogical potentials, and skills that teachers must develop comprehensively on promoting learning interaction in teaching a school subject, is a mechanical perspective. This is that digital policy-oriented view is rather technically limited. Against an inadequacy as this, it is, hence, argued a necessity to adopt a comprehensive perspective that defines teacher's digital competence with a scheme to developing teachers' interactive pedagogical skills for using technologies to enhance teaching-learning practices. This is since, as Kamylyis et al.(2015, p.2) argue, "Digital technologies are enablers of a step change in changing teaching and learning practices. However, they themselves don't guarantee change."

As the digital strategy perspectives reveal, along with the growing digitalization in education and digital priority on a changing school system, policy expectation on the teacher's role grows significantly. It, too signals increasing priority in developing teacher's digital competence accounted as major element that contributes to effective implementation of technology teaching a subject on developing learning process. However, as the discussions signal, educational policy perspectives regarding teacher's digital competence with the goal of achieving technology integration as sought, are instrumentally technology-oriented and far too inconsistent. Thus, what follows is a short description of teacher's competence from comprehensive literature that this study draws for its relevance in the emerging European perspective also linking its relevance in Czech educational context. Besides, as the outlined literature also signals teachers' practice of technology integration as based on inconsistent paradigms and perspectives, following the sketch of teacher competence, a short description informs this component linking technology use in EFL teaching and teacher practices in European and as well Czech context.

1.3 European Framework on Teacher (digital) Competence

Along with the growing priority on technology integration for innovating teaching-learning practices of changing school education that stages within the emerging knowledge-based European sociocultural contexts (Anderson, 2008), priority on developing teacher (digital) competence increases quite a lot (OECD, 2013). However, concerning the meaning of teacher competence, equally inconsistent perspectives capture this issue. In this regard, educational digital-policy perspectives (OECD, 2013) project teacher competence instrumentally in view of teacher's operating knowledge of digital devices. Whereas, pedagogical views, on the other hand, inform teacher competence in concepts, knowledge, skills and practices of teacher appropriating technologies as globally connecting sociocultural

knowledge tools and media on constructing learning process. As pedagogical view is the major concern of this study, it is here outlined starting with a short reflection on instrumental view.

Lined up with digital strategy-oriented communications, teacher (digital) competence comes projected instrumentally in views of teacher's mechanical knowledge or expertise operating digital devices or media in class. On this perspective, the views come aligned with Stensaker, Maassen, Borgan, Oftebro and Karseth (2007) who highlight teacher's knowledge of today's digital devices entering the school class in multiple numbers. Going even further, digital views even come demandingly as forwarded by Mioduser, Nachmias and Forkosh-Baruch (2008). These authors emphasize the teacher's knowledge for using technologies e.g., navigating the info-space, communication literacy, visual literacy, hyperacy (ability to deal with digital media as consumers or producers), personal information management, coping with complexity and so on. As the listed features reveal, the digital strategy perspective projects teacher (digital) competence mainly in view of teacher's technological or operating skills of using digital devices in classroom teaching. At this point, digitally driven views, following Dcokstader (1999) reduce the teacher's knowledge, and so leading to merely mechanical practice of teaching or education and hence, yielding mechanical learning outcomes.

In contrast to instrumental concepts, comprehensive educational perspectives explore teacher's competence in different ways. The comprehensive literature, that too follows European framework e.g. Redecker and Punie (2017) highlights teacher competence in teacher's interactive pedagogical concepts, critical and creative skills and actions of appropriating technologies as defined for innovating subject teaching-learning practices. In this perspective, teacher's digital skills are embodied in interactive actions of using a wide range of technologies as innovative educational tools, media environments on enhancing classroom practices that develop as ubiquitous learning processes (Harasim, 2012). Tour (2015) argues that a teacher with interactive digital skills uses innovative technologies in class by bringing

subject knowledge embedded in real social and cultural concepts, contexts, media and skills in practices modelled as skills-integrated learning processes.

Following the given line of thought, the scholars point to a need for the emerging European educational context to interlink various skills that impact the didactic and media potentials for developing teacher (digital) competence in an interactive framework. In this regard, Ferari (2012) projects digital competence on teacher's confident and critical use of information society technology (IST) for work, leisure, and communication as basic, along with skills to operate digital devices of multimodal technologies integrated to everyday job of teaching. According to this framework Ferari (2012,p.12) lists these skills as most important,

Use of computers to retrieve, assess, produce, present and exchange information, communicate and participate in collaborative networks via the internet.

Similarly, European Parliament and Council (2006) in Ferari (2012, p.12) adds that teacher digital competence in skills for solving problems are both pedagogical and technological, apart from effectively communicating both in media and in blended channels, therefore able to manage information. In this way, teachers' skills to collaborate, create and share content, and build knowledge interactively using digital, online and ubiquitous media or channels are incorporated to the development of the teacher competence. Likewise, Rowan et al.(2001) present a list of interactive skills in projecting teacher (digital) competence in teacher's pedagogical knowledge, skills and practices of digital technologies integrated in subject curriculum as implemented in class. Implementation of curriculum in digital system entails multidisciplinary course content, concepts, contexts, cultures, skills integrated to enhancing teaching in real context. Within this model, several scholars such as Graham, Borup and Smith, (2012), Alayyar, Fisser and Voogt (2012) develop teacher digital competence skills of teachers media practicing and didactic actions as a collaborative framework. The sources assume that a digitally competent teacher innovates teaching practices that contribute to

extending learning beyond class as supported by online and ubiquitous media blended with classroom-based activities. Practices as these enable digital generations of 21st century smart-school education system to enhance multi-literacy skills (Oxford & Graham, 1993). To the extents as sought, thus, comprehensive pedagogical literature in line with European framework which emphasizes people's confident and critical skills of technology use for employment, learning, self-development and participation in knowledge society, concludes teacher's digital competence in the following terms as disseminated by Redecker and Punie (2017,p.4):

Ability to access digital media and ICT, to understand and critically evaluate different aspects of digital media and media content and to communicate effectively in a variety of context.

In addition to the signaled importance of critical skills for confident use of technologies, the European framework relating teacher (digital) competence further incorporates skills of privacy, safety, ethical issues, creativity and meta-cognitive skills on using digital media in creating and using the content availed to be appropriated in relation to real context. This too includes teachers' collaborative skills of using technologies for enhancing classroom practices. The collaborative perspective which highlights teacher's critical and creative attitude and skills of using technologies to achieving their educational potentials (Horn, 2011), come intriguingly to researchers seeking to study school teachers' practice of technology integration in the English class.

Education researchers in English teaching, in line with Godwin Jones (2010) treating collaborative perspective, describe teacher (digital) competence in constructive perceptions, knowledge and skills of the teacher being able to appropriate multiple offline, digital, e-language software and online or www learning media for building instructions as collaborative knowledge constructing models. According to this analysis, a teacher uses multimodal technologies for teaching English within communicative approaches. And this is achieved

through classroom methods e.g. content and language integrated learning¹⁴ methods (Europe, 2000), problem-based methods (Yoon, 2016), online-blended learning methods (Ansarimoghaddam & Tan, 2012) etc. which extend computer supported collaborative learning¹⁵ or (social) constructivist computer assisted language learning¹⁶ model (Warscheur,1997).

In short, as the discussions reveal, in contrast to digitally confined view of teacher competence limited to the skills of operating digital technologies, the comprehensive perspective teacher (digital) competence develops through interactive pedagogical concepts, knowledge, skills, integrating multi-modal media to innovate the subject didactic practices within the collaborative learning framework. However, as the previous outlined descriptions states, while projecting teacher digital competence on inconsistent perspectives, it also suggests technology practice as based on different paradigms in action. These are outlined in short descriptions below.

1.4 Technology Practices as Based on Different Paradigms

Regarding technology integration in education linking teaching a school subject Selwyn (2012), Harasim (2012), Dede (2008) etc. inform teachers' practices as based on different educational theories or paradigms. Amongst several, some practices are characterized with structural, psychological or cognitivist concepts, whereas others are constructivist or social constructivist, and connectivist or 21st century learning paradigm and so on. In order to explain them, the studies borrow a key idea that technology practices based on different paradigms are relative terms modelled by, and also synonym of, educational theories which guide teachers' classroom practices and use of technologies. In different educational paradigms, a teacher

¹⁴ CLIL

¹⁵ CSCL

¹⁶ CALL

appropriates technologies in different types, concepts, ways and systems to fulfil different needs. In this regard, following the educational literature as in Harasim (2012), I briefly outline technology integration in practice, as elaborated below, asserting the main paradigms in teaching a school subject in European school, linking to Czech context. These are:

Computer assisted instruction¹⁷ (1960s), intelligent tutoring system¹⁸ (1970s), logos and computer supported collaborative learning¹⁹ (1980s), online collaborative learning paradigm (1990s and 21st century) (Harasim, 2012, p.14).

A brief recap on these paradigms is as follows:

1) Computer assisted instruction (1960s): developed in the 1960s, this paradigm consists of the main technologies in use e.g., Sydney Pressy's testing machine and Skinner's teaching machine. It is named programmed instruction (Voogt & Knezek, 2008). The main practices within this model involve the use of interactive computer television and personal computer with 'drill and practice,' 'electronic page turning' etc. As for teaching English, the computer assisted language learning features the computer assisted instruction paradigm, which the teachers practice in school across several global circles e.g. in European school also including in the Czech context. Uses of technologies in this behaviorist model make up a structural approach as practiced in audio-lingual, translation etc. methods (Murphy, 2007).

2) Intelligent tutoring system: marked the 1970s, these technologies and practices are mentioned in this paradigm e.g., Charles Babbage's analytic vision engine, multi-purpose computer practiced with artificial intelligence instruction systems. In English teaching, this paradigm represents communicative instructions in cognitive computer assisted language learning model. Main uses of computer in this system are limited to spelling check, grammar check, games on simulations and language programs etc. This inductive approach to teaching

¹⁷ CAI

¹⁸ ITS

¹⁹ CSCL

replaces formal approach for communicative learning (Warschauer & Healey, 1998). Thus, it is labelled partly cognitive and also communicative paradigm, as the most practiced models for teaching English in European school (North, 2007).

3) Logos and computer supported collaborative learning paradigm: evolved in 1980s and onwards, this paradigm brings a shift in education, from transmission to learning by construction (Piaget's model) and interaction (Vygotsky) (Harasim, 2012). The teacher in this model uses various technologies in various ways developing a collaborative construction framework, involving uses of e.g., logo programming, hypercard or construction kits, micro-worlds system, email or learning networks, blackboard, moodle, online learning media integrated. This paradigm²⁰ in English teaching is characterized in teacher's practice of multimodal technologies and media, designing instructions based on communicative approaches e.g. content and language integrated learning²¹, task-based, problem-based, blended-learning etc. methods extended on (social) constructivist paradigm (Warschauer, 2010).

As revealed from the recap, teachers' practices of technology are based on different paradigms practiced in European schools and linked to the Czech context. Amongst these, the first two are called conventional paradigms whereas the third is called developmental, as it regards teachers' practice of technology integration in English class (Godwin-Jones, 2010).

1.5 Concluding

With the purpose to understand technology integration in subject teaching e.g. EFL in European schools, including in the Czech context, linking teacher practices from educational policy and research perspective, the outlined literature informs that technology use is growing

²⁰ CSCL

²¹ CLIL

in priority and significance. Following the priorities, not only general technologies, but a wide range of online and ubiquitous media are entering the teaching and learning process in education in the fast-changing European knowledge society (Anderson, 2008) where school education is modernized through and on a digital pace. So, in a fast digitalizing school system, educational policy, research and practice levels engage largely in the issue of technology integration which is conceptualized for developing school teaching systems. The goal as the literature bases assert is to enable subject teachers to maximize use of technology for the purpose of modernizing the process of teaching and learning. However, in real contexts, a wide range of inconsistencies have been reported regarding teachers' practices of technology integration in real class. While following the reports of individual inconsistencies, the literature also exhibits the role of the teacher (digital) competence as majorly accountable to innovating didactic practices in class through which technology integration develops into a learning process, albeit adding still further inconsistent views, perspectives and understandings.

Agreeing upon the significance of teacher role, European educational policy and research levels express a growing priority upon developing teacher (digital) competence. The policy and research levels, however capture this issue in quite a range of inconsistent perspectives. In this regard, educational digital strategy levels limit teacher competence in teacher's skills for operating digital media in which various interconnected pedagogical dimensions are yet undermined. Whereas, in contrast, comprehensive pedagogical literature as based on European framework projects teacher (digital) competence comes in teacher's comprehensive pedagogical concepts, skills of critically and creatively appropriating a wide range of multimodal technologies to enhancing classroom practice to develop it as a skill learning process. This view projects competence in teachers' qualitative actions or skills and cultural theme of appropriating technologies in classroom practices designed as collaborative learning practices as based on (social) constructivist paradigm.

Besides, as the descriptions inform, along with teacher digital competence developed on inconsistent perspectives, technology integration has been inconsistent with teachers' practices extended on different educational paradigms. The literature informs that the practices are based on three main paradigms e.g. computer assisted instruction, intelligent tutorial system and computer supported collaborative learning. This way, following the European educational perspectives and practices also linking Czech educational context, it is a point of departure that in the fast digitalizing European school system, technologies are growing in significance, despite the equal or even essential role of subject teacher competence in modernizing the process of teaching and learning. The point is that comprehensively developed teacher competence is essential to acquiring state-of-the-art technology integration in teaching a school subject to develop it as a skill learning process (Ainley, Enger, & Searle. 2008). From this point of view, it is argued that that teachers on limited perspectives e.g. on behaviorist or cognitivist paradigm limit the practices of technologies to practice of mechanical education. In contrast, teachers in interactive perspectives practice technologies upon the scheme of increasing learning interactions that contribute to developing technology integration in teaching a school subject as a learning process. Hence, it is essential to explore this phenomenon in comprehensive pedagogical perspective such that extend within phenomenological model or also featured with social construction paradigm. Within the phenomenological framework, it will be clear later, teachers integrate interactive media and technologies in teaching English on communicative skills focus as defined with cultural dimensions.

At this point, as this is the study of English teacher's practice of technology integration in teaching English in Czech school context, a focused description on this subject is required. Thus, what follows in chapter two is the description of English teaching including its

technology that will be relevant to study teachers²² practice from European and as well as Czech educational policy and research perspective.

²² EFL teachers

CHAPTER TWO

Teaching English in the European School Education Context

For research purposes, meaning to study technology integration in teaching English in Czech elementary schools from teacher perspective, this chapter describes English as a school subject, its teaching practice including technology under the account of teachers' practices in the European school context. The descriptions tell us about the relevance, meaning of learning and teaching of English from the European education policy and practices focused on research perspectives. As relevant to this research, the chapter also describes teacher's practice regarding technologies in the English classroom as drawn from theoretical perspectives. In this regard, this study centers on the phenomenological concept of social construction as a theoretical framework to, then, further explore exemplary teachers' practices that foster the development of technology integration as a learning process tool. The last part in this chapter describes these phenomena by drawing upon the Czech school context where this research was staged. The descriptions lead to identify the research gap linking Czech school English teachers practices of technology use in classroom. The chapter is concluded with a suggesting central research question to be addressed as elaborated in the third chapter, which refers to the methodology of phenomenological case-studies.

2.1 English in Relevance and its Study in European School

Having emerged along with a globalizing socio-economic and socio-cultures as an international lingua franca, English in the fast digitalizing global circles (Murray, 2012) and in the European school context, is a significant foreign language practiced on multi-prospective communication uses (Berns et al., 2007). Projected along with growing global communication needs in changing socio-economic contexts (Berns et al., 2007, p.41), learning English in

European schools, also linking to the Czech context, is practiced variously on different patterns from the practiced in native schools (Howatt & Smith, 2014). In this context, in view of English as an expanding subject of study for communication skills with socio-economic prospects, purposes and implications, educational concept, policy and practice levels, capture this phenomenon though projecting it in inconsistent perspectives (Luis, Lopez, Porto, & Aljendra, 2014). In this regard, though variously defined, the emerging European education policy and research perspectives come agreeing with Byram (2008) who constructs foreign language as a transformative phenomenon on cultural dimensions. According to Byram (2008), foreign language comes to the other-native people via channel channels, formal or informal such as; schools, economies, technologies, media etc. due to any social, economic, cultural, political reasons. In light of this, it is generally agreed that English in other-native circles as a foreign language (Hyte, 2008) is constructed in skills of communication as practiced in real social and (inter)cultural contexts. The practices of this subject in cultural contexts bring English interactively integrated with the emerging contexts, media, skills, techniques and technology systems etc. as interrelated constituents of culture on transformation in substitute of language limited in textual forms (Wang, Zou, Wang, & Xing, 2013).

In the fast globalizing European school education, the meaning of English is guided by political and practical implications. The political discourse e.g. (Byram, Gribkova, & Starkey, 2002; Byram, 1997; Byram, 2008) mentions English as a school subject for learning on a key purpose and it is to enhance communication skills defined by cultural dimensions seeking its use in developing global citizenship, though understood in various ways leading to inconsistencies in the matter of both learning and its educational outcomes. In this regard, as Crystal (2003) informs, English as a global language develops into world Englishes which gets captured in different patterns and purposes of learning that guide teacher's practices diversely

across cultures. In some settings, English is practiced as a common lingua franca²³ (Modern & Journal, 2016) in others, it is a language of special purpose²⁴ (Laborda, 2010). Whereas, in the largest part of Global settings, and so in Europe, English is learned and taught in schools as a foreign language (Johnson, 2008) where it develops new complexities as related to learning, teaching and teacher practices that differ on differing educational perspectives (Qian, 2016). In the view of English²⁵ increasing its significance along with a growing complexity in the emerging European context however, cultural dimension to teaching English is positioned as a comprehensive learning framework. Studies on this framework signal the process of learning and teaching English that are innovated in practical actions and on diverse implications, be it academically among others.

Drawing teaching English as a school subject in the fast digitalizing European cultures in the aftermath of expansion events and emerging socio-economic changes (Kramersch, 2008), new educational perspectives capture this phenomenon on increasing significance, though reporting quite a lot of inconsistencies on the level of teaching and learning or real classroom practices (Scholl, 2008; Little, 2014; Johnson, 2008). Following new perspectives, studies inform that teaching English in several European schools as still limited to transmission of formal grammar information from the native English texts. In contrast, studies as following the common European framework on languages (Broeder & Martyniuk, 2008) that posts English as a common lingua franca in European nationals (EN, 2003), also signify learning this subject in prospect of developing intercultural communication skills for global citizenship (Byram, 2008). On this plan, the main emphasis is lent for teaching English upon communication skills focus on intercultural communicative competence²⁶ as required for global citizens to effectively

²³ LF

²⁴ ESP

²⁵ EFL

²⁶ ICC

participate in global intercultural contexts on multiple career prospects (Nekvapil & Sherman, 2009).

Following intercultural communicative competence as an emerging global (Murray, 2012; Kachru, 2006; Howatt & Smith, 2014) and European framework of learning English as a foreign language (Cenoz, 2000; Europe, 2000; Byram, 1997; Coleman, 2006), the educational literature informs of varying perspectives and complexities added to teaching this subject and teacher practices which is sought on the scheme of transforming the learning process. As an example of complexity, Johnson (2008) describes a case of five learners of English for five different purposes and hence, five different teachers teaching in different methods.

Pertinent to justification of growing complexity in teaching English, as guided by intercultural communicative competence (Liaw & Bunn-Le Master, 2010) related to the development of global citizenship (Matsuda, 2003) joins some research communications.²⁷ In this connection and in line with Oxford (2008), researchers such as Gardner (2008) capture teaching English and teacher practices as based on “inconsistent approaches or designs.” In teachers’ inconsistent teaching practices, technologies are used identically either on conventional computer assisted model or in contrast (social) constructivist computer supported collaborative learning paradigm (Lund, 2003, p.65),” or beyond paradigms as innovative skills learning models.

Relating inconsistencies in teachers’ practices of teaching English, some research views²⁸ on mechanistic focus express skepticism regarding English within Europe as a common Lingua Franca (EN, 2003, p.127) learnt with a goal of enhancing communication skills defined in the theme of intercultural dimension (Martin, 2015). However, research on comprehensive focus still signifies intercultural dimension to teaching English arguing its significance for

²⁷ EFL research

²⁸ EFL research

transforming teachers²⁹ practices. Researchers such as Kramsch and Thorne (2001), Economy (2006), Coleman (2006) see intercultural dimensions to teaching English as associated to enhancing teachers' approaches, methods, techniques and technologies into enhancing classroom practices to develop as skills learning process. At this point, following the comprehensive literature that takes the emerging European school context into consideration, teaching English including teachers' practice are to develop with intercultural communicative competence goal as a transformative discourse on learning. As the field research still signals inconsistencies regarding teaching and teacher practices within European school also linking English in Czech school context (Nekvapil & Sherman, 2009) as based on different approaches, some main teaching approaches in practice are shortly outlined hereafter.

2.2 English Teaching Approaches

Following the research communications that signal inconsistent features of teaching English in European school contexts, in which teachers practice classroom instructions within different approaches to language as based on different educational paradigms, I represent the practices in three broad categories. These are termed: grammatical approaches, communicative competence approaches and intercultural communicative competence approaches, described below.

2.2.1 Grammatical Approaches

Several researchers e.g. Yassaei (2012), Chang (2011), Matsuda (2003), Garcia and Pena, (2011) report teaching English in several situations in schools across European in line with global contexts on grammatical approaches in practice. In these practices, teachers form instructions explicitly on linguistic focus. Conceptually, this practice is guided by the concept

²⁹ EFL teacher

of language as a verbal form or structural entity as in pre-Chomsky's linguistic research. Later followed by Chomsky's Universal Grammar knowledge (Hauser, Chomsky, & Fitch, 2002). The former concept informs language as a composition of discrete verbal aspects (Chomsky, 1959) whereas the latter, holds language as a composition of blocks of structures on lexical, syntax rules (Antony & Hornstein, 2003). Following these concepts that emphasize language on verbal aspects to be memorized (Fitch, Hauser, & Chomsky, 2005) a teacher is limited to the role of disseminating drill practices for learners to memorize (Richards & Rodgers, 2014). As such, the instructions are framed on audio-lingual, grammar-translation methods with formal assessment (Nattinger, 2016) and the goal here is knowledge of English with accuracy (Chang, 2011). On this goal, Yassaei(2012), Chang (2011), Garcia and Pena, (2011) show that even though teachers work in digitalizing school systems, yet they limitedly use modern technologies of audio-visual drill based on conventional practices. Research informs that such technology practices as limited to psychological use such as controlling learner's behaviors leads to practice memorization of the language. Thus, paradigmatically, English teaching and teacher practices as these are represented as replicative of behavioristic and cognitivist computer assisted language learning models (Terrell, 1991).

2.2.2 Communicative Approaches

In several global and European school contexts, some researchers (Mayor & Swann, 2002; Hong, Chen, & Lan, 2014; Cerezo, Baralt, Suh, & Leow, 2013; Petrie & Avery, 2011; Romero & Manjarres, 2016) report English teaching practiced within either functional or communicative competence-based approaches. In such practices, several new perspectives and features related to teaching include changing goals, content, medium of teaching and classroom methods and technologies. In communicative approach, teaching is guided by the concept of language as a semantic system, in which verbal and grammatical aspects as bases, are used in

a context of language function. This concept adds functionality to language learning into interpersonal exchanges of information as in Hymes's (1971) communicative competence (CC) for use in specified contexts. Brown (2006, p.196) observes, “on communicative competence framework, teacher³⁰ forms instruction on conversational patterns enabling learners to convey and interpret messages and negotiate meanings interpersonally within specific contexts.” In this model, as Brown (2006) in line with the scholars e.g. (Widdowson, 1979; Savignon, 1983; Bachman, 1990; Michael Canale & Swain, 1980) asserts that English teachers practice activity-based instructions with a communicative competence goal in view of which it is composed of grammatical, discourse, sociolinguistic and strategic competences as the main pillars of language with meaningful functional skills of “pragmatic use (Bachman, 2003, p. 43).”

In the interactive instructions, the teacher attempts to integrate language in skills e.g. speaking, listening, reading and writing and strategic skills-based practices built in the use of new technologies and topics of learner’s interest. Romero and Manjarres, (2016) inform that an English teacher, making use of communicative competence focus integrates various activities as active reading, writing, conversing, question-answers among others, in meaning shared contexts for learners to interact via digital media use to communicate messages. Within this framework different communicative methods are reported in practice. Functional notional method, situational method, language-skills based method, oral method, direct method are some examples as supported by balanced use of technologies (Tarvin & Al-arishi, 2016).

In communicative approaches as described, researchers such as Hong, Chen and Lan (2014), Cerezo et al.(2013), Petrie and Avery (2011), Romero and Manjarres (2016) explored English teacher expanding the use of technologies from a level of controlling the class to a stage involving the class into using language, for example watching videos, listening to audios,

³⁰ EFL teacher

completing writing or reading, speaking in groups in meaningful ways. Paradigmatically, teaching and teacher practices in communicative competence approach with emphasis on conversation analysis, extend on cognitivist and partly constructivist paradigm (Richards & Roger, 2014) also called computer assisted language learning on cognition/communication model (Warschauer, 2010).

2.2.3 Intercultural Communicative Competence Approaches

In contrast to teaching English in grammatical or limitedly communicative approaches (Kramsh, 2008), researchers Lewis, Chanier, and Youngs (2011), Nielson (2011) Kozar (2010), Rhoades (2013), Fotos (2004), Godwin-jones (2008) present intercultural communicative competence³¹ approaches practiced within the European school contexts. Expanding on (social) construction, intercultural approaches designed with phenomenological concept construct language in social and cultural practices of communications as based on comprehensive knowledge constructing principles. In this approach, studies report teachers as engaged in forming class practices within collaborative learning designs, integrating technology, language (English) and learners in constructing meaning within learning tasks as cultural practices and interactions (Byram, 2008). Within intercultural framework as composed of multiple competences e.g. communicative, networking etc. competences (Van Ek, 1986), English classroom practices are conducted for learning metacognitive skills e.g. “comprehending, interpreting, critiquing, evaluating, creating, adapting, assimilating etc. skills (Fantini, 2009, p.456).”

Regarding intercultural model, several issues need yet to be refined in teaching English as a school subject (Martin, 2015), scholars e.g. Nielson (2010), Kozar (2010), Rhoades (2013),

³¹ ICC

Guichon (2010) capture instructions³² designed as multi-approach communication learning models in addressing intercultural competence³³ for global citizenships. Among others, the following examples of teaching method listed are mainly in this framework. These are: content and language integrated method, task-based method (Brown, 2006, p.242; Richards & Renandya, 2002, p.5-6), e-media based corpus approaches (Campiyo-Cubilo, Belles-Frotuno, & Valor-Gea, 2010) as extended on social constructivist computer supported collaborative learning paradigm (Warschauer, 2010). In these practices, Warschauer (1997) noted that the teacher actively integrates hyper-media sources, online platforms and other tools, used as affordances for learners to practice English not only in writing texts but authoring, evaluating and researching metacognitive skills for transformation. Also, Brown (2006, p.231-232) mentions that in the scheme of intercultural competence, a teacher develops instructions on multi-thematic topics that engage learners to practice pragmatic skills of English such as registers, styles etc. These instructions engage teacher as collaborator with learners on mediating roles. In teaching English upon intercultural focus, Warschauer (1998, p.40) also adds, "Teacher is not the sage on stage but a guide on the side."

In regard to technology integration in class within intercultural communicative competence approaches it will also be clear in the section on phenomenological concept below that researchers in line with Godwin-Jones (2010) explore multimodal online technologies used to bringing English integrated with activities that contribute to enhancing collaborative skills learning as framed on blended model. For example, van Lier (1996) depicts that teachers practicing intercultural skills focused on phenomenological concept uses technologies in teaching English based on the skills of collaboration, being it one method of learning, as a process of social construction. In collaborative learning model, researchers find teacher working with diverse technologies used to engaging learners in problem-solving activities that

³² EFL instructions

³³ EFL as a school subject

construct language with awareness, autonomy and authenticity (Godwin-Jones, 2010). In such practices, scholars in line with e.g. Idris and Ghani (2012), Kaur, Ganapathy and Sidhu (2012), Li, Snow, Jiang and Edwards (2014) report an increasing use of social media (Fotos, 2004) as helpful to innovating classroom practices in that learning extends beyond with the use of online media (Warschauer, 2000).

Following these descriptions regarding the approaches reported from European school contexts for teaching English for this study of technology integration from the teacher's perspective, it is described below the teachers³⁴ practices of technology integration in English class³⁵ drawn from a theoretical literature in perspective. In this regard, first teachers' practices of technologies for teaching English³⁶ are shortly recapped from conventional theoretical models followed by phenomenological concept which this study centers as the main theoretical framework.

2.3 English Teachers' Approaches to Technology Use in the English Class

As a study of technology integration in teaching English from the teacher's perspective, this study seeks to explore the phenomenon on complexity which it explores in exemplary teachers' pedagogical experiences i.e. perceptions, practices and reflections within phenomenological case-study design. To this end, the main purpose in this section is to inform about technology integration in teaching English as a phenomenological concept that develops educational phenomenon hand in hand with subjective epistemology extended on educational principles of (social) construction. On this foundation, technology³⁷ integration in English class is explored associated to the teacher's interactive pedagogical approaches, perceptions, interpretations, skills on the use of technologies in developing learning processes. However,

³⁴ EFL teacher

³⁵ EFL class

³⁶ EFL

³⁷ ICT

following the research reports informing various paradigmatic designs in which technology use as limited to mechanistic purposes still practiced in European school contexts, I first briefly recap the conventional models. This will be followed by elaborating the phenomenon as developed within the phenomenological epistemological foundations or designs. Being specifically depicting technology in teaching English from the teacher's perspective, among different educational paradigms, as Lund (2003) categorizes, teachers' practices are characterized in three main epistemological models. These are based on behaviorist, cognitivist and (social) constructivist paradigms. Among these, a phenomenological concept with subjective epistemology and/or (social) constructivist principles, the technology integration in class develops in practitioners' subjective interactive approaches increasing the learning interactions.

Below, in the next two paragraphs, I reflect on conventional models followed by the descriptions of technology integration in English class developed on subjective and (social) constructivist phenomenological epistemology. The reflection on conventional model lends a departure to exploring this phenomenon within phenomenological epistemological concept designs adopted as the main theoretical framework for this study.

2.3.1 Technology Integration on Conventional Models

Technology integration in teaching English under a behaviorist model still in practice in many situations (Lund, 2003) builds stimulus in the teacher's practice of instruction and reinforcement principles (Chomsky, 1959) for language in verbal and formal entity (Phillips, 1971). Following this perspective, teacher practices instructions on audio-lingual paradigm in which technologies are used as extrinsic-psychological elements reinforcing learner's habit to verbal-formal aspects (Liddell & Garrett, 2004). In this model, as Murphy (2007) describes, the English teacher limited to an expert role concerning the use of computer for drill practices

focused on transferring lexical and syntactic components. Likewise, as reports Lee (2016) in this model research practice limits to assessing teacher's use of technologies limited to transferring of verbal elements of English such as assessing teaching reading of conventional letter cards on computer.

The other model of practice regarding technologies in teaching English is characterized conventional cognitivist paradigm. This practice is guided by the given main discourses defining language. One discourse defines language in acquiring grammar rules as building blocks within Chomsky's universal grammar model (Fitch et al., 2005). The other discourse develops language with Krashen's (1987) comprehensible input or natural order (Schütz, 2005). The third, following Del Hymes' communicative competence discourse (Hymes, 1971) defines language for meaningful use or in conversations (Kurnia, 2010). Following these outlined discourses defining language with an objective meaning in which language and technologies are conceptualized as two discrete elements, the research and likewise teacher practice in these perspectives, limit to explore the use of technology on cognitivist model as characterized with intelligent computer tutoring system (Warschauer & Healey, 1998). Following these concepts, as Warschauer (2000) informs, teacher³⁸ as limited to the role of knowledge instructor, though using multi-modal computer, yet remains mainly as a source of/or medium to communicate information about language of its syntactic and semantic aspects. Likewise, Liang (2010) relays the use of technologies in English class as explicitly limited to conversational discourse. The researcher reports on English teachers as using computer to mediate learning defined in simple conversation skills acquired. Though described as mechanical and conventional models of teaching and practice of technology integration, as Arnesen (2010) highlights, these models are still largely in practice in European schools and quite common in global circles (Hauck et al., 2012; Danan, 2006; Matsuda, 2003; Garcia & Pena, 2011; Romero & Manjarres, 2016).

³⁸ EFL teacher

2.3.2 Technology Integration on Phenomenological Model

In contrast to conventional computer assisted language learning practices as still inadequate models in addressing communication skills (Warschauer, 2010), scholars have started to explore technology integration in teaching English on phenomenological epistemological model for developing classroom practices within intercultural communicative approach framework. This model of teacher practice extends on social constructivist paradigms (Godwin-Jones, 2010). Within the phenomenological concept lending subjective and (social) constructivist epistemology for teaching English within intercultural skills focused on communicative approaches as contributed by (Long, 1985; van Lier, 1996 ; Gass, 2003; Lantolf & Thorne, 2002; Michael Canale (1983), researchers explore technology integration in teacher's qualitative behavior and cultural themes of teaching and as well using technologies that enable learners to construct language practicing communication skills based on intercultural dimensions. In this sense, the phenomenological model technology integration develops as a learning process on its complexity in teacher's qualitative pedagogical skills and cultural themes of using technologies on constructing learning.

At the philosophical level, phenomenological concept constructs meaning of language in practice of communications in real social and cultural contexts (Phillips, 1971). As such, language gets defined beyond textual structure into cultural symbols, tools and technologies as cultural artifacts (John-Steiner & Mahn, 1996) drawing which (foreign) language learning (acquisition) comes suggested in subjective and social constructivist epistemology. Through epistemology, technologies and language on intersection are integrated as new literacy skills mediating language to construct in the practitioners, or learners' participative actions of communication framed in the instructions as based on problem solving or blended learning models that extend within activity system (Engeström, 1999; van Lier, 1996).

Within the activity system related to the phenomenological approach as guided by a concept, “knowledge is a social construction of mind (Pring, 2000, p.251),” the language pedagogical research projects technology integration in English class based on an intent of enhancing meta-cognitive skills of communication (Wertsch, 1993), though accounted with varying perspectives. In this regard, some studies inform English teacher’s use of technologies as focused on increasing learning motivation, others report teacher practices extended to increase the role of users, such as learners and teachers, on constructing language through skills of intercultural communication. Regarding the user roles on construction, among different dimensions, some scholars forward technology integration supporting Davis's (1989) Technology Acceptance Model (TAM) that accounts for the role of user’s perceptions, as usefulness, ease, acceptance of technologies, as means of enhancing technology integration in class teaching. Contemporary researchers Rahimi and Author (2011) also develop this phenomenon of technology integration in English class within teacher’s phenomenological experiences exploring individual’s interactive pedagogical perceptions and principles in substitute of merely technology-oriented perceptions, principles, and practices.

Following such phenomenological model, not only perceived ease in using technologies but also, as Kaur, Ganapathy and Sidh (2012) argue, teacher’s interactive pedagogical perceptions or approaches, and skills for using technologies as innovative educational media on constructing learning, play a major role to developing technology integration in class as a learning process. Following this argument, phenomenological model comes pictured as a comprehensive approach. However, as scholars in line with Warschauer (2010) claim, teachers’ practice of technology integration is still not much a researched phenomenon under a phenomenological epistemological model. For example, Rahimi and Author (2011) relay research in which technology integration in English class develops in teachers’ qualitative behaviors, as in pedagogical approaches or perceptions, interpretations, experiences, practices

and cultural themes of using technologies with skills learning focus, is still slim. Hence, as a focused study on English teachers' practice of technology integration in class, what follows is a brief description of phenomenological epistemological approach on (social) construction which this study centers as the main theoretical framework.

Phenomenological approach or model with subjective epistemology in (social) construction is far exhaustingly contributed and advocated by van Lier (1996) and colleagues as a major theoretical concept of practical significance in developing didactic practice of teaching English defined upon the skills of intercultural communication focus. van Lier's line (1996) forwards phenomenological epistemology supporting the key argument from Long (1985), Long and Porter (1985), Lantolf in Coughlan and Duff (1994) and colleagues who claim teaching English as a foreign language, as limited to linguistic concept, is an inadequate model of addressing communication skills. Taking this assumption further, van Lier (1996) and colleagues extend the concept as an interactive foundation for communicative approach in which meaning of foreign language constructs in social and intercultural practices of communication (Phillips, 1971; Watson-Gegeo, 2004). These sources stress, guided by intercultural practices of communication as key feature of phenomenological concept, that teacher integrates technologies and English as new social and cultural knowledge tools intersected for enhancing classroom practices to develop innovative-skills learning models. For instance, scholars in line with Moyal-sharrock (2009) claim that with phenomenological concept English teacher learns to integrate language and technologies as embedded in new cultural skills that mediate learning to construct in the practitioners' interactive actions of integration or use of both components in real contexts.

Exploring further technology integration in English class, literature on phenomenological approach design develops this phenomenon in ways and teachers' skills of using technologies on increasing learning interactions that promote skills of collaboration upon

problem-solving purposes and activities. In this scheme, van Lier (1996, p. 14) relays, "...teacher on regular basis comes to class with new materials and technologies used to bring along new problems." Adding a step further, the author lends idea that teacher stimulates students to interact, communicate and construct ideas upon solving the problems posed. In problem-posed practices, teacher along with increasing learning interactions, explores new technology skills in exploring new instructional strategies which as Voogt and Knezek (2008) assert, contribute to developing teacher's digital and professional competence. Teacher in developing competence, as the studies confer, creates and uses new pedagogical concepts and skills of using technologies not only to increase input of language in texts but create new affordances to inventing new instructional strategies on constructing learning as a skill developing practice (van Lier, 2000). In this practice, not only technology is used in digital or online media, television etc. types, but also, teacher attempts new ways or skills of using different materials or technologies that promote learning to construct in learners' intrinsic motivation (Ryan & Deci, 2000).

Regarding teacher's ways and skills of using technologies to enhance practices of English teaching to develop skills learning process, van Lier (2003) in Kalaja and Barcelos (2003) compares teacher's actions with a chess players' skills, practices and reflectivity. In this situation, the players' interactive ways of playing, as creative thinking skills, reflecting, and playing itself, all have the major roles in transforming the game. Similarly, in the interactive game of teaching, van Lier seeks English teachers to regularly research, revise, reform, reflect in order to invent new concepts, materials, tools and technologies that support designing learner-centered classroom practices for developing communication skills.

Within the phenomenological approach design, connected to teacher's ways of integrating technologies come added purposes of technology use and functions in the English class. In this regard, as agreed by Godwin-jones (2010), teacher within the communicative

approach design not only uses offline and online technologies as means of extrinsic motivation, but as authentic task learning tools for the construction of language in learners' intrinsic motivation. With this emphasis then, teacher's practice of technology expand beyond a mechanistic focus to develop teaching, as qualitative skills learning process innovated with cultural themes of using technologies upon skills of communications and activities of collaboration (Koester & Lustig, 2015).

Relevance of phenomenological epistemology as an interactive approach is drawn to modernizing English education in European context and it is sought by developing teacher practices (Europe, 2000; Byram, 1997). Under such developmental plan, scholars as do Koester and Lustig (2015), claim teacher's practice of technology integration as significantly advanced to enhance classroom practices in addressing intercultural communicative competence³⁹ goals of learning English in global circles (Murray, 2012, p.318), also linking European and Czech school context (Nekvapil & Sherman, 2009). With emphasis on intercultural dimensions, teacher integrates not merely general computer devices but various online sources as innovative sociocultural media bringing languages in interactive cultural forms, concepts, skills (Harasim, 2012). Guided by this goal, a teacher is mentioned to practice interactively defined communicative instructions which materialize on a wide range of interactive classroom methods, such as content and language integrated learning⁴⁰, task-based learning method, blended-learning method, problem-based or inquiry method, project-based model etc. (Warschauer, 1997; Wold, 2011; Johnson, 2008; Thorne, 2008).

Regarding relevance of phenomenological model for the study of technology integration in English class, researcher with phenomenological focus comprehensively analyses teachers' qualitative pedagogical perceptions, behaviors and skills of using technologies on constructing learning. For a quick reference, I cite a few studies that illustrate the phenomenon of technology

³⁹ ICC

⁴⁰ CLIL

integration in English teaching with a comprehensive focus on teachers' phenomenological approaches or pedagogical perceptions and practices of technology use in class hereafter.

Antón et al. (2014) researched teacher perceptions and practices with a focus on CALL⁴¹ in practice on this model. Their study captures teachers' use of technologies as significantly appropriated for constructing learning in task-based instructions. In task-based instructions, teachers appropriate various offline and online tools and media used to engage learners in tasks of communications, presentations and so on.

Similarly, Arnesen (2010) on this model, researched technologies in teaching English with a focus to teacher's individual theory of practice on complementary ecological relations. The study distinguishes that English teacher with grammar focus in class despite being well exposed to technologies, practices them for a purpose to transmit texts, whereas within communicative approach, integrates technologies enabling students to use in tasks of learning or building communication skills. Within communicative approach framework or design, Sharifian (2016) argues technology integration in teaching English to supporting classroom practices to develop on the goal to enhancing meta-cultural competence. In this study, the teacher practices multiple technologies as online or www learning tools and media in real class teaching on meta-cognitive skills focus. With this scheme in mind, this study adds advocacy to developing technology integration in class in teacher's interactive phenomenological approaches and skills of framing instructions as meta-cognitive skills learning practices.

On (social) construction, Lund (2003) researched technology integration in teaching English with sociocultural phenomenological focus. His research explores this phenomenon in exemplary teachers' pedagogical beliefs and attitudes that express teachers' personal experiences and practices of technologies in teaching English to enhance learning as a transformative model.

⁴¹ Computer assisted language learning

In line with the given studies, researchers, (Idris & Ghani, 2012; Kaur, Ganapathy and Sidh, 2012; Li, Snow, Jiang, & Edwards, 2014; Fotos, 2004; Guichon, 2010) among others, focusing beyond conversational discourse, explore various interactive concepts and models of technology use in teaching English class as invented in teachers' interactive pedagogical approaches that advance on teachers' phenomenological encounters, experiences and reflections. In short, the sources provide an idea, in the phenomenological framework with subjective (social) constructivist epistemology, English teacher's technology practices are not only limited to what types but how and why technologies are used which express their didactic and media encounters, experiences, perceptions, interpretations, skills, actions and reflections. With an extended reflectivity on the phenomenological model, teacher develops the phenomenon i.e. technology integration in teaching English in complex relations between teachers' pedagogical approaches and context factors. Hence, following the phenomenological literature, technology integration in teaching English is explored in teacher's interactive pedagogical approaches, practices, reflections and skills of using technologies on constructing learning by extending inquiry beyond conversation analysis.

However, as Warschauer (2010) informs, though phenomenological concept on (social) construction is a comprehensive learning framework regarding technology integration in teaching English from teacher perspective, studies on this model are very few, since this epistemology is still in its early stage of development. Then given the phenomenological epistemological concept as a comprehensive model for exploring technology integration within teachers' pedagogical skills and cultural themes of using technologies on constructing learning, yet insufficiently researched, this study centers on phenomenological epistemology as the main theoretical framework. According to this framework, this study explores technology integration in English class by exploring exemplary teachers' perceptions and reflections upon qualitative

behaviors, or skills, and cultural themes for using technologies on constructing learning on phenomenological case-study research design as described in the next methodology chapter.

As this is the study of Czech elementary school English teachers' exemplary practices of technology integration in class, the afore discussed perspectives and practices are recapped in the table for a reference while drawing the phenomenon in Czech school context.

Table 1

Some Key Features of Technology Integration in English Class on Different Paradigms

Paradigm	Behavioral /Structural	Cognitive/communicative	(Social) constructivist (phenomenological)
View of language	Verbal-formal (pre-Chomsky) Objective structural (Chomsky)	Mentally constructed Semantic system	In networked social interactions. (Warschauer, 2010)
Time series	1960-1980	1980s-1990	1990s-21 st century (Harasim, 2012)
Language teaching approach	Audio-lingual, grammar translation, instructional ICT	Comprehensive input, communicative language teaching (CLT), interactional ICT	Interaction-input combined (Long, 1985) Multi-literacies and collaborative ICT
Didactic focus	How-method oriented	What-content oriented	Why, where, when- processes oriented
Technology/ICT	Mainframe, tutorial software	PCs, educational software	Multimedia, internet convergence (www MOOC, MOODL, mobile, tablet etc.)

Principal use of ICT	Drill and memory practices	Communicative/conversational exercises	Authentic tasks, problem-solving, presentations, many to many discourses
Location of activity	Computer lab (CALL)	Co-located classroom and e-library	Networks, online platforms, social media etc.
Principal objective	Accuracy	Fluency	Social and cultural Interactions
Research issues	Technologies software	Learners use of ICT in practice	Online communications, e-learning networks, ubiquitous media
Research focus	Efficiency and effects	Information transmission or communication	Transformation by interaction and mediation

Following the recaps on international and European educational policy, concept and research perspectives and practices regarding technology integration in teaching English from a teacher's perspective as described below, this phenomenon has been drawn from Czech educational policy and research perspectives. The descriptions assess the practices of technology integration in English class from the perspective of teachers' pedagogical skills and themes of using technologies in constructing learning upon intercultural communication skills focus.

2.4 Technology and English Teaching in Czech School Education

At the empirical level, this study focuses on exploration of technology integration in teaching English in Czech elementary schools from the perspective of teachers' pedagogical perceptions and practices. Within the stated focus, the aim is to describe how technologies are part of exemplary teachers' everyday teaching English class. Following the empirical goal, the focus of this section is to understand the current Czech education and research perspectives and practices regarding technology integration in English as a school subject teaching⁴² linking teacher practices. To this end, the descriptions draw the phenomenon following a brief introduction to the Czech Republic as a knowledge-oriented society. On the fast-changing socio-economic background of this country, the descriptions track technologies as associated to digitalizing Czech school education and their integration into subject teaching e.g. EFL upon skills of communication from teacher perspective as represented in education policy and research levels.

2.4.1 Brief about the Czech Republic on Setting a Research Context

With a population of 10.625.449 people (CZSO, 2018b) over 78866 square km total area in Central Europe, The Czech Republic is a developed European Union member state (CZSO, 2017) and is a fast globalizing, knowledge-oriented economy (CZSO, 2018a). Guided by the fast changing knowledge-oriented socio-economic and educational perspectives, systems and cultures, Czech education along with its changing socio-economic systems (Brusis, 2005) has been in a rapid transformation; shifting the old structures into digital systems as guided by multi-literacy skills based economic cultures. In this regard, sources like (Machonin, 1994; Hellström, 2005) inform, following the historical socio-political transition in 1989, "Czech

⁴² EFL

socio-economic system through privatization occupying more than 80% of the economy is in advance leaps (Hellström, 2005, p.12)” in service, manufacturing industries, technology and education functioning largely as supported by digital systems (Cordero & Crosier, 2016; Spacek, 2015).

In the fast-changing knowledge-oriented Czech socio-economic systems, digitally skilled and professional manpower e.g. innovative educators or teachers in educational institutions now in digital pace of modernization play a vital role in promoting learner communities to grow smarter with enhanced technology and foreign language skills defined as multi-literacies. Linking this argument, the Czech educational strategy level as pin-pointed in Economy (2006) exhibits its unequivocal engrossment to amending Czech school education by means of digital system integration as a major tool to enhancing subject teaching practices on one hand and with computer and English added as 21st century literacies in new curriculum, is now heading along 21st century skills based education plans on the other. Also, it will be clear below, in regard to a need of bringing along innovation in the process of subject teaching and learning through technology integration upon development of digital system in school, the Czech policy level e.g. Grečnerová (2015) projects vital role of teacher’s digital competence together with subject-based qualifications. In such lines, along with common priority on developing learner’s digital competence, the strategy level i.e. Grečnerová (2015, p.7) expresses high priority upon, “development of teacher’s digital competence,” as instrumental for teachers to effectively implement technology in class teaching, enhancing the process of teaching-learning of a school subject.

At this point, as the purpose of this study, the short recap informs that the Czech Republic is now a fast digitalizing knowledge-oriented European economy. As for knowledge orientation, the Czech school education through digital pace together with new curriculum increases the role and educational priority upon developing teacher (digital) competence as

instrumental to enhancing teaching-learning process. On this backdrop, as school education is through innovation upon knowledge orientation in which language and digital literacies play vital role to orienting subject teaching process of Czech schools⁴³ and teachers' technology, a focused description of technology and English is required. Hence, below I draw these phenomena from the Czech education perspectives followed by review of teachers' practice of technology integration in English class in elementary schools that lends a departure.

2.4.2 Czech Perspectives and Practices Relating Technology in Teaching English

The education system of The Czech Republic guided by a vision to promoting knowledge-oriented socio-economic systems and cultures, is operated by two main governing bodies, namely municipalities and regional governances, both coordinated by the ministry of education (Ministry of Education, 2004). The Czech Ministry of Education (2004) confers its role of devising strategy or policy as a central governing entity. Regarding technology in school, the Ministry expresses a key priority upon modifying school education in system in addition to bringing along consistent changes in criteria related to changing teacher practices such as educational levels, curriculum, procedures, teachers' professional criteria etc. In this regard, the Ministry paper argues in favor of timely updating Czech education system that would provide strong foundations to developing Czech socio-economic systems (Ministry of Education, 2004) fast on digital pace also transforming through multinational business models. Along with evolving digital systems in each functional sector, the Czech school education has entered into digital systems and operates its programs within frameworks of new curriculum that priorities digital literacy and English as new skills (Economy, 2006). To these new requirements as the educational manuscript (Ministry of Education, 2004) communicates, for lower secondary

⁴³ The term, 'teaching-learning process at school,' in this study stands for EFL as a school subject teaching-learning. In other cases, this term as well means teaching-learning different subjects as taught in Czech school

school curriculum, the subject teacher has to have university degree with teaching course including digital literacy as basic skills.

The Czech school curriculum endorses English defined for communication skills in the category of foreign language subject taught from grade 6 and digital literacy from grade 4. On this scheme, along with English and digital literacy endorsed as new skills, technology integration in teaching a subject e.g. English in Czech schools has emerged as an engaging phenomenon. In this regard, English is described as an important subject of study signified for learning communications defined with inter-cultural dimensions (Nekvapil & Sherman, 2009). Linked with this comes digital system policy and its main projection is for enhancing classroom practices which largely engage different educational levels e.g. policy, research and teacher levels in Czech school context as briefed hereafter.

In general, the education strategy levels of the Ministry of Education (2001), Ministry of Education (2004), Economy (2006) etc. in resonance with European perspectives (Brusis, 2005) exhibit growing priority upon a digital system at institutional levels and these include developing subject teaching-learning practices in schools. In this regard, the education political levels mention increasing digital support to Czech schools like as noted in Sedova and Zounek (2008 p.18) e.g., “speedy process of saturating schools with ICT system.” Besides, changes in school education as sought to come reflected in the new curriculum that follows multi-literacy education framework within which along with digital technologies described as new skills, English is signified as a foreign language subject of study on communicative skills defined by intercultural competence goal (Nevkapil and Sherman,2009).

The Czech school curriculum positions English in the articulated significance of communication in “foreign language skill (Nevkapil & Sherman, 2009, p.126),” as important for school learners to effectively participate in global career prospects. In this vision, “English is a mandatory subject of study from grade 6 (Economy, 2006,p.5),” and ranks, “top in the list

among the foreign languages taught in Czech schools (Nevkapil & Sherman, 2009, p.125).” However, despite English signified in Czech context upon skills of communication, the school curriculum as still based on linguistic system is pictured to leading teacher practices are even more confined to linguistic approaches (Dvorak, Urbanek, & Sary, 2014). In light of these facts, it is nonetheless apparent that educational strategy level is still lacking when it comes to striking a balance between what the educational policy expects and what it contributes to promoting teacher competence and thereby practices in teaching English which in principle must develop upon intercultural dimension (Nekvapil & Sherman, 2009).

In common with English endorsed as a significant school subject of study, the Czech educational policy levels (e.g. in e-Europa, 2004 in Sedov& Zounek, 2008; Cordero & Crosier, 2016; Commission, 2011; Net, 2013; Economy, 2006) express high priority upon developing teachers’ digital competence deemed instrumental to bringing along innovation in the processes of teaching and learning (Grečnerová, 2015, p.6-7).” In justification to instantiated priority, the policy stresses essentiality of a digitally equipped teacher for an effective implementaiton of technology in developing education as a process of knowledge construction (Sedova & Zounek, 2008). In this regard, the manuscripts make explicit announcement about technological supports extended to the schools upon development of digital system signified to promoting teachers’ digital competence as instrumental of enhancing subject teaching process. For an example, Sedova and Zounek (2008, p.18) note, “The process of saturating schools with ICT has been triggered by the national educational policy and concerns all schools in the Czech Republic.” The key intent as the document highlights is for developing technology support system in schools for user promotion and that links promoting teacher skills (Benes, Mudrak, Prochazka, Rambousek, & Stipek, 2008). The descriptions likewise inform that the schools equipped with technology structures that entail instalment of internet or online access, e-libraries, availability

of educational and language software and learning management system⁴⁴ etc. are intended for effective use of technologies by teachers. The teachers must integrate the tools upon a focus to enhancing the classroom practices in teaching the school subjects.

Linked to the fast digitalization of the school system, albeit with persistent gaps between policy and implementations (Spacek, 2015), bringing along priority upon developing teacher's digital competence, the Czech policy levels make even stronger announcement on increasing roles of Czech school subject teacher⁴⁵. And these are suggested for transforming the old educational perspectives and practices. The fact as this becomes apparent from educational manuscripts, such as the one from the Ministry of Education (2004,p.2) while emphasizing new vision to modernize subject teaching-learning process, also stresses that educators/teachers must be ready to changing educational and professional perspectives and practices in order to create competitiveness with progressive, multilingual and multi-cultural European and global socio-cultures. Moreover, the policy highlights English and digital learning adopted in Czech school as new skills on learning significance which teachers are to internalize and implement in real classroom practices in the light of English increasingly attended upon the goal of learning communication skills defined with cultural dimensions (Parliament (2010; Commission, 2011; Spacek & Nemeč, 2012; Economy, 2006).

In short, the educational policy and research voice reveals technology integration in teaching English is a prioritized phenomenon and it is for enhancing classroom practices on a goal to addressing Czech school learners' communication skills for the promotion of global citizenship skills (Education, 2004). In other words, technology integration in Czech school is sought within the Common European framework to enhancing classroom practices (Commission, 2011) which in teaching English must address digital natives' (Eickelmann & Vennemann, 2017) communication skills defined by intercultural dimensions (Byram et al.,

⁴⁴ LMS

⁴⁵ EFL teacher

2002). It is to these goals that the Czech education policy explicates high priority upon developing digital system.

Despite increasing priorities upon the development of digital systems envisioned to enhance school teaching-learning process, the educational research communications signal a wide range of inconsistencies as persistent in teachers' practice of technology integration in school subject teaching such as English. In some situations, teachers are reported using technologies that to some extent support learning, whereas in others using far less than the level technologies can afford the educational potentials and so on. For instance, Eickelmann and Vennemann (2017, p.756) capture, "teachers negative perception regarding technology use in teaching a subject in Czech schools." Sedova and Zounek (2008, p.1) find teachers using technology upon an intent to maintaining power rather than addressing learning. Hrtoňová, Kohout, Rohlíková and Zounek (2015) report variations in teachers' ways of technology use due to levels of motivation differing and so on. In brief, following the research reported inconsistencies, it is surfaced that there is an increasing trend of gaps between policy perspectives and practices of technology implementation in real class teaching in Czech school context. However, as this is the study of Czech school English teachers' practice of technology integration in class, whereas the above literature limits description regarding technology use in teaching a school subject as general, a focused description on this issue is required. Thus, what follows is the short-focused description upon Czech school English teachers' practice of technology use drawn from the research perspectives which lend this study a departure.

2.4.3 Czech School English Teachers' Technology Use in English Class

To the purpose of this study, following descriptions drawn from a few studies accessible in the e-versions of the scientific journals in finger counts yet relevant, the Czech research perspective on teachers⁴⁶ practice of technology integration in English class for a recap.

In their concept paper, Klimova and Semradova (2012) appropriate technology in teaching English suggesting their use for teachers to design instructions within communicative approach framework for intercultural competence, one of the key goals of learning English in Czech context. This framework argues for the use of technology in teaching this subject within blended or autonomous learning models. Though this paper devises some ideas relating teachers' practice of technology for enhancing teaching-learning process of English on the scheme of (social) construction within intercultural focus, since it is limited to theoretical exploration, the study yet doesn't properly contribute to an understanding of the phenomenon from teachers' perceptions and practices on real grounds.

In their research, Klimova and Poulova (2014) report teacher perceptions on online and multimedia teaching of English in school as focused on increasing student motivation. Within this focus, though the paper informs about the use of technologies as related to increasing student motivation, it doesn't inform about the various dimensions of technology use in relation to teachers' practices. For instance, the study doesn't explain, extrinsic or intrinsic motivation that teachers appropriate technologies for, nor does it address teachers' perceptions upon English curriculum and approaches in which technologies are integrated in Czech school context and so on.

In a qualitative study, Klimova (2015) captures technology integration in teaching English relating teachers' practices within the corpus-based approach in addressing communication skills. In this regard, the study reports teachers' knowledge and use of media

⁴⁶ Czech school EFL teachers

in teaching the subject on corpus approach, yet poorly developed. As such, Klimova suggests further research for comprehensively exploring teachers' pedagogical perceptions, practices and reflections regarding the use of technologies in class on constructing learning. In an action research, Kisby (2011) projects the role of technologies in class relating positively on increasing English learning motivation. However, it minimally informs about the phenomenon regarding competence and likewise, teachers' classroom practices of technology use. In a Master's thesis, Egri (2013) records technology use in teaching English in Czech school as positively related to increasing student performance. In this study technologies are highlighted as a means to increasing student knowledge of English in textual forms leading to performance TOEFL⁴⁷, IELTS⁴⁸.

In a longitudinal study, Dvorak, Urbanek and Stary (2014) capture Czech school English teacher practices as still limited to traditional approaches. The study claims this finding on its key report that informs English teachers face content and language integrated learning⁴⁹ approach (Europe, 2000) and it is due to lack of communication skills. However, the study doesn't elaborate various interrelated questions, as whether teachers invent or apply alternative strategies to better invent new approaches as supportive in integrating technologies, what models of practices or alternative methods teachers inaugurate and so on.

At this point, as the cited studies signal, technology integration in teaching English in Czech schools has emerged as a largely engaging phenomenon. Besides, the cited research evidences that technologies in Czech school setting, among others, are appropriated as motivational tools to promoting student performance in English. However, as concerned to how technology integration has been augmented in English classes regarding teachers' perceptions and practices of technology use on developing learning, in general with signal inconsistencies,

⁴⁷ Test of English as a foreign language

⁴⁸ International English language testing system

⁴⁹ CLIL

research communications on this very question don't address various interrelated issues. In addition to Czech educational studies in sparse number, research relating teachers' practice of technologies in English class upon communication focus is still more sparse and as such, various dimensions related to Czech school teachers' classroom practices of technology, are yet to be explored. Connecting the findings thus, this chapter is concluded with a knowledge gap as identified below that lends this study a departure for comprehensive research on phenomenological case-study design as described in the third chapter.

2.5 Concluding Literature with Knowledge Gap

Relevant to the purpose of the study of technology⁵⁰ integration in teaching English in Czech school relating teacher practices, chapter one and two were designed aiming to understand and clarify meaning, relevance and practices of technology and English teaching from educational policy research and theory perspective. Along with technologies described in the first chapter as innovative educational media integrated to promote the process of teaching and learning a school subject in European school also linking Czech context, the descriptions in this second chapter focus on English teaching and technology in its process also linking teacher's practice. In this regard, in addition to European educational perspectives engaged to develop digital systems upon promoting technology integration to enhance classroom practices in teaching English with intercultural competence goals in focus, the theoretical literature informs this study. That teacher's practice of technology use in teaching English develops as a learning process on phenomenological concept with subjective and social constructivist epistemology, though many dimensions of this phenomenon on this framework are yet to be explored.

⁵⁰ ICT

Associated to the issue informed, in line with the international European research, the Czech educational policy and research reports inform that technology integration into teaching English emerged as a largely engaging phenomenon. The literature evidences this basic point in expression of growing priority upon digitalizing school as instrumental to promoting technology integration in developing teaching this subject as an innovative educational process. As regards this goal, the curriculum endorses technology and English as new literacy skills in which use of technology in teaching English is on the scheme to enhancing classroom practices upon communication skills as defined by intercultural competence goal of learning this subject (Nekvapil & Sherman, 2009).

From the Czech educational policy perspective, the school teachers equipped with digital competence in principle, are to integrate technologies and English⁵¹ as new literacy skills on the intent of innovating teaching approaches in addressing 21st century learning skills. However, as the research reports inform, along with inconsistencies signaled in teachers' practice of technology use in English class, very few studies cover this phenomenon on comprehensive research focus. Besides, despite increasing the priority upon developing digital systems and teachers' digital competence as being essential to promoting classroom practices in teaching English within communicative approach designs, Czech school teacher⁵² practices inconsistently in various ways, are still limited to mechanistic use of technologies. These limitations are signaled in the cited research which informs English teachers' instructional⁵³ practices as limited to grammatical or mechanical approaches. In mechanistic approaches, teachers use technologies but primarily as means to transmitting information about English from text, for example in grammatical approaches, Klimova and Poulouva (2014) found teachers limitedly using technologies as means of extrinsic motivation for controlling students'

⁵¹ EFL

⁵² EFL teacher

⁵³ EFL instructions

classroom behaviors. In this regard, the literature suggests that due to persisting conventional teacher's practices as based on inconsistent research perspectives (Arnesen, 2010), an increasing scope to study technology integration in teaching English within the comprehensive research focus is necessary. Furthermore, it is important to explore multiple dimensions related to motivations and conversely barriers to teachers' practice of technology use in teaching English on constructing learning.

Linking a need to develop the phenomenon, as in technology integration in teaching English as a learning process, the literature informs phenomenological model as a comprehensive approach. On this model, this phenomenon is explored in its complexity in developing teachers' pedagogical perceptions, experiences, interpretations, motivations, skills of using technologies in English class on constructing learning (Warschauer, 1997). This is what phenomenological studies explore educational potentials in exemplary teachers' qualitative skills and cultural themes of using technologies on increasing learning interactions.

However, as informed by Warschauer (2000), studies that explore educational potentials in teachers' pedagogical skills of using technologies on phenomenological focus, are very few within the realm of European education including Czech school context. Following the research reports as these, along with inconsistent policy perspectives and lack of focused educational research on exploring technology use in teachers' interactive pedagogical skills (Godwin-jones, 2010), several questions related to teachers practice of technology integration in teaching English on communication skills focus, come suggested as remained unaddressed. Among others, these questions seek comprehensive answers e.g.: How do teachers perceive and appropriate to use what types of technologies in English class? Relating to this, which technologies are used and in what types of English lessons and activities? How are technologies used? For which purposes, functions and educational outcomes do teachers signify technologies? How are teachers' individual factors related to technology use in class? and so

on. These complex questions seek qualitative analysis of teachers' phenomenological experiences such that analyzed in case study design to exploring technology integration in English teaching practiced to developing as a comprehensive learning process. On qualitative research or case studies, technology integration in teaching English is explored in teachers' exemplary pedagogical approaches, motivations and skills which in Czech school context are nearly null. This is due to the existing studies limited to describing the phenomenon on increasing technology use within quantitative focus irrespective of how teachers use them in class.

Given the significance of teachers' phenomenological perceptions or exemplary approaches, experiences, and skills of technology integration in developing teaching English as a skill learning process, and insufficient research on comprehensive focus, this study is designed on qualitative phenomenological case study research design as described in the third chapter. On phenomenological case-study research design, I anticipate exploring and describe how technologies are part of exemplary teachers' everyday practice of teaching English class on developing learning. To this end, the central research question has been articulated in the next chapter that describes methodology of phenomenological case study research.

CHAPTER THREE

Research Methodology

In this chapter I describe the methodology of a phenomenological case-study design, its meaning, and methodological concepts, foundations and procedures as adopted for comprehensive analysis of the research phenomenon in hand. These components are described after the central research question stated with brief elaboration following the statement of meaning of educational research.

3.1 Methodology of Educational Research

Methodology of educational research interchangeably represented in terms of research design, or method as based on different scientific and philosophical traditions, is characterized as positivist, post-positivist, interpretivist among others research approaches and paradigms. Relating methodology with research approaches on different paradigms, Cohen, Manion and Morrison (2013, p.5) relay that methodology stands for a design in which, “the inquiry process is operated,” and finalized to meet the research objective to come up with an understanding of the phenomenon. Creswell and Poth (2017) add that, guided by different scientific and philosophical traditions and concepts, educational research methodology, in general, frames within quantitative, qualitative or mix-method design depending on the concept it extends on. In this regard, a study guided by structural or cognitivist concept builds on quantitative methodology, whereas the other may be guided by constructivist e.g. phenomenological concept with social constructivist principles build within qualitative methodology. Among these, educational research is built as a complex inquiry process within interpretivist methodology as an alternative to positivist and post-positivist structural methods in exploring

education as a social constructivist learning process. Inherently, on interpretivist paradigm, educational research methodology is qualitative. Through such, the inquiry procedures are devised to explore subjects' personal experiences and understanding upon developing the phenomenon as such, that is done within phenomenological research approach (Creswell & Poth, 2017). Moving closer to the subjective approach, phenomenological case-study is one example of qualitative interpretivist research methodology. This research methodology is designed for a key purpose. It is to construct a complex understanding over the phenomenon and that is created by exploring exemplary subjects' unique or qualitative perceptions, encounters and behaviors against the issue of research in addressing a general principle or to explore new principles (Cohen, Manion, & Morrison (2013)).

The stated interpretivist methodological concept is relevant as linking my study, which is planned on a phenomenological case-study design. The above description borrows from the idea that research methodology incepts upon research objective which has some concepts, ideas or experiences as antecedents (Cohen, Manion, & Morrison, 2013). My study idealizes this design extending upon my primary objective being it to understand on empirical basis how technologies are part of Czech school English class teachers on a daily basis for constructing learning. It incepted partly due to my professional encounters and partly due to some conflicting information from the educational concept, policy and research concept and experiences. On these encounters, phenomenological concept with subjective epistemology in principles of (social) construction informed me that technology integration in teaching English develops as a comprehensive learning process from the teachers' qualitative skills and cultural themes of using technologies and English⁵⁴ as new skills for constructing learning.

However, in addition to increasing contradictions between policy perspectives and practices on ground, slim volume of research that comprehensively captures technology use in

⁵⁴ EFL

English class from teacher perspective inspired me to explore the phenomenon from exemplary teachers' unique pedagogical perceptions, practices and reflections. These variables fully express teachers' pedagogical skills of technology use on developing learning process. To the primary encounters as stated, an open question formulated for a complex understanding e.g., how exemplary teachers use technologies in English class on developing learning.

This phenomenological quest seeking qualitative answer idealizes phenomenological case-study as an interactive, flexible research design (Creswell & Poth, 2017) in which I describe its procedures in this chapter. In this regard, below I first elaborate the central research question as framed in coherence with phenomenological concept and subsequently, I specify the methodological procedures of gathering data and analysis. The central research question is as stated:

1) How do Czech elementary school EFL teachers use ICT in teaching EFL class?

1.1. How do teachers decide regarding the use of individual ICT in EFL class?

1.2. Which functions are fulfilled in the EFL instruction fully supported by ICT?

1.3. How do teachers reflect the use of individual ICT in EFL class?

2) How do individual factors affect teachers use of ICT in individual class?

2.1 Can some stimuli and conversely barriers be identified between teachers' individual factors and their use of ICT in individual class?

2.2 Can ICT integration in EFL class from exemplary teacher perspective be described developing as a learning process?

These basic questions have been briefly elaborated hereafter in deepening the focus of analysis on addressing the research objective and it is:

to explore and describe how ICT are part of Czech elementary school exemplary English teachers everyday practice of teaching class.

The first question is addressed by using these broad categories in guiding analysis that elicits answer to which technologies are used, why and how they are used, with which functions

they are used. The focused dimensions inform exemplary teachers' personal experiences that express their pedagogical perceptions or approaches, interpretations, decisions, skills of practices, and reflections regarding technology use in English class. In this regard, few more sub-questions are formulated for deepening analysis to answering, as how teachers make decisions regarding the use of individual technologies in class. It too sheds light on why teachers select (or not) individual technologies which might be due to own approaches or on a purpose to inventing new approaches or skills, or beyond due to external reasons etc. Apart from external or internal factors that influence teacher decisions, these questions as well enable an understanding of motivations or barriers as experienced by teachers regarding the use of individual technologies in English class teaching on a focus i.e. communication skills.

Linked to the first question follows the analysis of the use of selected technologies in English classes. In this regard the specifications help learning about the types of lessons or activities, purposes and functions in which teachers' ways and skills of technology use are involved. At this point, these sub-questions are formulated to answer, such as why and how the selected technologies are used. Connecting these, the focus is lent to which types of English lessons, activities and purposes, technologies are used, how they are used and by whom (teacher/ student), and upon which functions. Functions might entail, teaching-learning interactions in the didactic units as fully supported by technologies used (interactions in class, teacher roles, activities). In deepening the focus regarding what is expressed and observed, follows the teachers' reflection question. It asks, how the exemplary teachers reflect the use of individual technologies in class. This is the question of teachers' post-teaching experiences that too expresses their long-lived encounters and interpretations regarding different technologies in use in English class. Reflections as well express motivations and conversely barriers to the use of technologies in individual class which in my study shed light on exemplary teachers' unique experiences that contribute to transforming this phenomenon. Connected to

phenomenological encounters and reflections, the second question relates the role of exemplary teachers' individual factors that entail personal and professional contexts related as first order and second order barriers (Ertmer, 1999). It asks, how exemplary teachers' individual factors contribute to the use of technologies in class. This question elicits how these factors are associated to the use of technologies in class by illuminating relations of stimuli and conversely barriers between individual factors and exemplary teachers' use of technologies in class. Teachers' individual factors include three main categories: personal factors, technological factors and cultural factors. Personal factors stand for teachers' personality factors and these involve teachers' personal attitude, education, digital literacy etc. Technological factors entail teaching methodology including the use of technologies and cultural factors include student and school culture. Finally, the last question stated above is researcher's interpretation question. As based on data from different questions, the researcher interprets the current stage of technology integration as developing learning process. Based on this, how it has been developing on ground is interpreted (Geertz, 1973) upon concluding the research finding.

Following the elaborated qualitative questions, my study designs the research on qualitative phenomenological case study design as elaborated hereafter starting with the meaning of a case study.

3.3 Concept of Case study

In this sub-section, I draw upon the meaning of case study as relevant to understanding the methodological plan. The objective of my study as stated above is incepted upon phenomenological epistemology, suggesting that technology integration in teaching English develop on its complexity of the teachers' qualitative behaviors and cultural themes for using technologies on constructing learning. To this complex objective, qualitative research methodology is idealized and it comprehensively develops on phenomenological case study

design that enables complex understanding of the research phenomenon or case in special instance in action as referring to a more general principle (Cohen, Manion, & Morrison, 2013). Following this basic idea, I specify its meaning with key features as relevant to design my study.

With a notion that case study as a problem-solving method (Alfred Schutz in Walsh, Leherent, & Walsh, 1967) is designed to bring a special instance in action, case study is sometimes taken for narrative inquiry in resemblance. However, as Creswell, Clark and Plano Clark (2007, p. 245) inform, “significant distinctions exist,” and that entails, distinctions in aims, goals, structures, procedures between case and narrative inquiry. In this regard, among others, the focus of a case study is not on individual/s but individuals’ issue which distinguishes it from narrative inquiry. On this distinction, as Cohen, Manion and Morrison (2013, p.253) elaborate, “A case study brings a unique example of real people in real situations enabling readers to understand ideas more clearly than simply presenting them with abstract theories or principles.” With emphases on being object oriented, several case studies are guided by research question rather than fixed methodology appearing as true with narrative inquiry or else. However, since there are instances of academic case studies incepted upon different educational concepts, case study is as well claimed of its methodological roots.

Concerning methodological root, the real intent of a case study is argued to present details of the phenomenon from the person’s developing actions which are explored as unique examples that could be used as instances for solving problems. Yet the methodological literature further informs that educational case study develops in a methodology which the educational concept idealizes in practice. This argument is supported by Creswell et al. (2007, p.245) who assert, “Although scholars choose it a choice of people, we choose to view it as a qualitative methodology with its origin.” As the authors validate, case study develops on qualitative methodology practiced on different schemes yet having its origin in the developmental educational concept or foundation. Further, this information comes true from

the instances of different types of case studies termed as, ethnographic, narrative, phenomenological etc. (Creswell, Hanson, & Clark, 2007).

Following the stated argument, as relevant to devising methodology of my study upon the goal to explore exemplary teachers' qualitative didactic skills of using technologies in class for constructing learning, some common features that define case study by bringing unique examples related to a case are as recapped:

Case study brings rich and vivid description of events relevant to the case, makes description with the analysis of cases, lends focus to main actors, highlights specific perceptions, communicates temporal characteristics that provides boundaries to distinguish phenomenon and so on... (Paraphrased from Cohen, Manion, & Morrison, 2013, p. 253-263).

As obvious from the extract, a case study is a unique research methodology for solving the problem in hand and it forms in exploring exemplary people's approaches, skills and reflections regarding the phenomenon in hand. I adopt these unique features upon my empirical plan to explore the case in complexity in this case, the technology integration in teaching English from exemplary teachers' perspective. To this end, I adopt phenomenological case study as a developmental or comprehensive inquiry process rooted within qualitative phenomenological approach extended on interpretivist research paradigm. One of the key reasons behind this inspiration is, due to, as Geertz (1973) allows, methodological procedures of phenomenological case-study design that enable researcher to explore interactively, as 'what it is like' to be in a particular situation, to catch the close up reality and 'thick description' of participants' lived experiences, their thoughts about and feelings for a situation with a narrow focus on fine-grain details.

At this point, as phenomenological case study has its root in phenomenological methodology with subjective epistemology on (social) construction, I briefly state its

methodological foundations followed by the descriptions specifying procedures as employed in my study.

3.4 Methodological Foundation of a Phenomenological Case study

Phenomenological case study as thick qualitative descriptive research has its methodological root in Husserl's (1970) phenomenology through its alliance with sociological constructions of Max Weber, lending ontology and epistemology of social actions to subjects (Gamst, 1991;Rotry, 1992). This methodology owes to metaphysical foundations in Immanuel Kant (1790) who constructed knowledge in freedom of expression or reason over material (Matt McCormick, 2002). As said, phenomenological methodology upon which case study is one unique phenomenological framework, approaches the phenomenon from the human wisdom, individual values, rationales, lived experiences, encounters, interpretations, and reasons in substitute of objective science limiting the complex world of human science within the level of discrete world-objects (Gibson, 1962; Corbin & Strauss, 2008). At this point, these methodological foundations are relevant, linking my study with its objective being to explore technology integration as developing learning process from the perspective of exemplary teacher perceptions and practices. In this regard, these basic concepts suggest approaching this phenomenon from exemplary teachers' lived experiences, encounters, interpretations and reasons which fully express their skills of technology use.

Further, on the phenomenological foundations, several scholars following e.g. Schuetz (2018), Berger (2011), Zalta, Nodelman, Colin and Perry (2010) etc. add up new dimensions that interact phenomenological methodology to extend from merely within subjective to intersubjective inquiry on discovering reality related to a case as based upon peoples' social encounters and experiences. Following these assumptions, in my study exploring exemplary teachers' subjective encounters with technologies in teaching English doesn't limit the finding

merely to their own subjectivity but also through subjects in interaction reveals their interconnected contextual realities. Such an inquiry, as (Gibson, 1962, p.1) relays, “explores people’s perceptions, intentions, interpretations, intellectual and affective elements against the phenomenon in real context.” According to Husserl (1970, p.8), “depends on our (not only my) representations and concept formation,” also philosophically validated by Wittgenstein who assures that meaning is created in the social and cultural practice of language not in the object (Rorty, 1992). Considering this methodological foundation, the phenomenological case study is practiced as a thick qualitative descriptive research method (Mackenzie & Knipe, 2006) which significantly inspires educational researchers.

Methodological literature suggests phenomenological case study as one of the comprehensive qualitative research designs that enables researcher to explore the phenomenon in subjects’ stream of consciousness. In subjects stream of consciousness, “an object is encountered, perceived, understood in reflections, introspections, retrospections etc. leading to invention of new dimensions that develop the case (Zalta, Nodelman, Colin, & Perry, 2010, p.25).” Linking this phenomenological concept with the case in my study, technology integration in teaching English, it is anticipated to develop on a complexity of exemplary teachers’ innovative encounters, interpretations, skills experiences, and reflections (Zalta et al., 2010). This means, with phenomenological case study method, my research is designed to explore the reality of the phenomenon in hand which keeps reforming in people’s principles, values, approaches, skills and actions that change on regular basis (Gibson,1962).

Following the methodological foundations of phenomenological case study as a flexible approach to solving the research problem (Alfred Schuetz in Walsh, Leherent, & Walsh, 1967) with a scheme of sociological interpretation (Walsh, Leherent, & Walsh, 1967), scholars devise several interactive techniques of inquiry which have practical significance. In this regard, Wilson (2002) relays, phenomenological case study researcher brings understanding of the

phenomenon but without interfering into the interest of research participants, since the focus is on people's interpretations, perceptions, experiences, and understandings, not the participants. This comes importantly for my study in light of its key intent. It is to explore multiple dimensions as accountable to developing technology integration in teaching English in exemplary teachers' exemplary perceptions or approaches and actions instead of the ways that might impose researcher's interests. This idea is valuable in keeping the researcher neutral on a role that minimally interferes participants' personal innovative interests.

Regarding procedures of phenomenological case study as an interactive or descriptive inquiry science of interpretation on construction, though least practiced for educational issue (Creswell & Poth, 2017), which in my study is linked with teachers' practice of technology integration in teaching English, Campbell (2011b) suggests these main components. These entail e.g., open interviews or focus-discussions for constructive reflectivity and open observations that bring subjects' own interpretations and actions further analyzed with qualitative interpretative data analysis method (Creswell & Poth, 2017).

In short, as these descriptions reveal, the methodological foundations allow to project phenomenological case study as a unique qualitative design of inquiry for exploring unique examples related to a case. It is therefore, that my study idealizes this methodology for a comprehensive inquiry for exploring technology integration in teaching English developing on the complexity teachers' exemplary practices. To this end, below I specify the procedural methods as adopted in this phenomenological case study.

3.5 Phenomenological Case Study Procedures in this Study

Following the literature that suggests educational case study on exploring the case or phenomenon in unique example/s in action that in my study is for research objective, namely to explore technology integration in exemplary teachers' unique practices which frame on

phenomenological epistemological principles, I now devise its procedures for qualitative inquiry. In this regard, I follow practicalities as disseminated by Creswell et al.(2007, p. 239). The authors suggest that phenomenological case study on selection of exemplary participants in purposively selected research setting develops with open and deepening inquiry process with open questions. Open questions lead to inquiry, “on how different cases provide insight into an issue or a unique case”. Part of the procedures within this design is the analysis for interpretation which in my study forms with, “qualitative method (Creswell, Hanson, & Clark, 2007, p.241-242).” Also procedural practicalities in my study are the open tools and credible skills of inquiry, triangulation, and analysis (Patten, 1990 in Angers, 2005) as the key components of a phenomenological case study. I briefly specify these procedures below as employed in my research design.

3.5.1 Participants and Setting

On its qualitative framework, for a study of technology integration in teaching English class in Czech elementary schools from the exemplary teacher perspective, the empirical study was conducted in the schools located in two different demographic locations; city and town. The schools were chosen purposively for data from the English teachers on the assumptions of common and different characteristics that the school contexts develop in subject teaching also that links to use of technology in developing the system. Within the given background, this study was designed to explore how technologies are part of teachers everyday practice of teaching English class on constructing learning. As such, in the pilot phase within qualitative phenomenological approach to inquiry design, twelve English teachers on service were selected for open interview and class observations using purposive sampling followed by snow ball sampling techniques. Gathered data were pilot analyzed on qualitative theme analysis method with triangulation of observation and interviews (Flick, 2014b). The findings led to the

identification of participant teachers' practice of technologies in English class as based on different educational paradigms that characterized cognitivist and constructivist principles. On these mixed findings, however, four participants whose practice of technology integration in English class triangulated with phenomenological concept developing the phenomenon as a comprehensive learning process in subjective epistemology or social construction, were selected as exemplary teachers. In this way, the participants were selected as exemplary study teachers due to their qualitative pedagogical perceptions, approaches, skills, experiences, and reflections upon using technologies in class on constructing learning for empirical analysis of the issue within the phenomenological case study design.

The selected exemplary teacher participants met different criteria lending the case study a comprehensive solution to the research problem in hand as expressed and captured in their very personal phenomenological encounters, experiences, perceptions, practices and reflections (Cohen et al., 1994). The four exemplary teacher participants qualify on these listed criteria. For instance, participants involved in the same issue (Creswell et al., 2007) as in my study of technology integration in teaching English class of elementary schools. Exemplary practices in my study are conceptualized in teachers' interactive pedagogical skills and cultural theme of using technologies on constructing learning. Connected to these are teacher's qualifications, teaching (job) experiences, and training. In my study, these variables are relevant regarding technology integration in teaching English on phenomenological scheme of (social) construction. Besides, research setting in my study is comprised of two main types of schools, Czech elementary state school and grammar school elementary level with some differences in contextual factors. Following the stated features, below I specify empirical and desk-based procedures such as tools and methods of data gathering and analysis.

3.5.2 Data Procedures Linking Research Tools and Analysis

Incepted upon the concept of education as a developmental process (Wertsch, 1993), my study idealizes qualitative methodology on phenomenological case study design to explore technology integration in English class in exemplary teachers' pedagogical perceptions, practices and reflections. In such design, the study employs open and interactive research tools and methods for gathering data and analysis (Willis, 2007). The tools and methods employed for data collection and analysis in my study are based upon the scholarly disseminations in methodological literature. In a phenomenological case study design, the literature relays as Brown (2016) among others suggests, open interviews, direct observations and researcher diary used as the main qualitative tools for gathering data. Accordingly, the sources also suggest qualitative theme analysis method along with practical procedures of data triangulation as interviews and observation for analysis and interpretation which must assure credibility or validity upon what is expressed by participants and interpreted by the researcher (Creswell et al., 2007). In this regard, Maxwell (2012) claims direct observations and open interviews as among the key procedures that enable the researcher to approach the phenomenon in its natural setting. These procedures operated interactively engage participants in expressing personal perceptions, understandings, experiences, skills, actions on developing the phenomenon and researcher in recording their lived experiences that construct in real context. Mackenzie and Knipe (2006) call these approaches and methods as different ways of visualization. Below these procedures are specified as operated upon the suggestions from some selected methodological literature bases. The descriptions start with open interviews followed by observation, researcher diary, and method of data analysis.

3.5.3 Open Interviews

Open interviews are designed with open questions framed upon the main research question and purpose as interactive tools for gathering data upon qualitative construction of knowledge (Creswell & Poth, 2017). In this primary vision, open interviews in my study on phenomenological case study design are formulated for comprehensive information on the phenomenon in hand with open questions. The open interview questions align with the central research question as to how exemplary English teachers integrate technology in class on constructing learning and how their individual factors contribute to their actions. Within this quest, the open questions were created for interviews that would express concrete ideas from actors' own meanings and actions which typically the case study in general aims to project from within the cases (Erickson, 1985). The interviews were, then, operated with two main practicalities that entailed the researcher to ask open questions which individual participants answered and the researcher recorded their voice on electronic record device, in the "immediate scenes and face-to-face interactions that too link information on the wider surrounding (Erickson, 1985, p.1)." With these tools and procedures, it was possible to achieve a comprehensive focus on exemplary teachers' actions as shaped in real context on everyday basis. The questions seeking answer to how technologies were appropriated in class on constructing learning were operated in interviews in which redundancies and reductions also occurred. Yet, the focus was maintained by centering analysis to exploring teachers' perceptions and reflections. These components expressed practitioners' pedagogical approaches, decisions, experiences, interpretations, ways, skills, actions, purposes and practices on which, "the phenomenon develops in complexity (Sloan & Bowe, 2014)."

As concerning the purposes of open interviews in my study frame for a communication process that is shaped by the use of interactive language not confined as a structural entity but that makes up with symbolic interactions, personal reasons, intents, experiences, reflective

interpretations in gathering evidences the participants relate to the phenomenon (Langdrige, 2007). These tools, also as supported in literature e.g. (Marshall & Rossman (2014), enable a view as related to the research phenomenon. This is about learning here the structure lies, which are the channels, sources or motivations and barriers to actions in a real context in my study concerning the exemplary English teachers practice of technology integration in English class. As such, the open interviews in my study were operated upon the key ideas and goals in line with Saunders et al. (2011) from Kahn and Cannel (1957, p.318), as the open tools on purposeful discussion for “valid data in addressing the research question or purpose.”

Besides, for the purpose of bringing bulky and comprehensive understanding of the phenomenon, constructing learning from the perspective of exemplary teachers’ encounters or experiences, along with open interviews, direct open classroom observations are required. These were conducted as the key tools for data. I briefly specify open classroom observations further on.

3.5.4 Open Classroom Observations

Describing teaching or teachers’ technology in class as an observable developmental phenomenon, Wajnryb (2013) informs about direct classroom observations as effective learning tools providing observer a practical exposure to real experiences. In this regard, direct observations are carried out in different types, ways, focuses and structures among which, open observation is just one approach. These interactive procedures are employed with a focus on different sub-components and dimensions interrelated to the main phenomenon as designed in central research question. The main purpose of open classroom observations is to explore the phenomenon in practitioners’ real experiences that build upon their own activities carried out in ways, skills and also with the use of tools and technologies in real context (Wajnryb, 2013). With these assumptions in mind, in my study the central question as of how exemplary teachers

use technologies in class on constructing learning, as following Wajnryb's (2013, p.8-11) idea of interactive focus, I carried out the open observations. While taking notes on observed phenomena in class, the main components were focused in different steps as set on a grand tour observation model (Spradley, 1980).

In practice of open classroom observations, I focused on describing general procedures teachers demonstrated in relation to the use of technologies in English classrooms leading to reflections on their ways, techniques, intents, purposes and uses, looking forward to drawing conclusions. All the components focused were related to the exemplary teachers' actions, roles, techniques and effectiveness regarding their practice of technology use in the different English lessons and activities in class. My focus of observation at this stage following suggestions from Wajnryb (2013), interacted upon noticing teachers with different technologies in class, their use in lessons (language related focus and organized activities), intents or purposes, functions relating learning interactions and motivations, teaching skills and strategies, classroom management etc.

In this way, direct open classroom observations played significant role in my study for first hand qualitative experiences on the phenomenon which it is possible from complex understanding on teachers' skills, strategies and techniques accountable to developing this phenomenon. Along with open interviews and observations, researcher diary was another main tool used along for data gathering that also enhanced data analysis purposes.

3.5.5 Researcher's Diary

In qualitative phenomenological case study, as Creswell and Poth (2017) mention, researcher diary is a manual note book or record book in which researcher designs memos, keeps record of the people's ideas, information or data," and uses them for research from field to desk process (Czarniawska, 2014). Moreover, research diary contributes to multiple

functions and these involve recording, reflecting and managing data and most importantly data storage to increasing reflections. Based upon this idea, from the research development phase of gathering data right until the analysis phase, I used the researcher diary as an integral support tool that enabled to gather data even extending beyond the electronic record device and with increasing reflectivity during analysis to enhancing rigor or robustness in triangulation and interpretation of the findings. The researcher diary in my case was used both as logistic and practice tool on its practical significance in supporting other tools and procedures. In interviews it was used for memos besides used as a main notebook on recording observations, and other research related plans, dates, activities, encounters which I as a researcher came across during the whole inquiry process.

3.6 Data Analysis with Triangulation for Research Credibility

Data analysis is a process of selection of information based on individual characters of distinction for a synthesis between the variables of research focus. It involves numerous activities and techniques employed from the beginning of research development through empirical phases of inquiry to the phase of research on desk and then conclusion (Silverman, 2011). In a phenomenological case study, data analysis frames an open, interactive and qualitative analytical design that resembles “qualitative content analysis pattern (Sturman, 1997 in Cohen et al., 1994, p.262).”

Upon the given framework, data analysis in my study constituted within qualitative analytical design and was operated through different phases. The task was carried out with a focus on exploring technology integration in English class in exemplary teachers’ perceptions, practices and reflections that express pedagogical skills and themes of using technologies on constructing learning. It also included the task of data triangulation as required for research credibility or validity. In this regard, following the literature (Creswell et al., 2007) and others,

I incorporated different activities carried out on different stages related to data analysis. On the first stage, my task centered on taking note of observations and interviews apart from other features relevant to the object of study together entering the data on observations and interviews which I transcribed in the Office-Word and uploaded on The Atlas.ti. software for further analysis.

Having transcribed and managed the data, I involved on, “initial description phase of pilot study which analysed all data on the themes based on the research question to distinguish the findings (Creswell et al., 2007, p.248).” This was followed by the case analysis of the 4 selected exemplary teachers as carried out using the variable-oriented analysis method (Miles, Huberman, & Saldaña, 2014) in that all data from both electronic sources and researcher diary transferred to the office-word file were merged and analyzed. Cases as selected on the common framework of representation of their practices (Angers, 2005) along with individual differences in contexts due to the emerging themes (Cobb & Yackel, 1995) were analyzed taking the central research question into consideration. The procedure mostly developed upon a rigorous content analysis method concentrated on developing technology integration instrument that tallied with the research question on which the themes were developed. Then, both data, the interviews and observations were triangulated. Based on the criteria that matched, findings on cases studies were synthesized as stated in the 4th chapter.

On a necessity to meet research credibility or validity which depends on the procedures of gathering data and analysis to validly address the research issue and purpose, the procedures in my study were operated with a focus on exploring how teachers perceived, practiced and reflected technology integration in class on constructing learning. Therefore, following the phenomenological research question, data were analyzed in qualitative method. For the accuracy of analysis, a checklist was prepared that allowed to sort out the four exemplary teachers’ perceptions, practices and reflections regarding the phenomenon. This as a

descriptive, analytical and synthetic procedure helped to check the differences and similarities in what was said and practiced while triangulating the information on findings in which credibility was maintained for example with the help of research framework to bringing valid results from the participants' own voice (Cohen et al., 2013). As such, data analysis in this study involved data reduction, data display and drawing conclusion and verification (Creswell et al., 2007) for the statement of findings, discussions and research conclusion as stated in chapter four and five.

3.7 Ethical considerations

My research is guided by the philosophy of transformative teacher learning for better student learning within the emerging European context, Horizon-2020 vision. Within the European vision relating the study on teacher education, my research was staged in the elementary schools of the European Union member country, the Czech Republic. Within the research setting and context, regarding ethical considerations, I follow the consideration lines as instructed in the manuscript e.g. TOPDP (2000) that draws the national law no. 101/4.3.2000. It specifies ethical considerations relating the protection, the operating and the confidentiality of the personal data. Likewise, I have consulted the manuscripts on international legislation- EU directive 95/46/EC as disseminated in e.g. EUR-LEX (1995) also following the criteria as specified in e.g. REA (2015), ECDGRI (2018). These sources provide latest research-related ethical guidelines to maintain the research integrity in following the ethical standards, norms and values along with the regulations as applicable within the European research traditions and across the academic disciplines. As an educational research I have taken into consideration the ethical norms of sensitivity, anonymity and protection of people' self as articulated in the sources like Gardner (2011) and (Hughes, Hunter, & Sheehan, 2010) which in my study are

Czech elementary school EFL teachers, the literate, scholarly and professional adult generations.

Following the legislative and educational research ethical guidelines as cited I carried out the secondary and empirical research activities to explore the status of technology integration in teaching English as a foreign language from the teacher's perspective. Regarding a secondary analysis, I undertook a qualitative review approach towards the theory, policy and research disseminations which provide relevant theoretical and conceptual framework for the research phenomenon in hand taking its overarching objective being to explore how technologies are part of the EFL teachers on everyday teaching class, into consideration. At this level, following the ethical literature, it lent keys to review within the parameters of comprehension, interpretation, critical thinking and assimilation following that the sources reviewed have been cited and referenced with maximal level of precision.

Regarding ethical considerations for empirical data and analysis, the main units of analysis in my research are English as foreign language teachers on service in the Czech elementary schools who provide their first-hand empirical data. The data were collected and analyzed by the researcher on qualitative methods of direct observation, interviews and analysis (Flick, 2014a). At this level, ethical considerations in my research entail observations of people's personal and professional sensitivity, integrity and anonymity regarding getting access, sampling, rapport building, accessing, collecting data and analysis (Gardner, 2011). Considering such issues, coordinated by the Department of Educational Sciences, Faculty of Arts, Masaryk University, Brno, the Czech Republic on official basis, I fully observed keys to research operational procedures on personal and professional basis (EDiTE, 2016). In this regard, ethical considerations were applied in building rapports, collecting data from the teacher participants during their job-hours and later. On these matters, using email as the main channel of communication, the participants were contacted, pre-informed and

involved with volunteering bases. Data were protected and used with anonymity and analyzed and disseminated accordingly in patterns of scientific publication (Jucan & Jucan, 2014).

3.8 Limitations

As focused on understanding technology integration in teaching English from exemplary teachers' perceptions and practices, my study limited analysis to teachers' pedagogical perceptions, practices and reflections along with individual factors. These variables are associated to results on exemplary teachers' skills of technology use in English class on constructing learning as analyzed on qualitative phenomenological case study design. To these limitations, my study covers methodological logic of using technologies in enhancing classroom practices on constructing learning upon the skills of communication. It brings findings related to these components by means of qualitative analysis that explores the exemplary teachers use of technology in English teaching within the communicative approach on blended-learning model. On this model, my study explores different pedagogical principles represented within the common framework of communicative approach in which exemplary teachers use technologies significantly on constructing learning. However, this study as limited to reporting from the selected exemplary cases and on pedagogical focus only, might not cover some other dimensions. Among others, my study was not able to cross compare teacher practices of technology use as one example of a dimension as could be related to developing teachers' skills of technology integration in class within various typologies. Likewise, concerning the data sources, my study, as confined to exploring the selected exemplary teachers' practices, doesn't directly draw the phenomenon from various levels e.g. school administration, support staff, people, students and macro management levels whose roles could be accounted to developing this phenomenon. Methodologically as based on phenomenological case study design my study could show methodological limitation as the case study expresses

the issue with a sense of advocacy, though limitations within the exemplary practices have been precisely stated in conclusion. Besides, my study doesn't mix up different methodological procedures e.g. analyzing the phenomenon in mixed methods research design which could add up along with credibility or validity, the sense of reliability lending a strength to generalizability.

CHAPTER FOUR

Findings on Case Study of Teachers' Technology Use in Teaching English Class

In this chapter I present findings on the case study related to teachers' perceptions, practices, reflections and relations of individual factors defined as personal and professional or context factors associated as first order and second order barriers to integration of technologies in English class.

4.1 Analytical Procedures Employed for Syntheses on Findings

The case analysis in this study began following an empirical pilot survey on teachers' TPACK⁵⁵ which informed the sample of the Czech elementary school English teachers practicing technologies in classroom on two distinct paradigmatic models. The practices were captured developing formal and functional models of teaching English characterized by grammatical and communicative teaching approaches (Brown, 2006). On formal models, teachers integrated technologies in class limitedly to communicate information (Warschauer & Healey, 1998) whereas on functional models the practices extended to developing classroom activities upon communication skills focus within blended-learning model (Warschauer, 1997). Four teachers in functional models were marked quite interactive regarding technology integration in English class selected herein as exemplary teachers.

To conduct the case analysis within variable-oriented analysis method (Miles et al., 2014), the variables specified in the central research question e.g. perceptions, practices, reflections, and individual factors (personal and professional factors) were used. For the

⁵⁵ Technology pedagogy and content knowledge, the findings regarding this issue have been published in the paper: Paneru, D.R. (2018). Information communication technologies in teaching English as a foreign language: Analysing EFL teachers' TPACK in Czech elementary schools. In *Transnational Perspective of Teacher Education, CEPS*, 8 (3) 119-142.

analysis, a tabulation (Appendix 2) was created representing the selected exemplary teachers' individual profiles also indicating their approaches with technology. Below are the common features of individual differences related to exemplary teachers selected regarding their practice of technology integration in English classes.

4.2 Exemplary Teachers' Personal Characteristics

The study teachers Donna, George, Dave and Jane in this study bear distinct personal backgrounds:

They vary in age, education background and teaching experiences. This entails their classroom practices of technology integration in English class with each teacher projecting technologies for teaching their subject within the framework of communicative approach, however, defined by individual ways and distinct principles. Each teacher has different individual context characteristics being it school system or students among others.

However, the selected teachers bear, as well some common components regarding the practice of technology integration in English class:

Their technology skills are self-learned on job through individual classroom experiences, they perceive technologies as useful. They use innovative tools for teaching and learning language as supportive to enhance learners' communication skills, they are self-motivated and interested in using technologies in order to improve classroom practices to develop learning processes. Also, they are self-engaged on a learning profession, appropriating technologies to practice teaching in communicative approaches on blended-learning model, even though they draw from different learning principles.

The stated features provided a conceptual framework related to the study of exemplary teachers' practice of technology use in English classes. It showed the representation of some common components leading the study of teachers to integrate technologies in class as

identified for a blended-learning model, even though each represented it on different principles. These were the main principles in practice as, learning by doing, learning by inquiry or problem, learning by collaborated actions, and learning by games.

Concluding the personal common characteristics and of individual differences as outlined, it was assigned the exemplary teachers' case. Technology integration in English class is primarily decided in relationship of teachers' practices with personal attributes as causative or linked to the development of the teachers' pedagogical perceptions or approaches which lead to understandings, experiences, reflections and so on. These relations of personal pedagogical and professional variables, known as first and second order barrier factors (Ertmer, 1999) as Tondeur, Braaka, Ertmer and Ottenbreit-Leftwich (2017) claim, define teachers' practices of technology use in class. This way, case analyses of the selected four exemplary teachers' practices of technology integration in English class in this study are based on the outlined phenomenological suggestions presented hereafter.

4.3 Exemplary Teacher 1 Donna

Considering teacher's practice of technology integration in teaching English class in Czech elementary schools, Donna is an exemplary teacher. She works at a reputed school located in the South Moravian region of the Czech Republic. In her mid 30s Donna has taught English for more than 10 years. She possesses master's degree in English and Health Education and is the school deputy. Hence, apart from teaching English, she undertakes several responsibilities that keep her exceptionally engaged. However, on professional accounts, Donna expresses herself as a pro-active English teacher. Her activeness as an English teacher is evident in her daily actions of preparing lessons, teaching 5 to 6 classes, updating the curriculum renewing its goals, principles, practices and teaching technology. Besides, Donna

keeps herself engaged in seminars and conferences that enhance her teaching competences or learning technology (Interview, October 5, 2017).

Hereafter, I present Donna's practices within the categories of her perceptions, practices and reflections as sub-titled to align with her decisions, ways and skills of practices and her reflections regarding individual technologies in her class.

4.3.1 Donna's Perceptions on Decisions to Technology Use in English Class

Donna perceives technologies as primarily interactive teaching-learning tools useful in teaching English to today's digital generations for communication skills. She, herself is profoundly interested to use technologies in various ways that support her teaching styles as guided towards learning by doing principles on blended-learning model. She believes that technologies are important because to her students learning English is for real-life communications for which the use of technologies enables her to bring real global contexts, cultures and skills lending students an opportunity to communicate and learn by practice. Technologies are seamless in her class and are integrated in alliance with her course objectives. She, too uses technologies beyond class teaching such as in preparing lessons and in learning her profession. Donna suggests that technologies used in mature ways help augmenting quality of lessons in enhancing students' learning skills. Donna asserted, "ICT are better to use to meet different purposes for teaching digital natives."

Within her teaching scheme, Donna perceives and decides to use both offline and online technologies not just add-on stuffs but integral educational tools, sources and systems of practical significance in English class. In this regard, she accounts her teaching approaches on greater role leading her to decide on the use of different individual technologies in her class. In part, she also acknowledges her students' growing digital interests as influential for her to decide to use English music, audio-visuals and movies. Taking into account that her students'

digital interests influence her decisions, Donna said, “The difference is mostly that children today learn by watching English movies with sub-titles, playing computer games in English. That is very positive.” As indicated, Donna uses various simulating media that engage her students to learn language in skills with activities.

Her students’ digital interests are considerably pressing her to use online technologies. However, Donna perceives, and likewise decides, that blending both offline and online tools and media under her own guidance as essential to addressing learning purposes or functions that technologies are potential for. She thinks that online sources such as, Google, Wikipedia, YouTube etc. and presentation tools as pertinently useful in the activity or project-based lessons presented to students allow them to autonomously explore content, materials, do projects and presentations. Other technologies, however are thought of being useful for teaching grammatical items blended with communicative activities. On her schemes, Donna’s practices appropriate these different technologies such as: Laptop, iTOOL, projector, online learning sources and media like, Google, Websites, YouTube and downloaded English audiovisuals, music, movies, and diverse subject relevant information on photocopy papers.

Drawing on her decisions for using (or not) the listed technologies in her class that relate with motivations and conversely barriers, Donna expresses mixed experiences. She perceives and decides to use both offline and online technologies though differently. For instance, relating offline technologies, Donna pointed out, “Though not without technical problems, iTOOL, photocopied materials on language skills and downloaded English documentaries and movies about history, cultures are very useful teaching aids.” As revealed, Donna decides mostly on these listed technologies in her class for teaching and preparing lessons. Regarding the online technologies, Donna spells them in the project and presentation lessons. She reported, “Computers and online sources are useful in the bigger projects.”

However, when it comes to enable students to free access to online sources and media without teacher's guidance, Donna expresses a critical perception. In this regard, she said, "Technology is not very personal." Further, specifying the issues faced, Donna added, "Yeh, you might find some material problems, but you can avoid them and choose other materials." As signaled, along with the extended uses, online technologies are as well associated as main factors that distract students (Blacker & Mackie, 2008). Yet, as Donna suggests, teacher's mature guidance in helping students to learn selecting materials, is still a solution explored by her. In other words, instead of avoiding the online technologies, Donna appropriates them under teachers' guidance enabling students to use media on constructing skills.

Despite her mixed encounters as outlined, in real practice such as in lesson planning and in teaching class, Donna integrates both offline and online technologies interactively involving herself and her students in various tasks-learning activities. In this regard, she specifies offline technologies e.g. iTOOL, projector, downloaded audio-visuals, movies and photocopied items and online sources e.g. Google, websites, YouTube etc. for a use in different types of English lessons in different activities and purposes. Donna relayed, "My students do work projects, send emails, they do things online, they do problem solving tasks, they do write essays, and put pictures."

In her daily work of lesson preparation, Donna uses the school laptop supported by technologies for materials that she uses to integrate with textbook language and its curriculum. Donna reflected, "I prepare on laptop, use the book, its activity books. Obviously, if I find something interesting, I use YouTube, the internet, data projector." Also, Donna uses emails while lesson planning. She said, "I open my computer for checking emails. There are parents' questions I need to respond to." In a reason for using technologies in preparing lessons, Donna expressed, "Now- a- days, it is not about the teacher to get ready all the materials, you can search and find materials." As her expressions illuminate, one main reason among others for

Donna using technologies, is to get ready materials as relevant to teach English. The other main reason for Donna using technologies on preparing lessons relates to students' digital motivations in learning. In this regard, she expresses heterogeneous learning interests in her students who however are motivated in digital-based lessons with activities integrated. Donna reported, "My students argue in class when we practice lessons with downloaded audio-visuals and topics. It really makes lesson successful." Reflecting on heterogeneous learner motivations, Donna added, "Some of them like to do mobile work, some them like to work on computer, it differs from pupil to pupil." As revealed, learners' growing digital motivations are as well among some key reasons for Donna's use of technologies in lesson planning as well as to prepare activity blended instructions.

As far as practices of technology use in lesson planning is concerned, it meets Donna's decisions, experiences and practices of technology use in real class teaching. In class context, Donna decides to blend various types of technologies along with the textbook in different ways, activities, purposes and functions. She generally decides to use textbook, iTOOL and photocopied materials in lessons designed on vocabulary and grammar focus and assessments. For example, Donna informed providing a reason, "I prefer textbook and writing by students in vocabulary learning. It makes them write and think." Also, textbook and photocopies are decided on assessment purposes, Donna reported, "I test grammar, vocabulary, speaking, listening activities, working in the class, homework for which textbook has sufficient material."

The other types, as downloaded videos, audios, movies, films etc. in Donna's class teaching are considered in lessons on communication skills such as listening, speaking, reading and writing integrated. Besides, different online sources and media in Donna's class are decided for use in class project lessons as well as in student presentations. She reported, "We have projects. Students use online sources to do them and send to me by email. It is not always, it is once a month." In justification on why she decides the projects once a month, Donna expressed,

“I don’t want them to work on computer all the time. But for the bigger projects computers are good.”

4.3.2 Donna’s Practices of Technology Use in English Class

Following her decisions regarding the use of different technologies, integration of technologies in Donna’s class is determined on how she uses the mentioned individual technologies in daily encounters. On this matter, Donna provides answers to these questions as what technologies are used, in what types of lessons and activities, how are the tools used or what her own roles and roles given to students, why are they used or which purposes and functions the used technologies fulfil in her class. Answering these key questions Donna exhibits her practices of both offline and online media as basically for practicing instructions on blended-learning model that she conceptualizes on learning by doing principles as outlined hereby.

On blended-learning model of teaching English, Donna integrates the current textbook content with offline and online technologies of various types as equally important materials and teaching aids. She relates the textbook as enriched with multiple new content, contexts and cultural skills related to the English language. She perceives these items as stimulants leading her to integrate new technologies which then enable her to invent new instructional strategies and skills as helpful to increasing student learning motivation. Donna pointed out that, “This English book has interesting English cultural content. It has DVD (iTOOL).” Besides, Donna links the textbook as accompanied by the exercise-book and photocopy items more useful aids than electronic sources when it comes to teaching grammar and vocabulary components. She said, “If you learn vocabulary, you want to use it, it is better if you write the words by hand, make them think about them and textbook is much better.”

The other use of the textbook as explored by Donna is connected to changing her teaching strategy and it is sometimes for balancing class when noisy especially in task-based instructions as supported by use of online technologies. In this manner, Donna reported, “I should say, it is ideal to practice all the skills as necessary in the lesson. If the class is too noisy, I prefer to give them grammar, so that they don’t have time to talk.” With this experience, Donna illuminates her encounters of using online technologies in class. As indicated, their uses cause problems of class management that then lead to learning barriers. The other problems with digital and online tools as Donna usually encounters are technical types. She reported, “There occur technical problems in the class with the projector or the online materials.” In such situations thus, textbook used in an integrated way is a better solution for keeping learners in constructing learning. However, in the integrated frame, Donna uses various technology-based materials as listed above that enable her to switch new activities and engage students in pair work on language skills-based practices, solve problems, write and present content etc.

In activity integrated lessons, Donna interprets it as useful to integrate online technologies specially in preparing projects occasionally to enhancing students’ presentation skills. Donna informed, “The online sources provide free access to information for projects on multiple topics that students do themselves”. Highlighting this she describes that project lessons bring English embedded in native cultural skills as the given curriculum also demands and hence, online sources supplement skills learning needs. She said, “The text book is British. It is about British culture, Canadian culture, American culture or the countries where English is the first language.” By asserting these points, Donna admits that the online sources are primarily important to get her students exposed to English in its cultural settings, contexts, skills etc. In short, as her practices reveal, along with usual textbook-based language and activities, she integrates various offline and online media for special purposes among others in designing multidisciplinary skills focused English lessons on learning by doing model. In the activity-

based lessons as these Donna gets a chance to actively scaffold the needy students as one of the main advantages of technology use in her class.

Drawing on Donna's approaches, ways or techniques, purposes and functions of class practices of technologies, she exhibits appropriate technologies as interactive educational media for creating learning through both extrinsic and intrinsic motivation to her students. In this regard, her practices project the offline technologies with downloaded content and materials as useful in constructing language skills focused class practices on listening, speaking, reading, writing etc. skills. In line with these, Donna appropriates the online technologies to blend language and activities given in the English textbook with new items of learning for materials and activities that involve such as English games, audiovisuals, music, documentaries, movies, and project materials e.g. content or information about history, cultures etc. Donna informed, "We use the online sources for games, oral language skills, English movies, project topics and information about English history or cultures." Below follows an example of her ways of using offline and online technologies as observed:

Donna displayed an online documentary on YouTube in which English speakers were interviewed to explain what they wanted to be when they grow up and following, students in groups presented on the projector their tasks on what each of them wanted to be in future (Class observation, October 5, 2017)."

Such were the common class practices and ways of technology use in Donna's class. The practices of technologies in Donna's class activities also entail blended activities with items such as, watching English films followed by writing to solve the problems related to the content of the film displayed. As an example of activity-blended lesson:

Donna arranged class in groups to watch a movie about spaceship. Then she distributed a task photocopied. Having watched the movie, the task was to be completed by students in

groups. She herself moved through the desks providing necessary cues and feedback (Class observation October 6, 2017).

Expressing her purposes behind these practices, Donna said, “These blended activities extend beyond only grammar lessons. These lessons motivate my students to engage them actively to practice communication, also I should say, watching movies entertains kids.” Moreover, in the skills focused blended-lessons as these, Donna multiplies her roles from disseminator to facilitator.

Apart from the skills focused lessons as built on audio-visuals, movies etc., her ways of using technology, their purposes and functions also consist of practices of class projects and student presentations that she designs each month. In the class project lessons, Donna primarily integrates the online technologies such as Google, Wikipedia, YouTube with projector for the purpose of sourcing information and on task designing. In these activities, she provides her students online links to explore information, pictures, materials for individual and group tasks set on different themes. Her students explore information online, write their projects and present the tasks on PPT models. Donna relayed, “We have projects. Students use online sources to do them and send to me by email. I mark them, give them the feedback, display their errors.” As Donna further interpreted, the activity-integrated project lessons are significant in motivating her students to construct English for communication on their own and for her to play facilitative roles. Therefore, she prefers practicing class projects by using the online technologies and media. Donna mentioned, “I love communicative activities because that is more important way of using English for abroad communications.”

In short, as the class practices of technologies reveal, Donna has explored various ways of integrating the technologies. Her ways of technology use in the skills focused and project-based lessons designed as student-centered and blended-learning models are significant in enhancing communication skills. In practices as these, technology integration as helpful to

blending learning skills and activities on learning by doing principle serves a purpose of creating intrinsic motivation rather than limiting technologies supplying extrinsic motivation.

4.3.3 Donna's Reflections Regarding the Use of Technologies in English Class

In addition to the impacting role of inventive perceptions, experiences and class practices, teacher's reflections determine technology integration in teaching in long term prospective. Teacher's reflections also contribute to reforming individual factors that take shape on personal and professional characters (Dewey, 1933) and contextual elements as well that come related as motivational or conversely barriers in developing the phenomenon.

In general perceptions, Donna expresses mixed experiences and encounters with technologies. Although, her reflections regarding the integration of both offline and online technologies in her class in developing student-motivated learning processes, are significantly explorative and creative. In this regard, though Donna reflects the issues of learner distraction with online media, she creatively reflects solutions. As she proceeds, instead of letting students uncontrolled access to media as potential to learning distraction due to de-educating materials, a much better way is to enable students to use media under teacher's guidance. Donna reflected, "There can be material problems, but you can avoid it, choose other materials."

The other way as Donna reflects is to download the online learning materials such as, English writings, audiovisuals, movies etc. and integrate with the English textbook items in class. In this regard, Donna reflected a downloaded documentary-based lesson about an English tourist place that was integrated for group writing activities, as an example of a successful lesson which it was possible due to the online sources. Donna said, "It was a successful lesson, you saw, some students talked, but it engaged all students who are really not same in competences. They argued and communicated." In this way, despite some critical encounters with the use of online technologies, Donna's reflective actions and efforts and ways of guiding

students seem significantly related to enabling her to integrate the media effectively on constructing student-learning process. As such, in her reflective expressions, Donna displays a change in her previously expressed perceptions regarding online media. In these, she reflects the online technologies as essentially useful to blend language and activities in creating learning motivation in her students instead of using the book for merely grammatical lessons. The integrated class activities for Donna increase students' participation in taking ownership of learning. She too, reflects and interprets the online technology integrated activities going beyond class teaching and hence, constructively developing learning as an ongoing process.

4.3.4 Donna's Individual Factors as Related to Technology Use in Class

Also, to some extent, practices of technology integration in class are determined by teachers' individual factors that constitute on personal and professional characters and context factors. In this regard, Donna reflects her interactive learning attitudes and her explorative approaches primarily accountable, reforming her professional characters or context factors enabling her to invent practices of technologies. Donna reflected, "Students are smarter than me in ICT, I obviously learn a lot from them." As her statement lends idea, Donna learns from her students as her context factors. This attitude also pushes her to self-explore ways to use technologies on inventing new techniques and strategies to teach her students effectively. She said, "About ICT I got to know by my own efforts."

Donna's individual factors are counted in two main terms that constitute her internal or personal and as well professional characters as given:

- 1) Internal factors e.g. her education, digital literacy and her personal perceptions and attitudes.
- 2) External factors e.g. her teaching technology cultures that particularly relate with school system and her student factors.

In qualification, Donna has a master's degree in English. However, her digital literacy is informal but self-educated. Donna reported, "I learned to email when I was in London on a study." Likewise, she recalled, "I learned to make presentations while in University." In perceptions and attitude, Donna presents herself as an interactive personality who likes to learn new ways, techniques, technologies and improve her teaching today's digital generations. Donna relayed, "I am open, I must say, I love learning things and changes." Shortly, Donna accounts these attitudes as her enablers to exploring new ways of teaching and likewise practices of technologies that significantly impact her teaching effectiveness. Linking her attitude toward students she concerns in building students' new skills. Donna said, "Students must learn communications skills, they need to use English abroad, they need digital skills." As revealed, Donna's constructive attitude encourages her to integrate new media and support her students learn English communication skills rather than transfer English in grammar.

The external factors are Donna's school teaching technology systems and her students' level of technology use. In these, she reports both growing in digital tendencies which she reflects positively helpful enabling her to explore new ways to practice technologies in her teaching. For instance, Donna commented, "Students learn to use and write on computer from basic. It is the difference in learning and it is due to technology." About school technology culture Donna reported, "All teachers in our school are active using technologies in general." Further linking her school with her learning professional or development, Donna said, "The school sends us for seminars on subject-teaching and technology." Besides, Donna's school has several external programs that she and her students get a chance to participate in. She reported, "We have several exchange programs, in these programs our students communicate in English and we engage on media communications."

As Donna informs, her external factors are supportive in many ways. However, while comparing, Donna reflects her own internal factors with more impactful role relating

technology integration in building her practice of teaching English. In this regard, Donna admits the role of her internal factors. These are: her interactive pedagogical perceptions or explorative and communicative approach to teaching English, her understanding about technologies as innovative educational tools, her attitude on students as digital natives, her personalized efforts in learning profession etc. For example, claiming these components, Donna said, “I love communication, technologies help to bring materials about English cultures for teaching communication.”

In this way, based on the experiences as outlined it is exemplified that practices of technology integration are significantly developed due to Donna’s internal factors and communicative approaches with determinant roles. Likewise, supportive to her internal factors are mainly her years of teaching-learning experiences, her understanding of learning in self-motivation, her approach to teaching as based on “learning by doing” principles, her perceptions on technologies as tools to constructing learning motivation etc. Some key features of Donna’s practice of technology integration in English class are summarized in the table in appendix 1.

4.4 Exemplary Teacher 2 George

George is the second exemplary teacher selected in my study. George works at an elementary school located in the South Moravian region of the Czech Republic. The school has been enriching its teaching-learning practices with fast changing digital systems and is well equipped with the modern technology infra-structure along with online operations of administration.

George has a bachelor’s degree in English along with master in pedagogy and is TESOL⁵⁶ certificate holder. In his early 40s, he has taught English for more than 15 years in the same school. George is the coordinator of English department. Hence, apart from teaching

⁵⁶ Teaching English to students of other languages

classes, he undertakes other responsibilities too. His activities related to technology integration in teaching English entail preparing lessons, teaching 6 to 7 classes, and updating curriculum also to coordinate other teachers about the curriculum goals, principles, practices, and teaching technology. He keeps himself engaged in learning via online courses for preparing himself to teach his digital savvy learners. George mentioned, “I remain exceptionally busy, I keep designing teaching things on computer, which is different from other English teachers in Czech schools (Interview, November 7, 2017).”

Hereafter, I present George’s practices within the categories of his perceptions, practices and reflections as sub-titled to align with his decisions, ways or skills of practices and his learning reflections regarding individual technologies in English class.

4.4.1 George’s Perceptions on Decisions to Technology Use in English Class

Drawing technology integration in English class, George perceives the modern media as considerably interactive and motivational teaching-learning tools for teaching his students new ways of communication skills. George himself is absorbed in work with technologies. He perceives technologies support him to practice teaching within blended-learning model as projected on learning by inquiry or problem solving principles (MacKenzie & Bathurst-Hunt, 2011). In his perception, digital/online technologies are important for mediating learning upon skills of communication since their uses enable to bring English embedded in real global contexts, cultures and skills lending the students multiple opportunities of learning by inquiry practices. Technologies are well integrated in his class as aligned with lesson objectives which he keeps reforming even beyond the English curriculum. He too, practices technologies every day in lesson planning. As for the critical perceptions, George expresses that though technologies are helpful, don’t teach themselves, and hence, teacher’s skills to properly use them are essential.

On learning by inquiry or problem based communicative approaches to teaching English, George perceives and decides to use various offline and online technologies as integral language learning tools and programs that enhance students' skills. As regards the factors influencing his decisions regarding the use of technology of various kinds in his class, George emphasizes his own teaching technology and approaches as considerably responsible. For instance, George said, "Although school encourages to use ICT, it more depends on my ways of teaching and lesson plans which I usually design on integrated activities e.g. quiz, games and inquiry learning processes."

In some ways, George also accounts his students varied digital interests as influencing him to use technologies for integrating varieties of activities such as movies, games, quizzes, inquiry topics, projects and presentations etc. George commented, "Now-a-days, ICT are normal for students." He then connected, "If you don't bring new items, students don't feel motivated." As signaled, students' digital tendencies are too varied due to which George finds using offline or online technologies in unintegrated ways of no significant use on creating learning motivation. Hence, George decides to use the media to integrate various materials, skills and activities such as language and activities as in the textbook and design skills-focused lessons for constructing learning motivation in his students.

Among different technologies, George appropriates English textbook with iTOOL on usual vocabulary and grammar focused lessons. He perceives and decides the offline and online downloaded materials in listening, speaking, language games, quizzes, reading, writing integrated skills focused lessons. Likewise, George appropriates the online technologies such as, Google, Wikipedia, YouTube, Language Programs on inquiry, student project and presentation-based lessons and activities. In different types of lessons as listed, George's classroom practices involve these main types of technologies integrated:

Laptop, iTOOL, data projector, photocopied materials, online downloaded audio-visuals and content, online sources and tools e.g. Choke.com for lesson planning, Google, YouTube, Wikipedia, Online language program (Port of your knowledge), and record system.

Integration of technologies is determined by teacher's decisions of using (or not) different technologies as listed in class which relate with teacher's experienced motivations and conversely barriers with them. In this regard, George's main encounters of barriers entail technical problems, problem of plagiarism, and problems of student loss of learning interest when frequently used in an unintegrated way. Regarding problems with online technologies in his practice, George pointed out, "Online sources are somehow distractive if not handled properly." Referring to technical issues, George said, "There is whiteboard in every class which is sometimes interactive sometimes not." On plagiarism, he informed, "Once I gave a project which one of his students brought all copied from Wikipedia." Likewise, linking the problem of student losing learning interest George commented, "These are shiny, flashy and attractive, but after 10 or 15 minutes, you will see students lose interest." As revealed, there are a number of issues of barriers related to the use of technologies in George's class.

In contrast to the above given barriers, George's perceptions and decisions also inform of his experiences of motivations in integrating technologies in class. In this regard, George expresses his motivations to use offline and online sources and programs of various kinds both in preparing lessons and class teaching on a wide range of activities, purposes and functions in different ways. George reported, "I use various types of ICT in different types of lessons as required every day." As his reports further inform, George decides the iTOOL along with the textbook and photocopied materials as useful in grammar-based lessons. George said, "iTOOL has everything; skills, reading, writing, grammar you need to teach." Likewise, he decides the downloaded audio-visuals and content considerably useful in the quiz, games and language skills-based class practices on integrated designs. Finally, George relates the online

technologies such as Wikipedia, Google, YouTube, online-language program (Port of your knowledge) in the lessons and activities on inquiry topics, projects and student presentations. He informed, “Online programs and Wikipedia are quite used in projects. We do inquiry topics and projects a lot, it is very active way of learning.” The digital devices are also useful for George in recording students’ oral skills for assessment. He said, “I find it very useful to record students speaking to assess.”

As his decisions inform, George expresses irrespective of offline or online technologies as motivational when used in the activity-integrated class practices whereas he decides them as useless used without activities in class instructions. For instance, George expressed his encounter, “ICT are helpful and do lot of things, but you will see after 10 or 15 minutes, students lose interest.” Connected to this, he reported, “I developed a vocabulary App. In the beginning, it was hype, but after a few days, students began to take it as usual.” By reporting the stated problem of loss in students’ interest as this, George convinces that using technologies in an unintegrated way is an ineffective practice. It is therefore, he decides to practice both offline and online technologies in order to integrate new learning materials, techniques and activities that can switch on student learning motivations. George said, “Yes students lose interest, so we have to keep switching new activities. I most often do quiz, inquiry and project lessons with ICT.” As indicated, Gorge expresses that teachers’ creative decisions are essential on creating learning motivation by integrating technologies in class.

Despite the mixed encounters as stated, in real practice, such as in lesson planning and in class teaching, George practices both offline and online technologies interactively involving his students in various task-learning activities. In preparing lesson, George plans his lessons on laptop using a software called choke.com. He informed, “It is an online software.” Explaining its usefulness George expressed, “I love this software because I can see whole week plan and can upload things what I need to use in class.” In line with this, George integrates

various offline and online tools, their materials and media with the textbook items in planning lesson. He reflected, “I use the notebook as well, which is useful in many ways, but it is always integrated with digital things.” In a reason among others for using various technologies or media in planning lessons, George expressed, “I find it easy to plan lesson with ICT, the real advantage is that you can revise and plan in many ways.”

The practices of technologies in lesson planning are followed by George’s inventive decisions, experiences, practices, ways and techniques of integration in real class teaching that then lead to knowing about his reflections. In this regard, George decides to integrate various types of technologies in class teaching in different ways to addressing student learning motivations. As also exhibited above, George decides using the textbook with its iTOOL and photocopied materials in lessons on vocabulary and grammar activities and assessments. He decides the downloaded audiovisuals, movies, and online content in quiz, game and communication skills-integrated lessons. Finally, his decisions appropriate online sources, programs and media in the inquiry, project and student presentation-based lessons. E.g. George reported, “I prefer online language programs and sources for inquiry-based topics and projects I have been doing for 10 years.”

4.4.2 George’s Practices of Technology Use in English Class

Following his decisions, George’s practices of technology integration in class are determined by how he uses the mentioned technologies on daily basis. In this matter, his practices provide answers to these questions as, what technologies are used, in what types of lessons and activities, how are the tools used or what her own roles and roles given to students, why are they used or which purposes and functions the used technologies fulfil in class. These questions are answered below in George’s practices of both offline and online technologies basically integrated in designing skills-focused activity, inquiry, and project-based instructions on blended-learning model.

On the inquiry-based blended-learning model, George's practices of technology integration consist of using the English textbook for its language and curriculum integrated with various offline and online media supported activities. Within the integrated design, he uses the iTOOL of the textbook specially in vocabulary and grammar-based lessons integrated with other supported materials. George reported, "The iTOOL makes it easy, quick and attractive to display grammar, I don't need to write texts on the board." Apart from grammatical instructions, George also uses the textbook as an effective teaching material to integrate other technologies and their items in designing language skills-focused activity-integrated class practices in substitute of using technologies just so. He relayed, "These days ICT can motivate students only when activities are integrated." More importantly, George integrates online technologies and media as profoundly useful tools for practicing inquiry, project and student presentation-based English lessons. On some occasions, George practices the online media and materials to entertain the class for a change.

Drawing his ways, skills or techniques, purposes and functions of technology integration, George exhibits appropriating both offline and online technologies interactively for teacher to actively facilitate with and for students to construct English in learning inquiry, project and presentation skills on blended-learning model. Within the mentioned framework, George uses the technologies as interactive means of constructing intrinsic as well as extrinsic motivation in students that however fulfil learning purposes. In such practices, George's ways of technology use support integrating varieties of activities for students to engage in practice of listening, speaking, reading, writing etc. communication skills. Besides, George's ways of using online technologies in students' project and presentation activities fulfil advance skills learning purposes such as inquiry or meta-cognitive skills.

In activity-integrated language skills focused lessons, George practices technologies for obtaining materials and to design classroom activities as well. These include, practicing

language games, forming skills-based activities by use of audio-visuals, science fiction movies etc. which motivate students to autonomously practice communication skills. George reported, “I use lot of online materials, it is to switch new activities even beyond the curriculum. Well, its function is to engage students practice communications.” Along with the mentioned functions, George accounts special purpose of using both offline and online technologies and it is to engage students in learning inquiry or problem-solving skills. George said, “Sometimes I bring recorded materials for inquiry lessons.” He claimed, “Inquiry lessons engage students in problem-solving activities, these increase students’ reflective skills.” Given here is an example of George’s ways and techniques of technology integration as practiced in activity-integrated inquiry-based English lesson as observed:

In a lesson on grammar in integrated model taught in language lab, George distributed words on photocopy paper that engaged students in pairs to reading and presenting meanings. Then he made students write a text on “What a friend of yours usually does on weekend?” using simple present tense verb. In groups, students could look at samples online on Wikipedia or google. George facilitated the groups in exploring ideas and write task. It was followed by question-answer interactions for George to assess students (Class observation, Nov 7, 2017).

Such were the common ways and techniques of class practices as mediated by the use of iT00L of the textbook, offline and online technologies. On occasions, the videos and movies were used to entertain class as demanded by students. In the skills integrated lessons as these George also varied his roles from just an instructor to a collaborating facilitator.

Apart from the skills-integrated practices, George’s ways of technology integration also relate his purpose of practicing project and student presentation-based lessons. In the project lessons, along with other sources, George integrates the online sources or media such as Google, Wikipedia, online language program, YouTube, multimedia projector. In these lessons, George enables his students to use the listed media in order to explore information, ideas, visuals etc.,

do projects and present. George informed, “I have lots of projects, in projects, I usually use online programs, like “port for knowledge,” and other media, for say, websites.” Elaborating their functions in the project practices, George communicates the used technologies specially for keeping him and his students active in practices of communication. In these, students in groups work in building tasks using technologies and George facilitates and assesses learning in his collaborative roles in class and beyond via online system.

Apart from practicing online technologies for creating learning engagement, George also expresses another reason after using online media to practice project lessons and it is for extending class practices beyond English curriculum. This is because the curriculum is limited to native English contexts whereas his students need learning international content and cultures instead. George pointed out, “The text book has only English language and its cultural things. It is brilliant to teach international students but not effective for Czech students.” As revealed, George integrates online media for the purpose of getting new materials for practicing projects on multiple topics and that is to compensate limitations of English curriculum. This way and in short, as the outlined class practices and ways of technologies use reveal, George exhibits to have invented various ways and techniques of using technologies in English class. His ways of technology integration in the inquiry and project-based lessons that center students in activities, seem significantly interactive practices in promoting students’ English communication skills.

4.4.3 George’s Reflections Regarding the Use of Technologies in English Class

In addition to the impacting role of teacher’s inventive perceptions, experiences and class practices, teacher’s reflections determine technology integration in his teaching. Teacher’s post-class teaching reflections determine individual technologies either useful or conversely useless in class. Besides, teacher’s reflections constitute on teacher’s individual creativity or constructive thinking and hence, also relate to reforming individual and contextual factors

(Dewey, 1933) that too associate as stimuli or conversely barriers in developing the phenomenon.

In general perception, George expresses along with his motivational experiences some critical encounters. However, his reflections regarding both offline and online technologies in the activity-integrated, inquiry, project and presentation lessons of English, are considerably innovative. In this regard, though George reflects using technologies in increasing frequency not effective to motivate students on increasing learning interest, in creative reflections, he alongside presents technologies as primary to supplementing or fulfilling learning motivations, purposes and functions. It is that instead of using technologies just so, George reflects both offline and online technologies as effective tools in activity-integrated English instructions that activate himself and his students actively in constructing learning on skills of communication. For instance, George reflected both offline and online technologies used for a list of activities as given:

Language games, quizzes, language skills, inquiry or problem-based class activities, student projects and presentations along with technologies used to record students' oral skills for assessment.

In the activities as given, George reported in substitute of the textbook used to practice merely grammatical lessons, digital and online media as effective to motivate students of varying interests on learning construction. In these lessons, George informed, technologies used partly to entertaining purpose, however, in interactively participated activities, he reflected both offline and online technologies served to engaging students in learning communications with intrinsic motivation.

Given is an example of his interactive actions of technology integration that present his creative reflections on a use of online language program that helped to blend reading, writing and grammar learning on engaging students in group activities. In this regard, George reflected

the “port of knowledge” language program used that helped to blend reading, writing and grammar on a problem-based topic as a successful lesson. He said:

It was a successful lesson, as you saw the students were learning on a flow from one to another activity. They used the program to explore ideas, learned reading and writing in groups. They also learned grammar (simple present tense) integrated with their reading writing activities.

Relating the use of online technologies in the inquiry lessons as intrinsically motivating, George reported another example of his creative ways of integrating technologies that increase reflective skills. George relayed, “Last time I assigned a project on free topic of problem. I instructed students to use Wikipedia for ideas. Although one girl did copy everything from the Wikipedia, most of the groups did well.” As was revealed, while asserting his post teaching reflections upon the activity-integrated and project lessons as reported, George succinctly expressed the impact of online technologies in increasing both his and his students’ reflectivity and learning skills. These practices for George increase students’ own agency leading to learning from controlled to free inquiry skills.

In this way in short, despite some encountered problems, George reflects use of online technologies significantly associated with creativity and learning English as skills constructing practice within activity-integrated designs in substitute of textbook or technologies used without activities integrated. In activity-based class practices, he finds his students collaborating or cooperating each other on learning purpose as related to increasing reflectivity. Moreover, activity-integrated or inquiry-based projects go beyond class and hence, use of technology extends to developing learning as an ongoing process. Thus, as potential for practicing integrated class activities, George reflects offline and more importantly online media as significantly associated to learning innovation in teaching English within communicative framework.

4.4.4 George's Individual Factors as Related to Technology Use in Class

As for concerning individual factors, George reflects his internal character as related to his practice of technology integration in class. In this regard, George accounts his interactions with students and his explorative attitude as positive to enhancing his skills of technology use that too link with reforming his personal and professional factors. George said, "In fact, from students, I learn what I need to bring in, it also takes me to reflect how to use technologies I bring." As clear, George's interactions with students help him to invent new ideas, skills, techniques and teaching technologies in increasing students' learning motivations. Besides, George claims his own explorative efforts affording to improve his individual aptitudes and context factors as associated to his actions of technological invention and their use in class.

George's individual factors are counted in two main terms that constitute his internal or personal and as well professional characters or external factors as given:

1) Internal factors e.g. his educational and digital literacy background and broadly his personal perceptions and attitude.

2) External factors e.g. his teaching technological culture that particularly relates with school culture or system and his student factors.

In qualification, George has a bachelor's degree in English with TESOL certificate and master's degree in pedagogy. His digital literacy is program-based training. George reported, "I attended training for a computer program developer but as my father's computer business collapsed, I decided to discontinue." In perceptions and attitudes, George presents himself as an inventive practitioner who keeps trying new approaches and teaching technologies. George said, "I don't like teaching in same way again and again." Linking his attitudes toward his students, George is collaborative and respectful of students' choices in many cases. He said, "I use ICT items, and you know I need to respond to my students' choices." In this way, with

similar claims, George accounts his internal attitudes and approaches as helpful for him to upgrade his practices of technology integration in teaching.

The other factors as related to his practice of technology integration are his school culture and his students. Relating both, George reports them progressive in digital tendencies that too stimulate him to engage inventing ways of technology integration in class teaching in developing learning process. George reflected, “ICT are too common for students to excite them. So, you need to keep bringing new items and activities that can engage them in learning.” About school culture, George said, “The school likes us to try new things.” Further his school is mentioned to be supportive regarding learning profession or development. Besides, George engages in school’s external cooperation programs such as Erasmus plus, and others in that he said, “I coordinate all these programs since our students participate. These are helpful in promoting communication skills.”

As the reports inform, George’s external factors are supportive in many ways. However, he reflects his internal characters with more impactful role as related to his skills of technology use in English class which he appropriates within activity-integrated inquiry-based learning model. In this regard, these internal individual factors are accounted for main roles:

Georg’s knowledge of modern pedagogical principles and communicative approaches, his creative skills and approaches to technologies, his attitude on students as digital savvy generations, his own efforts in learning profession.

Besides these components come supportive to his internal factors e.g. years of teaching-learning experiences, his approach to teaching on learning by inquiry or problem-solving principles, and his self-motivation in learning interactions.

The main features of George’s practice of technology integration in English class are summarized in the table in appendix 1.

4.5 Exemplary Teacher 3 Dave

Dave is the third exemplary study teacher selected in my study. She works at a Grammar (Gymnasium) school located in town in Vysocina region of the Czech Republic. The school is advanced in digital systems equipped with modern technology infra-structure along with online systems developed for everyday administrative purposes.

Dave has bachelor's degree in English and German. In her late 30s, Dave has taught English for more than 15 years. Apart from teaching school classes of English at elementary level, Dave gives private lessons with what she keeps herself busy. Besides, she engages in professional courses online related to teaching English and technology. Dave said, "I usually remain busy, I often consult Websites (Visit your teacher) and other learning platforms." Her main activities connected to technology integration in teaching English class entail lesson preparations, teaching 6 classes a day, some private lessons, surfing online sources for materials, designing tasks, learning courses etc. (Interview, December 12, 2017)."

Hereafter, I present Dave's practices within the categories of her perceptions, practices and reflections as sub-titled to align with her decisions, ways or skills of practices and her learning reflections regarding individual technologies in English class.

4.5.1 Dave's Perceptions on Decisions to Technology Use in English Class

Drawing technology integration in English class, Dave perceives technologies as innovative, interactive and motivational tools for teaching students' communication skills in English. In her perception, learning English for today's students is for real-life communications on international levels for which the use of technology helps her bringing real national and international contexts, cultures and skills in class lending students an opportunity to learn interactively. She said, "These are media for communication and well, we can discuss things."

Dave is self-motivated to learning and use digital media to improve teaching English develop as an innovative learning practice. Dave believes technologies enable her to put her students in practice of collaborated projects, peer-teaching and in presentation lessons that promote them to learn communication skills on blended-learning model. Technologies are well integrated in her classroom practices and are aligned with curriculum objectives and beyond. As for the critical perceptions, Dave perceives that online sources have too much information which might distract students. She mentioned, “I find no problem, but I’d say, online ICT have lot of information that creates chaos for teenagers.” In such a situation, hence, Dave draws importance of teacher’s role to help students cope with learning pressure.

On collaborative learning model, Dave appropriates various offline and online technologies as integral educational tools for teaching in integration of a variety of collaborative activities that enhance students’ communication skills. In this scheme, as regards the factors that influence teacher’s decisions for using technologies in class teaching, Dave accounts her school context only as a basic factor. Whereas she takes her own approaches on developing learning in collaborative model and her perceptions of technologies as media for transparent communications accountable factors. For instance, Dave said, “The school is advancing in digital systems. But I’d say, it is my preference to teach communication skills, integrate lots of activities, I need ICT more.” Dave too takes her students digital-integrated learning motivation as accountable influencing her to use these listed types of technologies and activities e.g.:

Language games, problem topics and items, audio-visuals on listening, speaking, reading, writing skills, online information and materials for mini and big projects and student presentation activities.

Linking her reasons why Dave decides to use digital or media-based materials and activities, she commented, “Students don’t feel excited with ICT just so, well, ICT have become normal like face-to-face communications, so, I’d say, we need activities to switch on their

interest.” As signaled, though technologies merely don’t motivate students, are potential to design interactive practices. These lead Dave’s decisions to integrate them for new materials, content, activities in creating interest in students on learning engagement in new contexts.

In her collaborative approaches, among different technologies, Dave perceives and decides to use the English textbook with its e-version together with its online-links on vocabulary and grammar lessons. She appropriates the offline technologies such as, photocopied items, downloaded audio-visuals, music and items in games-based, listening, speaking, pronunciation, reading, writing skills-focused lessons. Likewise, she draws on online technologies such as Google, Wikipedia, YouTube, online platforms, Facebook and emails in mini and big projects, and student presentation-based lessons. She also reports the online system developed by school and Facebook appropriated in homework and assessment purposes for communicating tasks or materials between teacher and students.

Technology integration in English class context is determined by teacher’s decisions to use (or not) different technologies and media which might be related as experiences of motivations and conversely barriers. In this regard, despite her own motivations, Dave also expresses some critical barriers and as indicated above, her critical perceptions rest on the use of online technologies faced as causes of learning distractions. For example, Dave said, “There are too many materials due to ICT, I feel like can’t go through which I’d say is a problem, it distracts students too much.” Among others, her encounters of barrier entail some technical problems, problem of copy and paste of a task by students and technologies without activities as common as traditional teaching. Dave maintained, “It is very difficult, sometimes, students copy and bring ideas which they themselves don’t know.” Likewise, linking technologies as grown normal and hence not exciting for students on learning, Dave reported, “ICT don’t these just excite students, they have become too common as face-to-face communications.” As

revealed, there are a number of issues related as barriers to the use of technologies in English class for Dave to tackle with.

In contrast to the outlined barriers, Dave's perceptions and decisions regarding different technologies in English class as well inform of her experiences of motivation. In this regard, Dave relates technologies of various kinds for a use in a wide range of activities and purposes specially in practice of instructions as based upon collaborated projects, peer-teaching and communication skills-integrated classroom practices. In these, Dave decides and expresses her motivation to use iTOOL of the textbook with its online links along with different offline and online technologies in various ways. Inter relating them, Dave perceives English textbook with its iTOOL and online links essentially useful to engaging students in grammatical and in peer-teaching lessons. She informed, "The book has its e-version and online links, it has all language skills, reading, writing, it is very useful for grammar exercises that students need to practice in groups, and sometimes students teaching students." Likewise, Dave decides on various photocopied items, downloaded content and audio-visuals particularly to be used in conversational class exercises and language games yet in integrated ways.

Finally, Dave expresses her decisions of motivation on the online media such as language-based Websites, Wikipedia, Google, YouTube etc. specially in student collaborated project and presentation lessons which serve enhancing metacognitive skills. Dave reported, "We have several mini projects and 10 big projects in a year, these activities are advance skills based, in these, students use several online websites and platforms." In line with, Dave also integrates the online media to assess her students' oral skills. She said, "I use the online technologies to make interactive tests." In this way, as her motivations inform, Dave perceives and likewise decides to use technologies of various kinds in interactive ways in a wide range of activities integrated to practice classroom instructions upon communication skills-focus

However, when it comes to using technologies without activities or on grammatical scheme, Dave expresses them as ineffective as textbook used to transmitting English texts that students hardly grasp. Dave commented, “Just ICT don’t excite students, nor they teach without teacher using them.” Relating technologies with barrier to learning, Dave said, “Well, the problem is, ICT engage teenagers with materials that entertain instead of engaging in language we would like them to learn.” By reporting such encounters, Dave sheds light on technologies used without proper activities or mainly to transmit information make no significant contribution to motivate students in learning English. It is therefore, Dave decides both offline and more importantly online media to blending varieties of new activities, projects etc. to switch on students’ learning interests.

Despite her perceptions or decisions upon online technologies as causes of learning barriers, in real practice, such as, in lesson planning and in class teaching, Dave practices both offline and online technologies interactively involving her students in communication skills or task-learning activities. In lesson preparation, Dave plans her lessons on her tablet (laptop) availed by the school using various offline and online sources and media for integration of a number of skills learning activities. She informed, “I use my tablet, photocopy, projector, internet to prepare lessons.” Expressing reasons and her purposes for using the mentioned technologies in planning lesson, Dave said, “Well, I plan lessons with ICT, I’d say, these make lessons attractive and also motivate students.” Also, her practice of lesson planning involves the use of email and Facebook. Dave reported, “I communicate with my students on Facebook. I send materials that they have to prepare for the following day.” Among other reasons for using technologies in preparing lessons for Dave is due to a perceived benefit such as, increasing speed and transparency of information that a teacher needs while engaging students in learning. Dave expressed, “It is a quick way of doing things, I can put all data my students need, it is transparent...they can go through lot of materials, it is lot more helpful for students to focus in

English.” As revealed, Dave integrates technologies of various kinds in planning lessons and one of the key reasons after her practices, is on a key purpose being to create learning environment.

The practices of technologies in lesson planning are followed by Dave’s inventive perceptions, decisions, experiences and practices of technology integration in class teaching that then lead to understand her reflections. In this regard, in her teaching schemes, Dave decides to use the textbook with its e-version in vocabulary and grammar-based class practices, downloaded audio-visuals, music, movies and photocopied materials in language skills-integrated and student peer-teaching instructions. Dave said, “I provide audio-visuals on listening, reading lessons that students teach their part in class. It is student-to-students teaching method.” Linking this model with activity orientation, Dave then appropriates various online sources and media in project lessons and student presentations. Explaining these decisions Dave said, “Students doing presentations in projects results into learning motivation than other way using ICT.”

4.5.2 Dave’s Practices of Technology Use in English Class

Following the role of perceptions relating decisions to use different technologies, technology integration in class is determined with Dave’s ways and skills of using them on her daily encounters. In this matter, Dave’s classroom practices of technology integration provide answers to these questions e.g., which technologies are used, in what types of lessons and activities, how are the tools used or what her own roles and roles given to students, why are they used or which purposes and functions the used technologies fulfil in her class. These questions are answered below in Dave’s classroom actions of technology use basically in practice of skills-based student peer-teaching and collaborated project lessons on blended-learning models.

Within the collaborated learning framework, Dave practices various offline and online technologies along with the English textbook language and its activities integrated in class teaching. In this regard, Dave uses the textbook with its e-version and online links specially in class practices designed on vocabulary and grammar practices in integration with technology-based content, contexts or activities. Dave said, “This English book has several exercises on grammar and language skills that I use along with activities in the e-book and extra ICT materials and sources.” Linking her key reasons for using the textbook with its e-version in grammatical lessons, Dave informed, “It is necessary to use the textbook, well, it has the whole curriculum. I mean all sets of language, its skills that students need to pass.”

Apart from the use of textbook with its e-versions, Dave integrates various offline and online items, and these are used to design language skills-focused instructions engaging students in practice of communication skills. In these activity-blended designs, both offline and online technologies are practiced, and the key intent is to integrate listening, speaking, reading and writing activities, language games, student peer-teaching practices, student collaborated projects, and presentations. Dave reported, “Definitely I use lot of online learning tools and platforms, online pages connected with the book with different activities.” She further informed, “I use the online tools and platforms for practices on writing topics such as writing about English speaking countries, their food, questionnaires, listening, speaking.” Part of Dave’s class practices include the use of online technologies specially used in testing students’ listening and writing skills, as well as photocopy materials in assessing grammar and vocabulary components.

Drawing on her ways and skills or techniques, purposes and functions of technology integration, Dave exhibits appropriating both offline and online technologies as interactive learning media of use enabling her to actively facilitate and her students to construct English by practicing skills in collaboration. In this regard, Dave claims her ways of technology use as

based on active teaching that motivates her students learning to solve problems, doing projects, presenting tasks and practice communications even going beyond the curriculum. She mentioned, “My students are too much into ICT, they love doing projects, preparing all the projects, well in the form of presentations.” In Dave’s practice, though technology use limits to serving extrinsic motivation in some cases, in activity-integrated instructions, she manages to integrate offline and online technologies which instead engage students in learning to collaborate and practice English in tasks in learning to construct with intrinsic motivation. In these, she integrates technologies as rich sources of information, for materials and as tools to design student-activated cultural skills focused class activities primarily fulfilling learning functions. Dave said, “I feel that ICT absolutely help learning purposes, well, students are motivated to do activities, learn cultures, which won’t be possible without.” Projecting technologies as useful to constructing communication skills, Dave further informed, “I remember when I was a student, it was difficult to learn communication, there were no computers, now it’s different, media help a lot.”

Besides, Dave’s practices of technologies in students’ projects are interpreted for a special function and it is to multiply hers and her students’ learning efforts that would yield communication skills learning outcomes. She informed, “Students need a lot of effort, practice communication to learn English. I ‘d say ICT activate me and my students to learn communication.”

Along with the mentioned functions of the technologies as realized in the skills-integrated, project and presentation-based lessons, Dave also accounts students peer-teaching practices as one of the active learning practices. In these class practices she enables students to use the technologies and teach. This manner of technology use does a significant job in creating intrinsic motivation. Given is an example of Dave’s class practice in which media are used by her students in student-to-students or peer-teaching practice as observed:

In Student-to-student teaching, students in turn taught a problem-solving lesson that integrated use of grammar supported by an online program displayed on a smartboard. The teaching student discussed the content and provided answers whereas other students interacted with her/him. In case of difficulty, teacher scaffolded the class. Teacher both monitored the activities from the back and in the meanwhile, she too regulated other students' turn for teaching their parts (Class observation Dec 12, 2017).

Such were the common class practices mediated using textbook, offline and online technologies. In the skills-integrated lessons as this, Dave varied her role from information conveyer to facilitator and facilitated students on group tasks. On some occasions, Dave also appropriated online sources for materials such as downloaded videos, music and movies used to entertain the class for a purpose to change environment.

Apart from technologies appropriated to practice skills-integrated English lessons as instrumental to raise student learning motivation, Dave also expresses another purpose of using online technologies/media in her class. As she connects, the online sources or media are integrated specially in student collaborated project lessons and the main purpose is to enable students enhance intercultural skills. This process drives learning beyond the current English curriculum practiced in Czech schools. In this regard, Dave argues that the textbook is only about English cultures whereas her students require learning English in cultural skills of different countries. She pointed out, "This textbook in whole curriculum has only English contexts. I'd say, it is the drawback, so, online ICT are necessary for information about different cultures, also our local cultures." As signaled, Dave integrates various online sources and media in class also for a purpose to designing instructions that integrate different cultures, technologies and literacies or subjects of learning significance. In such practices, online technologies are used to bringing English embedded in cultural skills as related to enhancing communication skills on driving learning beyond the linguistic system.

In short, as the outlined classroom practices reveal, instead of practicing teaching as exclusively technology based or limited to English textbook on grammar focus, Dave appropriates various offline and online technologies in activity-blended English lessons. In this regard, Dave's uses of technology that too make upon the influence of students' digital motivations are considerably varied, however, her ways of technology appropriation specially in student-to-students teaching and student collaborated projects, come significantly related to addressing learning as these practices seem to be based upon and serve developing students' skills of communication.

4.5.3 Dave's Reflections Regarding the Use of Technologies in English Class

In addition to the impactful role of teacher's inventive perceptions, experiences and class practices, teacher's reflections determine technology integration in teaching English in long term prospective. Teachers in post-class teaching reflections decide individual technologies either as useful or conversely useless/barriers to learning in real class teaching. Besides, teacher's reflections constitute on teacher's individual creativity and actions of constructive thinking and hence, are associated to reforming individual factors (Dewey, 1933) as might be related as stimuli or conversely barriers to technology integration.

In general perceptions, Dave expresses along with her motivations, some critical encounters specially with the online technologies as outlined above. However, her post-teaching reflections regarding both offline and online technologies for practicing activity-integrated or student collaborated project lessons, are considerably interactive. In general perceptions, Dave expressed the online technologies with a regard as cited here, "Perhaps, with online sources students love using teenager material rather than learning grammar we expect." However, in her post-teaching reflections, Dave expressed the online sources, portals, and media including Email, Facebook etc. as considerably supportive on constructing learning in

practice of student collaborated multi-thematic projects drawn on, “learning by collaborated action,” principle (Liaw & Bunn-Le Master, 2010).

Along with the use of online websites such as YouTube, Wikipedia and online learning portals and downloaded content in projects, Dave reflects their use in the creative-writing or topic focused classroom practices formed on student-to students teaching pattern. In student-to-student teaching, Dave finds her roles interacting from instructing to scaffolding and in projects collaborating with students via emails and Facebook for communicating materials, information and as well providing support and feedback on students’ tasks. She reflected the below mentioned student-collaborated projects as successful way of teaching and technology use which enable her students to practice critical and communication skills. As an example, Dave reflected:

Once I had a project lesson in computer lab. We did on different topics of students’ interest. Some chose sports, some cultures, technologies. All students were too much into it. They loved exploring information online, groups wrote creative ideas, did cooperate each other, pasting pictures. I’d say everyone loved the activity. So, if students love, it is successful lesson. Well, it was successful also due to the online platforms I gave the link of (Interview December 12, 2017).

As revealed, Dave in her post-teaching reflections, admits the impact of technologies in increasing her students’ learning agency, though her creative skills are equally accountable enabling her students to integrate the technologies in constructing learning process. In project lessons, Dave reflects the online technologies used creatively by her students to collaborate in groups, cooperate each other, take ownership of learning in exploring information, construct and present tasks skillfully. In such practices, Dave reflects herself playing the role of collaborator when learning is constructed by students. In the technology integrated practices as

given, Dave herself explored new strategies and skills which helped to increasing learning reflectivity in herself and alongside in her students.

In this way Dave's post-teaching reflections express various offline and online technologies as useful to practicing student-to-students teaching and student-collaborated projects, are significantly interactive. From these communications, Dave's explorative actions along with creative reflectivity come associated as key components that transform her existing perceptions, skills, and practices in achieving technology integration upon developing learning process.

4.5.4 Dave's Individual Factors as Related to Technology Use in Class

In her information, though her school factors are supportive in role to some extent, Dave accounts her internal characters that constitute her individual factors as primarily associated to her skills of technology integration in class. In this regard, she accounts her keen interests on using technologies and her communicative approaches to teaching as the main enablers. As reflected above, in English instructions as based on diverse activities integrated or the ones practiced within communicative approaches, Dave increases her learning interactions with students. From students, she explores various new ways of technology use in developing learning process. She reflected, "Well, I know from students what they love, what they learn better, specially, in activity-lessons as I and students interact a lot." Clear enough, in classroom practices as formed within communicative approach to teaching English, Dave's learning interactions increase which function as enablers to use technologies not just so, but to integrate new activities. At this point, hence, Dave's communicative approaches as internal factors play a catalyst role that enable her to invent new skills of teaching including use of technologies to enhancing quality of English classroom practices. These components also link with reforming

Dave's individual factors as constituted with her personal and professional attributes or characters.

Dave's individual factors are articulated in two main terms such as:

1) Internal factors e.g. her educational and digital literacy background and broadly her personal perceptions and attitude.

2) External factors e.g. her teaching technological cultures that particularly relate with school culture, support etc. system and her student factors.

In education, Dave has a bachelor's degree in English and German, but her digital literacy is self-learned. Dave reported, "Well, I got basic trainings, but I'd say, I learn ICT mostly in work." In perceptions and attitudes, Dave is creative practitioner and is well into inventing teaching technologies and new approaches. Dave said, "I love exploring new items for my students, I 'd say, I love ICT a lot." Linking her attitudes toward her students, Dave interacts with her students, makes her efforts to motivate them in learning. Dave explained, "I'd say that motivation and mutual understanding between teacher and students are more important than other things." She too follows students' choices in many ways. Dave informed, "I use music, movies well, to motivate students learn English sounds and speaking, students love these stuffs a lot." In this way with similar claims, Dave takes her internal characters or personal approaches significantly as accountable to upgrading her practices of technology integration in English class.

The other factors as related to her practices of technologies are school and student factors. These factors as Dave reflects are advance in digital systems and tendencies and push her to exploring new ways and techniques of technology use on developing learning process. Dave reported, "Students love activities on computer, they love them, I love them too, so, we have no problem with ICT." About school culture, Dave said, "The school is very advance on digital system." As a part of school's digital activities, her school also has an online magazine

publishing every 6 months. Dave relayed, “There is an online magazine for teachers and students to publish their creations online.” Besides, her school supports her to take seminars and conferences in learning profession and has external projects related to technology skills that involve teacher and students to participate. Dave said, “We have cooperation projects. These are also related to media, we teachers and students take part. The projects are communicated virtually.”

As the outlined reports inform, Dave’s external factors are supportive enough. Yet, as compared to these, Dave claims her internal individual attributes equally and even more influentially associated to fostering her skills of technology use in developing teaching English as a metacognitive skills-learning process. In this regard, below outlined internal or personal and professional factors are accounted as significantly related to Dave’s classroom practices of technology integration:

Her constructive perceptions and keen interests to work with technologies as media for interactive communications, her communicative approaches to teaching, her years of teaching experiences, her learning attitudes toward students as creative learners, her own digital learning engagements or her own efforts on learning profession.

Supportive to Dave’s internal individual factors and professional skills as outlined, her collaborative approaches are noted as being the unique features that primarily contribute to developing technology integration in English class as a learning process. The main features of Dave’s practice of technology integration in English class are summarized in the table in appendix 1.

4.6 Exemplary Teacher 4 Jane

Jane is the fourth exemplary teacher selected for my study. She works at an elementary school in a town located in the southern Bohemian region of the Czech Republic. Jane's school is in the early stages of installing digital system which sets it in the early phase of development relating technology integration into the process of teaching and learning the school subjects.

Jane holds a bachelor's degree in English and is still a Pedagogy student working towards her master's degree. In her mid-40s, Jane has taught English for 20 years, though her experience of teaching English at elementary school has been of 10 years. Jane teaches English at her school along with some private lessons. Besides, she spends her time playing computer games as a hobby. Jane said, "I play lot of computer games. It helps me improve English teaching." Her main activities related to technology integration in English class entail preparing lessons, teaching 5 English classes a day, teaching private lessons, surfing online materials, playing computer games in English etc. (Interview, December 8, 2017)."

Hereafter, I present Jane's practices within the categories of her perceptions, practices and reflections as sub-titled to align with her decisions, ways or skills of practices and her learning reflections regarding individual technologies in English class.

4.6.1 Jane's Perceptions on Decisions to Technology Use in English Class

Drawing on technology integration in her class, Jane perceives modern technologies as innovative and motivational learning tools to enhancing English classroom practices within communication skills learning focus. Jane said, "ICT are active learning tools." She is highly absorbed in learning new skills, techniques and technologies for teaching English for which she believes they are of extended significance. According to her, technologies are important means of learning English for real-life communication, technologies enable her to bring English embedded in real contexts and cultures that she uses to engage students in practicing English in

multimodal communication skills. Jane uses trial and error method to integrate different technologies, and these help base the classroom instructions in activities for English games, group participated tasks, projects and presentations within blended-learning model. Technologies are well appropriated in her everyday class practices including teaching grammatical items aligned with curriculum objectives and games-based lessons that she designs even beyond the curriculum. Concerning critical perceptions, Jane thinks that online media in some respect distract students in ways and in others technical problems create barriers. Jane said, “I have no problem but online sources for children, they need to be careful and yes, sometimes connections ha ha ha...” In such cases, Jane perceives that teacher’s participation with students to be important and to help them select and use appropriate technologies and materials on skills learning focus.

On the game-based skills-integrated teaching models, Jane tries to appropriate various offline and online technologies interactively used to blend various types of activities in classroom practices and the key intent after all is to engage students in interactive practice of communications. Within her scheme, as regards the factors that influence teacher’s decisions for using technologies in class, Jane assumes her own keen interests in technologies and her communication skills focused teaching approaches as majorly accountable. Jane claimed, “It is me who is fond of technologies. I like using computers, smartboard, play games.” Partly, Jane too takes her students’ interests in learning English with technologies as accountable that influence her to use these listed technology-based materials and activities as:

Language games, country and cultural topics, audio-visuals on listening, reading etc. skills, online-based information, materials and technologies on projects and presentation tools and activities.

Explaining students’ interests Jane said, “Students like to play video games and learn to communicate in English with these technologies.” As shown, Jane’s perceptions upon modern

technologies as potential to design interactive lessons influence her decisions to use technologies for integrating activities and language games with materials, content, context, culture and skills of English communication invented. These in turn are perceived to motivate students in their English practice upon skills of communication learning that forms within practice of cultural skills.

Within her scheme of teaching, among different technologies, Jane perceives and decides iTOOL of the textbook in usual vocabulary and grammar lessons as in curriculum. She appropriates the offline items such as, photocopy materials, downloaded audio-visuals, pictures and e-content in listening, speaking or skills-focused lessons. Likewise, she decides the online sources and media such as Wikipedia, YouTube, Google and other websites in language games, topic-based lessons, projects and students' presentations. Jane also decides to use the online-book in homeworks and sometimes Facebook in projects to communicate tasks to students. Jane said, "I have Facebook but only sometimes used, during the project activities."

Technology integration in teaching English class is determined by teacher's decisions to use (or not) different technologies. Decisions involve teachers' personal encounters or experiences and as such, express motivations and conversely barriers related to the use of technologies as practiced by teachers in real class context. In this regard, despite her own interests and perceptions of motivations to use different modern technologies or media, Jane, alongside expresses some critical experiences. In her critical encounters, online sources or media in some cases are faced as main elements to distracting students from learning due to mass of information of unwanted quality. Jane pointed out, "But children have to be careful about online sources. They have too much information and so, I don't think they can learn English without guidance." Jane also finds her school tough resources a barrier to her decisions to use modern technologies. She informed, "I can't use ICT in every lesson. There is only this class with these facilities." Sometimes, technical problems and problems of copying and pasting

by students are also seen as barriers. In technical problems Jane asserted, “Sometimes internet doesn’t work, I can’t really do anything.” Relating copy and paste problem, she said, “In projects, some students copy from Wikipedia which is not good.” Likewise, she also decides using technologies all the times not interesting nor motivating students toward learning. In short, as revealed, there is a number of issues or barriers related to the use of technologies in teaching English class that Jane has to cope with on everyday basis.

In contrast to such barriers, Jane’s perceptions and decisions also inform of motivating experiences regarding the integration of technologies in her class. In this regard, Jane’s decisions express her motivations to use various types of technologies in practice of instructions formed by integrating language games, group activities on language-skills, students’ projects and presentations. Emphasizing her motivations, Jane informs her decision of not using the English textbook. Instead, she perceives its iTOOL with the online links as motivating and decides to use these in vocabulary and grammar focused classroom practices. Jane said, “iTOOL has everything of the textbook, its grammar, vocabulary, I don’t need to use the book.” She appropriates offline technologies such as, photocopy items, downloaded content and audio-visuals as useful for group activities in conversational exercises, topic-based reading-writing lessons, and language games integrated. Accordingly, Jane expresses her motivation to use the online sources and media such as, Wikipedia, Websites, Google, YouTube etc. in projects and student presentations as intended to enhance students’ metacognitive skills. She relayed, “I allow students to use online sources to do projects on topics, like countries, traditions, celebrations as Christmas.” Jane also integrates the online media to assess skills. She said, “I use the online ICT to test students’ listening, speaking.”

At this point, as her perceptions that influence her decisions to use the outlined technologies, Jane decides to use different offline and online technologies and the key purpose is to enhance classroom practices, though the idea of using technologies each day in each lesson

type is deemed ineffective. For example, Jane argued, “Using ICT all the time is not good, when you use it just twice a week, it is interesting.” The quotes indicate that Jane decides to use different technologies or media not in all types of English instructions but in practices that she creates by blending language games, skills focused activities, projects and presentations.

Despite her mixed encounters, in real practice, such as in lesson planning and in class teaching, Jane decides and practices various offline and online technologies interactively involving herself and also enabling students to use them in skills learning activities. Jane plans her lessons on a laptop and iTOOL of the book using various offline and online sources. Expressing reasons and purposes for using technologies in lesson planning, Jane said, “It is easier preparing lessons simply because we can use many sources.” Also, her practices of lesson planning involve the use of online websites and tools like Wikipedia, YouTube etc. Jane explained her purposes of using them, “I use online for language games, different creative topics on reading and writing and projects.” Among other reasons and purposes of using technologies in preparing lessons, Jane relates them for sourcing information about new skills and ways of learning English. Jane said, “Online ICT let us bring new ways and skills for me and my students to learn English.”

4.6.2 Jane’s Practices of Technology Use in English Class

The practices of lesson planning are followed by Jane’s creative experiences and practices of technology integration in class teaching that then lead to knowing about her reflections. Jane’s classroom practices are determined by her ways and skills or techniques of using different technologies on daily encounters. In this matter, Jane provides answers to these questions as, which technologies are used, in what types of lessons and activities, how are the tools used or what her own roles and roles given to students, why are they used for or which purposes and functions the used technologies fulfil in her class. These questions are answered

below in her integration of technology basically in practice of games based, task-integrated and project lessons practiced within blended-learning models.

Within the games-based and skills focused activity-integrated learning framework, Jane practices various offline and online media on trial and error basis. In this regard, Jane uses the iTOOL of English book in the usual types of vocabulary, grammar-focused classroom practices formed in integration with online based content, contexts and activities. Jane said, “The iTOOL has several exercises on vocabulary, grammar and it too provides online content and materials for games or cultural learning topics.” The main reasons for using iTOOL and its online links, among others entailed as expressed by Jane, “Students need everything grammar, vocabulary, communication skills which this iTOOL makes easy to practice.”

Apart from the use of iTOOL in usual lessons of English curriculum, Jane practices various offline and online sources and media in designing instructions on language skills in an integrated design. Within the integrated design, she integrates different offline and online technologies specially to form the activity-integrated class practices as based on skills of listening, speaking, reading and writing, language games, group projects, and students’ presentations. Jane reported, “I use various ICT and online sources for games, activity-based practices and also projects that mix students to practice communications.” Part of Jane’s class practices include the use of photocopy materials and online sources in testing speaking, listening, reading and writing skills. Jane informed, “I sometimes use the online ICT for assessing students’ listening, reading/writing skills.”

Drawing her ways, skills or techniques, purposes and functions of technology use in English class, Jane exhibits appropriation of different offline and online technologies as interactive tools allow her to actively facilitate, and her students to construct, English in practice of language games and projects on cultural and real-life communication skills. Linking her ways or skills of technology use as related to a purpose of supporting her students to

construct learning, Jane explains, “Some children are very interested in learning English, they prefer using computers in projects, boys specially love games, I must say, ICT in my teaching fulfil communication purposes.” While reporting her ways of technology use such that form in student-participated games-based instructions, creative writing and project-based lessons, Jane informs that technologies in active learning lessons fulfill a key function which is to create intrinsic learning motivation in students on learning English upon scheme of communication skills. In this regard, Jane further linked, “I find computers and online sources very much motivating, you saw my students into games and in activities, communicating, they learn English automatically.” In some cases, Jane also uses the online technologies in activities as focused on entertaining students working as means of extrinsic motivation, though supportive to changing learning environment.

In communicative approach-based activity-blended lessons, Jane finds students engaged in learning English by themselves in activities such as playing games, doing projects, and presenting group tasks etc. In these, Jane and her students use technologies that support their efforts to enhance new skills as related to language. Jane asserted, “I feel ICT make me and my students active.” Active learning practices engage students in making use of technologies that help to explore new content and design tasks, whereas teacher facilitate students on designing tasks. She said, “In project lessons, I let my students use online sources to explore information and work in groups and I facilitate.” Moreover, Jane accounts her students enabled to use mobile to communicate information related to project works. She said, “I let my students use mobiles to search materials in special projects.” Along with this, the other purpose for enabling students to use mobile in projects as Jane exhibited was to allow students to collaborate and complete the tasks autonomously.

Given is an example of Jane’s ways of technology integration in English classroom practices designed in project on a blended-learning model:

Jane introduced the topic called What on a Date. She displayed the items online and discussed the topic which was followed by group practices. Teacher visited every table to groups engaged to exploring things online and write What on a Date. One student performed the writer, the other explored information using the internet, all did the task and the third student presented orally. Homework was writing the same topic from their work book using past tense (Class observation Dec 8, 2017).

Such were the common group-participated class as well as project activities as mediated by the use of offline and online technologies in Jane's English class. In these, Jane multiplied her roles from the instructor to facilitator helping students to engage in group tasks interactively. On some occasions, she also appropriated technologies in activities that better entertained students as demanded.

In addition to the purpose of using technologies to engage students in language games that motivate the practice English skills of communication, Jane also expresses another key reason after using online technologies/media in project lessons which is teaching English upon skills of intercultural communication that the current English curriculum lacks. In this regard, Jane said, "Though it is ok the book is about English cultures, I want students to know how to compare different cultures." She added, "With the online sources, we get information about Czech cultures e.g. Christmas, Halloween etc." At this point, as the expressions exhibit, Jane's main motivation, among others for using technologies, is due to potentials of media that bring English embedded into skills of different cultures. Integrating them, as Jane claims, enhances English classroom practices which enable her students to learn English in skills of real-life communication integrated.

In short, as the above reports reveal, instead of using technologies just to practice English instructions that transmit grammar in digital form, Jane's ways of technology use are for engaging students in practice of English upon skills of real-life communication that she

ensures by means of class activities organized with games, projects, students' presentations etc. integrated. As Jane said, "ICT need to be used in a balanced way for skills not just in every lesson." By asserting these points, Jane too, signals her perceptions upon technology use are varied. However, as her classroom practices lend a sight, her ways of technology use in language skills-based, games-based, projects and student presentations, are interactive enough to addressing her purpose of teaching English upon skills of communication or learning as a metacognitive skill.

4.6.3 Jane's Reflections Regarding the Use of Technologies in English Class

In addition to the impactful role of teacher's interactive perceptions and class practices, teacher's reflections determine practice of technology integration in teaching English on developing learning process. Teacher's reflections regarding technologies in class teaching bring into light among others, experiences of stimuli and conversely barriers of using individual technologies in real situations. Teacher's reflections as well lend idea of how teacher's individual factors that constitute on personal and professional attributes or factors are related to her/his practice of teaching and technology.

In general perceptions, Jane alongside her interests and motivations, also expresses some barriers with the use of online media. However, her reflections regarding the use of offline and online technologies in English class in designing instructions on language skills, games, projects and presentations integrated, are quite interactive. In this regard, Jane expresses use of technologies in every English lesson as not effective. Yet, in her post-teaching reflections, she presents different media as associated to increasing reflectivity and learning skills specially in games-based, projects and students' presentation-based class practices designed with a focus on communication skills. Besides, in these practices Jane reflects her interactions with students as contributing to foster her own skills and learning reflectivity. It is in increased learning

interactions with students that Jane invents new teaching strategies, skills or techniques and technologies in the activity integrated instructions in which she also extends beyond the English curriculum. As such, in the games or skills-integrated classroom practices, Jane asserts both offline and online media significantly used as working tools that help her developing learning process. Described below is a unique practice of technologies used in English class practiced on project model by students' groups instead of usual projects as reflected:

We did a project on a topic, What American Children Eat. Students in cross-groups had to do it using the online information sources and present in the class. One group had to write about breakfast, the other group lunch, other dinner and so, as a joint activity. Although some students did copy information from Wikipedia, most of the groups presented it very well. It was really a successful lesson. I found my students hooked in the topic that engaged them interactively in learning (Interview on December 8, 2017).

As the given example reveals, in project-based English instructions, Jane reflects increasing student agency on learning as supported using online media or technologies. Besides, she lends a sight that teacher in project along with games-based lessons, is creatively involved in helping students use technologies that mediate learning English in skills of communication. In other words, in projects, Jane's students learn to participate in groups, cooperate with each other, and take ownership of learning and Jane herself increases her role by collaborating to facilitate and assess group tasks. In these practices, also technologies are reflected in use which helps to raise teacher and student collaborations beyond class and hence, to develop learning as an ongoing process. In this way, seen with educational potentials in integrating skills learning activities, Jane reflects online technologies as significantly associated to constructing English in practice of skills, though offline technologies are equally quite meaningful on learning focus.

4.6.4 Jane's Individual Factors as Related to Technology Use in Class

In Jane's expressions, although students' learning motivations as external contextual features are consented for a role as external factors leading her to use technologies, she claims her internal characteristics as her attitude and personal background being primarily associated to her skills and practices of technologies in teaching English class. In this regard, Jane exposes her own interactive pedagogical approaches as the key enablers to explore new ways of teaching and integrate technologies of different kinds as well. Jane's activity and games-based classroom practices developed within her communicative approach to teaching and technologies also make it possible for her to support her students learn and help them rescue from learning distractions. Jane reflected, "I communicate with my students, it helps me know about their problems, it actually helps knowing how they learn..." Clearly as it is expressed by Jane's interactions with students function significantly for her to exploring new strategies, ideas and techniques that promote her practices of teaching or teaching technology which in real sense develop within her communicative approaches to teaching and technology as internal factors that contribute to changing her personal and professional characters.

Jane's individual factors that contribute to professional attributes and practices of technology integration in teaching English class are articulated in two main terms:

- 1) Internal factors as her educational and digital literacy background and broadly her personal perceptions and attitude.
- 2) External factors as her teaching technological culture that particularly relates with school culture, support etc. system and her student factors.

In terms of qualification, Jane holds a bachelor's degree in English and is still a university student of Pedagogy, her digital literacy is informal and job-based. Jane informed, "I should say just by practice because when I was a student there were no computers. So, I didn't learn that at school." In perceptions and attitudes, Jane presents herself as an interactive

teacher who keeps exploring and reforming teaching technologies and approaches. Jane said, “I am still learning using technologies and English.” Linking her attitudes toward her students, Jane reflects herself as a collaborator who loves helping students learn how to use technologies and solve problems or develop English in practice. Jane relayed, “I love helping my students to use technologies for appropriate materials to learn English.” Jane too accepts students’ choice while choosing technologies. She said, “I bring games of my students’ choice.” In this way, with similar claims, Jane lends sight of her internal characters and approaches significantly interactive as accountable to developing practices of technology integration in teaching English as skills learning process.

Other factors related to her practice of technologies relate to school culture and students. In relation to school, Jane reports that it is still in its primary stage however, her students growing digital motivation are associated to her motivation in inventing new ways of technology integration on developing class practices as interactive learning processes. About school Jane said, “We don’t have enough money, we have one laptop for all English teachers.” Linking student factors, she relayed, “Students love activities on computer, they learn English faster with computer games.” Besides, her school doesn’t have external cooperation programs, nor does it send teachers for seminars and conferences on professional learning. However, Jane has attended several training courses on her own and has taken digital learning subject in master’s degree to upgrade her professional capabilities. Jane reported, “We don’t have school projects.” She then informed, “I am now studying ICT in master’s pedagogy.”

In short, based on her reports as outlined, Jane’s internal individual characters constituted on her intrinsic factors are accounted which come related as enablers to inventing new skills or techniques of practicing technology integration in enhancing classroom instructions. In this regard, Jane’s internal characters, as given, are represented for greater role on developing skills of technology use:

Jane's self-initiative digital learning engagements and communicative approach to teaching, her years of teaching experiences, her student loving attitudes, her regular efforts of learning profession. The main features of Jane's practice of technology integration in English class are summarized in the table in appendix 1.

CHAPTER FIVE

Discussion and Conclusion

In this chapter I discuss the findings on the cases or study teachers' exemplary practices of technology integration that triangulate with therefore differing from the current literature. The discussions that develop on a theme which illuminates exemplary teacher' practices of technology integration to some extent correspond with current literature whereas in other perspectives, the practices as well differ. The discussions also shed light on similarities and differences resulting from learning principles that differ on individual bases on which English teachers, such as the exemplary teachers represented in this study and existing research, engage in developing this phenomenon with personal encounters. With these key findings the discussion concludes the thesis relating exemplary teachers' technology practices on a common framework of communicative approach to teaching and on principles of learning differences though that characterize the blended-learning model. Finally, the conclusion of this thesis is that technology integration in teaching English develops as a comprehensive learning process in exemplary teachers' unique or qualitative pedagogical skills and cultural themes focused on using technologies as a tool for communication skills learning.

5.1 Preliminary upon Discussion

Technology integration in teaching a school subject such as English in global circles (Arnesen, 2010), has been variously captured and developed both on research and user or teacher practice levels that approach this phenomenon from different perspectives (Lund & Lund, 2006). It is therefore that school subject teachers in some situations are represented using technologies traditionally whereas in others, teachers also integrate the tools on learning

significance. In this regard, Tondeur, Braaka, Ertmer, Peggy and Ottenbreit-Leftwich (2017) claim differences in teachers' practice of technology integration in classroom primarily due to a key role of teachers' internal attributes that constitute on pedagogical beliefs or perceptions. Pedagogical perceptions lend teachers approaches, attitudes, interpretations and skills for using technologies (Jimoyiannis & Komis, 2007). Besides, teacher perceptions as linked to individual's learning reflectivity come associated as internal factors developing this phenomenon in substitute of external factors. For instance, as Sang, Valcke, Braak and Tondeur (2009) elucidate, teacher perceptions constitute of a spectrum of individual pedagogical approaches and understandings, interpretations and these develop with teaching experiences. Based on the individual perceptions, as Drossel et al. (2017) elaborate, teachers decide to and use (or not) different technologies in classroom contexts as appropriated in individual ways. From this point of view, technology integration in teaching a subject in class situation rarely develops on a homogenous framework. However, within the phenomenological account from the literature, as informs Angers (2005), the possibility of common components in representing teacher practices that develop on an interactive or integrative pedagogical frame, does not yet decline. Within the integrative pedagogical or communicative approach framework, teachers practice technologies not centrally to completing curriculum but also beyond, though with differences in learning principles that in real context develop through individual encounters.

In my study, following the idea of common components, the selected exemplary teachers' practices of technology integration in English class were analyzed with the results as synthesized within communicative approaches on blended-learning model. However, the analysis too, enabled a view of each teacher's ways, skills, purposes and functions of technology use which were based on different learning principles such as learning by doing, learning by inquiry, learning by collaborated actions, and learning by game. The exemplary teacher practices came expressed on different learning principles since each teacher interpreted

or understood communicative approaches regarding technology integration in teaching English in ways of individual distinctions which I discuss in this chapter.

The discussions in this chapter are formed to assess the synthesized findings on exemplary teachers' practices of technology integration in English class drawing upon the main epistemological learning principles as adopted, practiced and developed by each case in framework of common representation and of individual differences (Deaney, Ruthven, & Hennessy, 2016). In this regard, exemplary teachers' pedagogical perceptions, practices and reflections are discussed as key variables to exploring the phenomenon in complexity. These variables as Tondeur, Hermans, van Braak and Valcke (2008), Lund (2003) and others examine, express subjects' individual phenomenological experiences, interpretations and knowledge regarding technology use in real class. The epistemological principles as developed by the exemplary teachers in my study are discussed in triangulation with the existing research experiences. On this matter, the findings triangulate with and also differ from the research reporting technology integration from teacher perspectives that differ in learning principles being based on individual perceptions, practices or subjective experiences (Godwin-Jones, 2015).

Linking the discussions to assessing exemplary teachers' experiences of technology integration in English class in triangulation with and difference from the existing research, as discussed below, the findings agree with the studies. That claim the role of teachers' pedagogical perceptions, approaches, skills of using technologies as main features in developing the phenomenon as a learning process. Whereas, exemplary teachers' communications on their practices only partly agree with the literature that ascribes major role to external and/or technological factors. On these matters, teachers' interactive pedagogical approaches or perspectives and innovative educational skills are expressed as associated with the use of technologies to reforming classroom practices. In these, technologies are perceived,

interpreted, decided, appropriated, used and reflected by teachers as interactive educational tools to creating contextual shifts and horizontal moves (Erickson, 1997). Exemplary teachers' perceptions, practices and reflections fully express individual approaches, skills and actions in real context. Inherently, these aspects lend a key idea as to how teachers, as main actors (Mueller, Wood, Willoughby, Ross, & Specht, 2008) have involved to developing this phenomenon in long term prospect. In this sense, the discussions with the accounts of variables that illuminate how teachers decide, use and reflect technologies in English class answer qualitatively the overarching objective of this study exploring and describing how technologies are part of exemplary teachers' everyday teaching English class in Czech elementary schools. The discussions are sorted within the sub-titles devised in answering the central research question, how exemplary teachers use technologies in English class and how their individual factors contribute to use of technologies in individual class. On this, the discussions are set within these categories. Being them teachers' perceptions on decisions to use technologies in English class, Teachers' technology use in English class, Teachers' reflections regarding technologies in English class, and Associated factors to teachers' use of technologies in English class.

5.2.1 Teacher Perceptions on Decisions to Use Technologies in English Class

Teacher perceptions defined as teachers' pedagogical beliefs, attitudes, approaches, understandings, actions, skills, techniques etc.(Deng et al., 2014) are generally associated as key to influencing teachers' decisions to use (or not) individual technologies in teaching a school subject. Yet, these components in the existing literature are variously interpreted. For instance, research holding instrumental view on technology focus in line with Gebremedhin and Fenta (2015) correlates teachers' perceptions positively to increasing use of digital tools highlighting the role of technologies as environmental factors. Research on this perspective,

hence, undermines pedagogical approaches or rationales. In contrast, research on comprehensive focus explores major role of teachers' pedagogical perceptions as instrumental to how teachers integrate technology in class in ways of individual differences (Ertmer, Ottenbreit-leftwich, Sadik, Sendurur, & Sendurur, 2012). Following this perspective, body of pedagogical research e.g. (Somekh, 2008; Hermans, Tondeur, Braak, & Valcke, 2008 ; Deng et al., 2014) etc. claims teachers' pedagogical perceptions as primarily associated to influencing teachers' decisions to use (or not) individual technologies in real class teaching.

On a comprehensive focus, a few noteworthy research communications elucidate the role of teachers' pedagogical perceptions or approaches to developing technology integration in classroom context. For instance, Tondeur et al. (2017) have studied a relationship between teachers' pedagogical beliefs and practices of technology integration in class teaching as based on aggregative analysis of 14 research projects. In their study, pedagogical beliefs are defined in terms of teachers' perceptions/approaches as constituted on teachers' individual characteristics identified as the first order barriers (Ertmer, 1999). Tondeur et al. claim that context factors as second order barriers (Ertmer & Ottenbreit-leftwich, 2010) do influence yet on marginal level. Their study takes teachers pedagogical approaches called first order barriers as primary to influence teachers' decisions and practices to developing technology integration in real class contexts. Having set primacy of teachers' pedagogical perceptions/approaches, also as signaled by Deng et al. (2014), the authors further assert. Teachers in (social) constructivist pedagogical approaches perceive, and likewise decide to use various kinds of offline and online technologies in ways as invented to practicing student-centered classroom teaching (Godwin-jones, 2010). In these, teachers not only integrate different digital devices, sources, media, online links, tools etc. for only teacher purpose but as well enable students to use the technologies to construct learning by being engaged in authentic tasks (Danan, 2006).

In agreement with the existing research experiences, the selected exemplary teachers, Donna, George, Dave and Jane in my study perceive technologies as supportive to their communicative pedagogical perceptions/approaches. Likewise, the selected teachers perceive regarding technologies of various kinds as key enablers to inventing new pedagogical approaches or instructional strategies and skills on constructing learning come to influence their decisions on the use of technologies. As synthesized in the finding chapter, the exemplary teachers in interactive perceptions and attitudes make decisions voluntarily to use different offline and online sources and media. The key intent after exemplary teachers' decision or selection of technologies in English class is to develop teaching as task-based or interactive learning practice in which the use of technologies is perceived as supportive and also key enabler to enhancing classroom practices within communicative approach framework on blended-learning models (Ba, 2006). Also in line with Angers's (2005) cases, the exemplary teachers in my study in communicative pedagogical perceptions appropriate and decide new technologies as effective media to learning profession which in principle corresponds with Stoll's (1999) concept of enhancing inner capacities. Besides, the exemplary teachers in my study with key role of their interactive pedagogical approaches overcome external barriers to their decisions to use different technologies in class on developing learning process (Ertmer, 1999). This is in agreement with the finding in their study by Setyowati and Widiati (2014) that accounts English teachers' communicative pedagogical perceptions as key to innovating teachers' decisions to use different digital or online technologies upon skills learning focus.

Despite agreement with the existing research experiences as outlined, each exemplary teacher in my study also exemplifies differences from existing research relating teacher's pedagogical perceptions on decisions to use different technologies in class within communicative framework. In this regard, some studies on teaching English within communicative approach framework in line with Dooly's (2011) tele-collaborative

participatory model generalize English teachers open in perceptions deciding online technologies exclusively for students to autonomously use on learning construction. In contrast, the exemplary teachers in my study differ from these findings. Since as synthesized in the finding chapter, each teacher decided to use various offline and online technologies in practice of English instructions within communicative approach framework with classroom activities that differed in learning principles, purposes and functions, and learning outcomes. For instance, Donna perceived offline technologies as useful in lessons to integrate grammar with conversational exercises or in creative writing activities. She decided to use yet only selected online sources and media in “bigger projects only,” that triangulate with Dooly's (2011) tele-collaborative participatory model in that online technologies engage students in activities of learning communication skills based on learning by doing principle (Tai, 2015). However, in her pedagogical perceptions, Donna thought it useless to enable students' free access to open online sources, since these are perceived as more transmitters of de-educating materials that learning barriers than media on developing learning.

The arguments supporting the key role of teachers' pedagogical perceptions as main to influencing teachers' decisions to use technologies in class in ways of individual difference come supported further by noted differences across the exemplary teachers themselves. In this regard, though exemplified for technology use in teaching English within blended learning model, in contrast to Donna's decisions as outlined, the other exemplary teachers as George and Dave in my study express a step further in advanced perception regarding their decisions to use online sources and media along with offline technologies in English class which differ in purposes and functions. These teachers perceive technologies of various kinds in creative writing, language skills-focused and project-based instructions formed in student-to-students teaching model. These decisions lead technology use that supports in Wheeler, Yeomans and Wheeler's (2008) classroom projection in which teacher decides to use media to facilitate

student activities with “student-created content.” Besides, agreeing with Dooly (2011), these teachers didn’t perceive it de-educating to enable students an access to open online sources and media e.g. online educational websites, web-pages, portals, platforms, and communication media as Facebook. Instead their decisions to use such technologies come associated to their collaborative pedagogical perceptions on deciding to use media student-collaborated mini and big projects on cultural themes. These exemplary teacher decisions as expressed support the research findings that align with Lee (2011) who captures these components in teachers approaches to teaching English upon teacher-guided inquiry-based model on intercultural themes. The other exemplary teacher Jane in my study, too supported these pedagogical perceptions as primarily linked to her decisions to use both offline and online technologies. However, her decisions rested more explicitly on learning focus with principles that she emphasized as based on learning by games model (Hwang, Shih, Ma, Shadiev, & Chen, 2015).

The findings as expressed by the exemplary teachers that inform the primary role of teachers’ pedagogical perceptions/approaches influencing teachers’ decisions to use (or not) certain types of technologies in real class teaching, have been supported in several other studies, (Bain, Bain, Mcnaughtw and Mcnaughtw, 2006; Mueller, Wood, Willoughby, Ross and Specht, 2008) etc. These studies claim that despite some barriers to technology use, teachers’ interactive pedagogical perceptions or approaches enable teachers to self-invent new teaching-learning materials, skills and likewise, new technologies and ways of integration. Most studies report that in interactive approaches, teachers’ decisions to use technologies innovate in integrating online sources and media dawn chiefly to enhancing classroom practices that improve learning in creating networks with global learning resources (Harasim, 2012). In support of these claims, Murphy (2007) reports that on phenomenological plan in process of (social) construction, teachers practice of teaching frames within communicative approach models. Within these designs, teacher in priority decides to integrate online media on building learning in activities

that extend beyond structural curriculum as confined within classroom. Murphy (2007) marks to stress the main intent of using different online sources and media is to generate participatory contexts within and beyond the classroom situations (Tour, 2015). In their survey research, Lund and Lund (2006) find English teachers within communicative approach framework exclusively deciding to use online technologies for many-to-many communications (Erickson, 1997). In these models, teachers perceive that students living world is new technology based, as Lund and Lund (2006, p.195) maintain:

Teachers who know that students' life-worlds are mediated by new technologies-the result is a third space-where different scripts meet and have potential of expanding the benefit of learning EFL beyond structures provided there is knowledgeable support for contextual moves.

The exemplary teachers in my study exemplified their interactive pedagogical perceptions noted for their decision to use offline and online innovative technologies in skills-focused English instructions in teaching English within communicative approaches which support the findings of the studies as cited above. However, my study teachers' perceptions in guiding their decisions regarding the use of technologies differ on an important matter. It is that the exemplary teachers in my study not only integrate online technologies exclusively to expose students to open sources in pretext of creating learning autonomy (Hauck et al., 2012). Instead, in Czech school contexts, my teachers decide to blend offline and online media. These decisions according to Fotos (2004) in principle are due to teachers' perceptions or approaches to teaching English in communication skills focused activities designed on blended-learning models (Blanka Frydrychova Klimova & Semradova, 2012). In these matters, the exemplary teachers e.g. Donna, George, Dave and Jane in my study advocate their own pedagogical perceptions as instrumental to influencing their decisions to use different technologies. For instance, Donna said, "It is me, I decide to use ICT as I love communication." Partly the study teachers also

acknowledge their students' digital interests supporting factors that influence them to increase technology use. In this regard, the exemplary teachers' common voice was as expressed by Dave, "Students doing group projects and presentations results into higher learning motivation than ICT used other ways."

Teachers decisions to use technologies are also influenced by school factors in various ways as captured in the existing literature with which findings on my study teachers in some respect triangulate yet on the principles of individual differences. On this account, existing researchers on technological line as (Albirini, 2006; Pavlou & Vryonides, 2009; Shapka & Ferrari, 2003; van Braak, 2001) etc. hold technologically equipped school related factors as significantly influencing teacher perceptions on decisions to use technologies in classroom. For instance, among others, Davis (1989) measure of teachers' perceptions on large scale claims teachers' perceived usefulness and ease to use technologies as primarily contributing to teachers' decisions to use technologies in class. In this regard, the study specifies variables along with teachers' attitudes and experiences with technologies, teachers' perceived usefulness and ease to use technologies, and digital training such that supported by their schools leading teachers' decisions to use technologies.

In agreement with the cited literature, the exemplary teachers in my study offer evidences, yet partly supporting the findings presented by Davis (1989) and other researchers, that account teachers' technologically enriching school factors and perceptions as key to influencing teachers' decisions to use individual technologies in class. In this regard, the exemplary teachers in my study perceive some technologies like laptop, audio-visuals and partly online sources as availed by schools easy to use, yet only for preparing lessons. Whereas in classroom teaching, in substitute of the perceived ease to use digital devices and training by school as a factor, the exemplary teachers express perceived usefulness of technologies in developing teaching English within communicative approach as main to their decisions to use

on learning focus. On this focus, Şahin Kızıl and Savran (2016) find teachers decisions to use technologies are for promoting self-regulated learning, which the exemplary teachers in my study consent of their decisions to use not only offline but also online media of various kinds. The exemplary teachers' communications evidenced not only offline digital devices, but also various online sources, platforms and media as decided to use in teaching English in activities. The activities integrated language exercises with conversations, digital audio-visuals, music, movies in assessing oral skills, e-media-supported games and quizzes, online sources or media integrated creative reading-writing and projects. The practices as these following Hauck et al. (2012) in teaching English frame within problem or inquiry-based or multidisciplinary project-based blended-learning models.

The idea of teachers' perceived ease of technologies is only sporadically supported in the exemplary teachers' encounters in my study that express their perceptions relating their decisions to integrate online media without teacher-guided selection as barriers to learning, though their use is not yet denied in English class. The exemplary teacher Donna said, "Yes, ICT is time consuming, and sometimes there are problems of materials, technologies distract students, but you can choose other ICT or materials [...]." As this information suggests, teachers' perceived usefulness (Ertmer, Ottenbreit-leftwich, Sadik, Sendurur and Sendurur, 2012) instead of perceiving an easiness to use technology (Davis,1989) comes highlighted for a greater role regarding exemplary teachers' decisions to use technologies of various kinds in teaching English within communicative approach framework. The idea of digital training which is school-related external factor as related to teacher decisions and skills of technology use, in my study is minimally supported in exemplary teachers' reports that inform of their school coordinated technology-training only incidental.

The findings on exemplary teachers' perceptions in my study that bring a theme that teachers' interactive pedagogical approaches are related to their perceptions upon technologies

as supportive to their existing approaches and also enablers of new approaches as main to their decisions, come supported in research line on social construction, as (Ertmer, Ottenbreit-leftwich, Sadik, Sendurur and Sendurur, 2012; Velázquez, 2006). These studies account teachers' decisions to use innovative technologies due to teachers' perceived usefulness as supportive of their approach to practice student-centered instructions. Godwin-Jones (2015) claims that English teachers' in social constructivist approach in exploring their internal capacities (Stoll, 1999) decide to use technologies that support their instructional strategies and skills on constructing language learning as innovative process. This is in contrast to technologically driven education (Dcokstader, 1999) and likewise teachers' perceptions. In this regard, the study by Tondeur et al.(2017) finds teachers decisions to use technologies in class as determined by teachers perception on technologies as useful to supporting their existing approaches to teaching in “student-centered instructions on design of social construction (Civiko et al., 2012 in Tondeur et al., 2017, p. 13).” The other accountable teachers' decisions regarding the use of technologies in class is teachers' perceptions about technologies as main enablers to inventing new approaches (Matzen and Edmunds, 2007; Ertmer, Ottenbreit-leftwich, Sadik, Sendurur and Sendurur, 2012). E.g. Tondeur et al. (2017) further add teachers perceiving technologies as potential to invent new approaches to becoming innovative teacher as well as constructivist teacher integrate various technologies in various ways in class (Chen et al., 2011 in Tondeur et al., 2017, p.13).”

Supporting the existing research findings on the theme that teachers' interactive pedagogical perceptions are to teacher's decisions whether to use technologies as supportive and enablers of interactive pedagogical approaches to innovative teaching, the exemplary teachers in my study inform their varying decisions to use different technologies in different schemes. In general, my study teachers decided to use common technologies e.g. projector, iTOOL, photocopied items, downloaded audio-visuals, movies etc. as these items supported

their wills, skills (Morales Velázquez, 2006) or approaches to practicing student-participated instructions upon skills of communication. Together, the exemplary teachers approved their decisions to use different online sources, language programs/games, learning platforms/websites, media etc. as these enabled to add-on new materials and activities upon inventing new strategies and skills that enhance classroom practices (Chen, 2011). The exemplary teachers in my study perceived the above listed technologies in the outlined instructional activities that function as enablers to enhancing classroom practices on extending learning even beyond curriculum, albeit their decisions expressed on individual bases differed significantly. For instance, Donna decided to present her students only with selected online links in project activities instead of letting a free access because she perceived them de-educating with unnecessary materials (Blacker & Mackie, 2008). George decided to use language programs and websites since he perceived these as the enablers for him to invent new ways of blending creative activities on developing inquiry-based teaching. Dave decided to use various online learning platforms and media as these enabled her to create collaborative contexts and invent new approaches to practice skills-integrated instructions. In Dave's case, these technologies are perceived as supportive to practicing student-to-students teaching and student-collaborated projects. Jane decided to use Google, YouTube and online or downloaded language games as these sources enabled her to explore new approaches to language teaching on trial and error methods. She perceived the outlined technologies in outlined practices as enablers to perform an innovative teacher (Velázquez, 2006).

In short, as the case study teachers' expressions and also findings in the existing relevant research studies lend sight, teachers' decisions to use (or not) individual technologies play vital role to developing technology integration in class teaching. In this regard as the discussions allow, teachers' decisions are fundamentally determined by teachers' pedagogical perceptions in substitute of technology factors. It is hence, noted that teachers' perceptions as internal

pedagogical capacities are primarily accountable to achieving technology integration in class teaching as a learning process (Stoll, 1999) within communicative approach framework. Within communicative pedagogical perceptions or approaches, teachers either decide to use technologies as supportive or enablers for inventing new approaches to teaching on constructing learning.

Along with the teacher perceptions as primarily associated to decisions to use (or not) individual technologies, technology integration in class teaching develops in teachers' classroom practices of technology implementation. In this regard, the findings on study teachers' exemplary classroom practices are discussed below. These relate to the main components of their pedagogical principles, ways, skills or techniques, purposes, functions and learning outcomes of using technologies in English class.

5.2.2 Teachers Technology Use in English Class

On the foundations of teachers' pedagogical perceptions/approaches as associated to influencing teachers' decisions regarding the use of technologies, the phenomenon as technology integration in classroom context, is achieved in teachers' real actions. The literature as in Pilten, Pilten and Sahinkaya (2017) lends idea that teachers' actions build on teachers' pedagogical methodological or teaching approaches, ways, skills, purposes, functions of using individual technologies in real context. In this regard, as the studies inform, though teachers' teaching might characterize within common components of a pedagogical approach-framework, the classroom practices of technology differ on individual bases. One of the key reasons, as Stoll (1999) claims, is due to teachers' individual pedagogical understandings as related to "internal capacities" that lead to their practices of technology use appropriated on different learning principles. Teachers either replicate or explore learning principles through individual encounters (Lund & Lund, 2006).

The outlined concept regarding teachers' classroom practices of technology use as based on different learning principles explored within a common pedagogical approach framework is well supported in case of the exemplary teachers Donna, George, Dave and Jane in my study. In my study exemplary teachers were noted using various offline and online technologies along with iTOOL of English textbook for teaching English within communicative approaches on blended-learning framework (Hinkelman, 2012). Yet, on individual bases, their classroom practices are projected as based on different learning principles adopted and explored through individual encounters. The principles as projected by each exemplary teacher in individual encounters as outlined in the finding chapter are these: learning by doing, learning by inquiry, learning by collaborated actions, and learning by games or trial and error. Although the outlined principles extent on social constructivist theoretical research foundations lending communicative approach to teaching and technology as further contributed by scholars e.g. (Tai, 2015; MacKenzie & Bathurst-Hunt, 2011; Kessler & Bikowski, 2010; Young, 2009) etc., their implementation in case of exemplary teachers' classroom differ from the literature in individual ways. The exemplary teacher practices in my study differ in ways, techniques, skills, purposes, functions of using technologies within the blended-learning framework that I discuss in triangulation with the existing literature in this section.

To the concept of common and individual differences regarding teachers' technology use in English class, the existing research captures the phenomenon in inconsistent ways. In this regard, in contrast to the existing research that captures the phenomenon on semantic focus in which technologies are used to the purpose of transmitting information for cognition (Burston, 2014), my study teachers' classroom practices support the existing studies on phenomenological scheme further contributed by e.g. Lund (2003), Angers (2005), Godwin-Jones (2015) etc. On these, teachers appropriate and explore apart from constructivist ways, various innovative techniques of technology use, though varied in individual ways on a scheme

of constructing English in skills of communication as a social process. For instance, the exemplary teacher in my study Donna used with priority offline technologies that entailed photocopies, downloaded content or audio-visuals, iTOOL of textbook and projector in English instructions formed in grammatical activities designed on integrated framework. In these, the technologies integrate language items with writing or reading topics practiced in groups. E.g. use of projector is to present grammatical component and appropriated to integrate tasks such as watching English documentaries and movies and/or to engage students in practice of communications e.g. in conversations, question-answers, and problem-solving exercises. Other exemplary teachers in my study had the common practices as outlined, though that too differed in individual ways.

Linking interpretations upon the use of downloaded and offline digital materials or technologies in English class, the exemplary teachers classroom practices, as outlined in my study, support the idea as presented by Lee (2016). The researcher though interprets the teachers in conventional practices, their use of sensory i-cards in class instead of online sources is interpreted as effective to improving early stage readers' reading skills in substitute of drilling rules. The exemplary teachers in my study, too integrate textbook e-version workbook and photocopy materials interpreting these as effective tools to teaching vocabularies and grammar in an integrated design. Supporting this idea for example, the exemplary teacher Donna interpreted "textbook with its iTOOL has lot of useful materials on vocabularies, grammar which help students to concentrate, reflect and solve problems."

Besides, the priority in the exemplary teachers in my study to use offline digital technologies embody due to their negative encounters with online sources encouragingly advocated in literature of computer assisted language learning⁵⁷ on construction. The findings of negative encounters in my study support several researchers who in line with Levy, Hubbard,

⁵⁷ CALL

Stockwell and Colpaert (2015) report, CALL on construction is yet not effective in the issue of teaching vocabulary, grammar and basic items of language. Besides, on occasions, along with downloaded English movies, music etc. used to integrate language with activities, all the selected exemplary teachers in my study used these items for entertaining the class on increasing student motivation. The main function of technology use as this following Levy, Hubbard, Stockwell and Colpaert's (2015,p.4) point of view is “psychological.”

Though the exemplary teachers’ use of offline technologies on occasions with psychological function is supported, their contextual practices, even though in activities of entertainment differ relating the intent to increasing student motivation not only in principles but also in features. For an example, though all exemplary teachers used downloaded English movies, Donna displayed documentaries, George used science fictions, Dave showed entertaining movies and Jane displayed cultural movies. Their interpretations also differed in relation to motivational functions, as outlined in the findings, Donna’s purpose was to expose learners to speaking, George’s to excite learner thinking, Dave’s to entertain for further collaboration whereas Jane’s purpose was to entertain in cultural exposure.

In addition to the use of general technologies in English lessons on basic psychological functions as discussed, the exemplary teachers in my study use different online sources, websites, learning platforms, media etc. Their key intent is to enable students to use these technologies in creativity learning, inquiry and multi-thematic projects, though practiced and interpreted in different ways in principles of learning differences. In this regard, the exemplary teacher Donna provides her students herself-selected online links. Using these, “her students explore materials, do projects and present.” The reason after selected use, is to protect students from learning barriers online technologies cause as supported in the studies reviewed by Jones (2004). Despite learning barriers as common to findings of the research reporting teachers’ encounters upon online technologies, there is a unique feature in Donna’s practice and it is in

projects. For instance, she provided her students the online links to explore materials on topics of their choice to work in groups autonomously and present on PPT⁵⁸. As the previous research findings in line with Danan (2006) relay, teacher in projects varies roles from an instructor to facilitator scaffolding and assessing tasks. Supporting this, the exemplary teacher Donna assesses, “understandability of the content not grammar”. The project practices formed by use of the selected online sources, websites, downloaded materials etc. with creative writing-reading activities on multiple topics relating science, health, and English cultures etc. are supported in literature on, “learning by doing principles (Tai,2015),” which the exemplary teacher Donna appropriates in teacher-guided learning by doing framework.

Within the communicative approach designs, the existing research studies in line with (Arnesen, 2010, Lund, 2003; Rahimi & Author, 2011; Cinakara, 2018) etc. inform individual variations regarding teachers’ use of online technologies in as identical or increasing degree as compared with the use of offline technologies. The existing research findings of individual differences are well supported in case of exemplary teachers in my study. In this regard, George, Dave and Jane, in my study, practice online technologies of various kinds in common with Donna as discussed above however, each teacher’s practices differ in ways, skills, purposes, functions that thereby relate to and develop in learning principles of individual differences. For instance, George in self-exploring new technological approaches on different purposes yet appropriated for educational functions, uses online technologies of various kinds. These entail online sources (Google, Wikipedia), websites (YouTube), online language programs, online communication media in instructions as based upon creative skills and inquiry-based multimodal projects extended on “learning by inquiry principle (MacKenzie & Bathurst-Hunt, 2011).” The main motivation of using the mentioned technologies that in contrast to Davis (1989) who found perceived ease, is to enhance classroom practices of English upon a focus to

⁵⁸ PowerPoint presentation technology

creating learning as critical and creative skill (Zou, Wang, & Xing, 2016). The findings on George's use of the online technologies in instructions as based upon quizzes, problem-based topics integrated activities on inquiry principle are supported in different studies, as in Thacker and Friedman's (2017) in which research relates different online media use serving as prompts, leads and cues for students to practice inquiry. Hauck, Fuchs and Müller-Hartmann (2012) also agree upon their use as helpful to autonomously engage students with varying learning interests to practice English upon skills of communication. Şahin Kızıl and Savran (2016) find teachers use of online technologies extended on an intent to promote students of varying competence learn English in teacher guided inquiry models, which otherwise causes learning deviation. As an alternative to online technologies as causative of learning deviation hence, the exemplary teacher George in my study invents idea of blending them with learning activities as in iTOOL of the English textbook within the communicative approach designs. These practices enable teacher to scaffold learners of varying interests to self-construct language (Hauck et al., 2012).

The idea of classroom uses of various kinds of technologies in principle of learning English by inquiry characterized within communicative approach on blended-models as expressed by George in my study, is supported in different studies on social construction, though variously regarding types of online technologies, activities, ways of use, purposes, functions etc. In this regard, Yoon (2016), among others explores teachers' use of online dictionary in English instruction on inquiry model. The intent of online dictionary as corpus media on language use in this practice is to find information, materials for activities as based on critical and creative skills focus. The other main intent is for teacher to facilitate students to ease their inquiry learning stress (MacKenzie & Bathurst-Hunt, 2011). These purposes and functions of technology use are evidenced in case of George in my study who varies roles to facilitate students as engaged on games, quizzes, creative writing, projects etc. in inquiry-based instructions. As to the principles of difference, in addition to difference from Donna's scheme

of teacher-selected use, George's practice differs from literature that in line with Robinson (2011) claims, use of technologies as exclusively supportive to creating intrinsic motivation. The contrast to this is evidenced in use of technologies of various kinds in George practice that in some cases center to entertain class, though on the intent of increasing students motivation which as Levy, Hubbard, Stockwell and Colpaert (2015, p.4) inform, yet fulfils psychological function.

In exemplifying the idea of common components and principles of learning differences regarding teachers' classroom practices of technology use within the blended-learning models as discussed in some studies (Arnesen, 2010; Lund, 2003; Lund & Lund, 2006; Cinakara, 2018), the other exemplary teacher Dave in my study adds another evidence of distinction. The practices of this exemplary teacher differ both from other teachers in my study and as well literature capturing the phenomenon in different perspectives. For example, in case of Dave, various online sources, websites, learning platforms, communication media along with offline technologies are used in common to and even in higher frequencies from other exemplary teachers in teaching English within blended-learning model. Besides, her practices differ in principles, in ways and skills, purposes, functions. In characteristics, this exemplary teacher's practices among others, come discussed as related to and developed in literature on principles of learning by collaborated action (John-Steiner & Mahn, 1996).

While discussing distinctions regarding the use of online technologies in English class, despite common grammatical uses that frame on scheme of structural competence as supported in research lined with e.g. (Cerezo et al., 2013), Dave in my study exhibits unique features. Her practices of online media of various kinds also integrated with offline technologies as integrated in language skills-based instructions vary in characteristic as formed in student-to-students teaching model. The practices of these technologies as well differ in ways from others as integrated in individual and group collaborated projects (Kessler & Bikowski, 2010). For

instance, unlike other exemplary teachers, Dave blends downloaded materials such as movies, histories or cultural events, music, audio-visuals materials with online sources and media. Uniqueness in case of her practice is involving students to use these media and teach class instead of teacher presenting language on projector along with collaborated projects. This practice is supported in research that in line with Teo and Jen (2012) technology for student-to-students teaching model as exemplified in Dave's case. This practice is interpreted in support of Teo and Jen (2012) who assert students involved on peer teaching use technologies for learning English embedded in multidisciplinary content as in history, culture, problem topics etc. These practices are to make up classroom learning interactive to developing students meta-cognitive and creativity skills. Involving students in such technologically interacted practices promotes collaborative skills on increasing students ownership in learning which as Marks (2009) advocates, is to help "meeting millennials on their own turf."

The existing research experiences in line with Jones (2004) study support the theme of technology integration to developing student acted classroom practices that better help constructing learning than to engaging students work individually in writing by using online sources merely for information which instead bring learning barriers. In common to the stated research finding, yet my study teacher Dave's main interpretation upon appropriation of offline and online technologies of various kinds is in contrast to exclusive use of online sources in tasks-based instructions. It is due to teacher's interpretation and purpose on technologies as integrated to enable students to use and practice English in metacognitive and innovative skills (Şahin Kızıll & Savran, 2016) enhanced in practices of student-to-students teaching model.

The interpretation supporting technologies for student-to-students teaching, is based on exemplary teachers' encounters of barriers in my study as resulted due to online technologies too. For an example, Dave said, "Students using online enjoy more with their teenage materials than doing grammar we expect." From the expressions of encounters, it is implied that

technology use in practice of teaching as centered to transmitting componential aspects of English is ineffective (Panggabean, 2015). Alternatively, the exemplary teachers as overemphasized by Dave seek to bridge the gap between teachers' perceptions and educational potentials technology can offer by presenting a model of student-to-students teaching. This enables students to learn and use various kinds of technologies in self-constructing English in skills. This finding is supported by Shifflet and Weilbacher (2015) who reporting the case of technology expert teacher claim. That despite positive perceptions on technologies, due to encounters of contextual barriers as in my study facing the online sources and replication of conventional skills, the case teacher's classroom uses significantly differ. In addition to student-to-students teaching based practices, Dave uses various online sources, websites, learning portals as "visit your teacher," and online media as well. Facebook and school's online system specially in mini and big group collaborated projects are designed on multidisciplinary topics (Fragoulis, 2009).

In projects, technology practices as relating teacher roles, skills, purposes and functions of technology in some existing studies that can be lined up with Prasojo et al.(2018) come projected as significantly related to mediating learning on social construction. However, the studies inform of differences in teachers' individual skills as based on inconsistent perspectives. This finding relating projects-based practices of technology use related to mediating learning as a meta-cognitive skill is supported in my study. In this regard, in project-based instructions, the exemplary teacher Dave in my study allows her students to use various digital and online sources and media of their choice to explore materials in computer lab or beyond class contexts. During the project work, the teacher and students communicate via school online system and Facebook. In the last phase, students present, when the teacher assesses and communicates feedback in class or beyond using the media. There are similar school organized projects in this

exemplary teacher in which online communication media come into teacher and students use in immersive ways supporting practice of English in real communication.

Concerning teachers' sources of motivation upon practicing projects Danan's (2006) finding states that these practices allow to enhance students' autonomous skills of learning in activities organized with content and technologies integration that enhances critical, collaborative and creativity skills. The teacher Dave in my study supports this interpretation as expressed in her experiences relating purposes and functions of technology use in projects. She said, "Well, I'd say, students exploring things online and making presentations results into higher learning motivation than other ways using ICT." Besides, project learning activities in case of Dave involve students in publishing projects in the online journal when teacher and students' collaborations extend virtually (Liddell & Garrett, 2004). The publishing activities, following Hung's (2012) finding that relates e-portfolios and online publishing as significant medium, are to increase learning collaborations that promote both students and teachers' learning on increasing reflectivity, innovative thinking and creativity. This is additional feature of distinction in case of Dave's practice of technologies in projects.

In adding evidence to the idea of common components and principles of learning differences regarding teachers' classroom practices of technology use in teaching English within the blended-learning models as discussed in the studies as in (Arnesen, 2010; Lund, 2003; Lund & Lund, 2006; Cinakara, 2018) etc. the exemplary teacher Jane in my study adds still another example of distinction. In this regard, her classroom practices of technology use in addition to being as identical to common teacher practices as discussed above yet differ in criteria or principles of learning differences. The general digital, offline and online sources and technologies in case of Jane are practiced in instructions of English as based on common grammatical or simple language skills focus within communicative approach as common to other teachers and research experiences relating technologies for communication of

information. However, her classroom practices of various online sources, websites (youtube), online media etc. technologies as integrated in language games-based instructions and projects are significantly built on learning defined as meta cognitive skill. These practices differ in principles, ways, skills, purposes and functions which as outlined in the finding chapter, are discussed here as based on principles of language learning by games featured within trial and error method (Peterson, 2010).

Relating teachers' technology use in games based instructions, few existing studies in line with Schmid and Whyte (2012) support these practices as featured with creative reflectivity and intellectual interactions that promote learning English in practical skills of communication. The researchers elaborate that in practice of games teachers use technologies that integrate English texts with skills-based activities engaging students to practice communication skills in practice of language games. The studies as well relate the given experience or interpretation in practices of English instruction as based on creative-writing and multi-thematic projects. Supporting these schemes, the exemplary teacher Jane in my study uses various downloaded digital or offline materials and online tools, sources, learning platforms and media in games and project practices. The key intent as she relates is to organize classroom practices with language games on communication skills, critical thinking and problem-solving skills focus (Hwang et al., 2015). In games-based practices as noted by, Kaur et al. (2012) teacher and students as practitioners engage to play games in different roles using digital materials and media to practice language intuitively in practice of team-work, strategic and creativity skills on intercultural competence goal (J. Wang et al., 2013). The study teacher Jane also stresses this point as she asserts that along with increasing learning motivation, game-based practices bring English to students in increasing awareness upon new content, contexts, strategies, cultures, skills etc. (Hauck et al., 2012). Games-based classroom practices also make out on a principle as articulated by Braak (2016) of enhancing language in fun of games.

Relating the source of motivation upon integration of technologies in games-based classroom practices, some studies agreeing with Cherner and Curry (2017) account technologies used as innovative resources and promotional tools. These enable teachers to create environment that supports students to autonomously engage in learning English upon skills of collaboration and reflective communication. Such practices as argued by Şahin Kızıl and Savran (2016) are significant in enabling students an exposure to new media in learning English in games as instrumental to enhancing meta-cognitive skills and also innovating new skills of collaboration (Tour, 2015). In this matter, support of the games-based practices of technologies within the scheme on language in communication skills, the exemplary teacher Jane in my study expressed, “I myself love playing games and my students learn English faster with games.” The quote reveals that in instruction on games, English teacher uses digital or online media/technologies as key tools that support students to acquire language faster. This finding corresponds to research supporting the use of online sources of various kinds as noted by Kennedy and Miceli (2010). The researchers inform the use of online technologies such as e-dictionaries in designing classroom practices as based on creative writing skills. In addition to features of technology use in projects in teaching English on a common design, these in case of the exemplary teacher Jane in my study inform unique features regarding classroom practices of technology use upon learning significance. In this regard, uniqueness is notable in the way Jane formulates groups and assigns them to work on a project. Therefore, not all students in a group, but groups of students are assigned different technologies and work to completing the assigned project as based on one theme at a time attempted by groups in its sub-divisions. Such collaborative practices following Erickson (1997) is a participatory method. The pattern as this is supported in research by Teo and Jen (2012). The researchers assert that this pattern promotes students ability of team coordination which is still more advance meta-cognitive skill level as

found in (Shonkoff & Phillips, 2000) who studied child developing on the theme, “from neurons to neighborhood.”

In triangulating the findings on exemplary teachers’ classroom practices of technology use in teaching English with the existing research experience, despite differences of varying perspectives, the studies on phenomenological construction account teachers’ interactive pedagogical approaches. The studies on this pattern build individual or internal capacities and skills for a greater role for developing the phenomenon i.e. technology integration (Stoll, 1999) in real context. In this regard, research on psychological and cognitive focus claims correlations between teachers’ technological factors including access to technologies, school or environment factors and development of technology integration (He, Puakpong, & Lian, 2013; Chigona & Chigona, 2010). In contrast, the studies reporting teachers’ qualitative behaviors or experiences as in (Ertmer, 1999; Drossel, Eickelmann, & Schulz-Zander, 2017; Chen, 2011) extend the role of teachers’ pedagogical approaches or rationales along with individually explored learning principles for major part. These studies claim teachers’ classroom practices of technologies as differing from individual to individual even within the same pedagogical approach-framework. On this line, subject teachers are noted practicing instructions within individual approaches which accordingly lead to use (or not) individual technologies in class teaching. As such, the studies claim teachers’ teaching and technology practices developing in different ways, with different skills, on different purposes and functions, and learning outcomes, though some common components of practices are possible (Angers, 2005).

Drawing on individual differences, as Tour (2015) reports, within the structural approaches, English teachers’ integration of technologies develops more due to extrinsic factors e.g. using technologies to fulfill curriculum or to control student behavior in class. In contrast, researchers e.g. Warschauer (2000), Fotos (2004) as on Tondeur et al.'s (2017) line on (social) construction within interactive phenomenology, find English teachers practice of technologies

in class developing significantly in interactive behaviors and cultural themes of technology use. On construction models, teachers' ways and skills of technology integration are accounted substantially related to developing classroom curricula on skills of transforming learning. For instance, on social construction, Warshauer (2000) notes teachers integrating online media integrated with English textbook in class practices designed on a model of many to many communications. The online media used in contexts enable students to construct English with real social and cultural content, contexts and skills of communication as embedded within the mode of virtual or online communications. Likewise, Wetzel, Zambo, & Buss (1996) based on their findings of multiple case-studies, describe a classroom model of teachers' practices of technology integration indicating their ways, skills, purposes and functions of technology use. In their model, teachers in "(social) constructivist pedagogical beliefs (p.5)," are informed of willing to develop new curriculum standards. In these, teachers not only integrate general technologies to form central instructions but explore new ways of teaching and integrate asynchronous and synchronous communication media. Their integration according to Pilkington and Kuminek (2004) enables students to debate, dialogue, communicate thoughts, ideas and skills on enhancing skills of critical thinking, problem solving, reflectivity, reasoning, creativity and communication skills.

Angers (2005) adds to the given claims that teachers in dynamic classroom practices on (social) construction practicing student-centered classroom instructions learn to be flexible. These teachers on collaborative roles appropriate different technologies to facilitate students on problem solving, reasoning etc. meta-cognitive skills learning. In meta-cognitive skills-based activities (Şahin Kızıl & Savran, 2016), technologies are used as innovative social and cultural thought tools (Harasim, 2012) that fulfil a function of constructing learning as a transformative process over transferring information from texts.

At this point in short assessing the findings on exemplary study teachers i.e. Donna, George, Dave and Jane's classroom practices in my study in triangulation with research experience as outlined considering the role of teachers' methodological perceptions, motivations and skills of technology use in class for developing learning, some primary insights have surfaced. In this regard, in common with reports as in several studies, it is noted that the exemplary study teachers in my study within the communicative approach framework practice a wide range of offline and online technologies in class. The teachers integrate various kinds of technologies apart from others, on a key purpose to enhancing teaching sought to design within integrated model to enhancing students' communication skills which are largely conditioned and embedded into digital or virtual skills. However, as the exemplary teachers' technology implementation along with teaching styles are individually distinct as based on different learning principles adopted and explored within job-contexts of each that differ, their skills of technology integration are represented as developed on different principles and models use classroom use developing significantly through individual encounters.

Following the given findings on exemplary teachers classroom practices of technology use in my study as triangulated and also differed with existing research experiences as in(Tondeur et al., 2017; Angers, 2005; Hermans et al., 2008; Eickelmann & Vennemann, 2017) it is hereby argued. That technology integration in English classroom develops on teachers' phenomenological experiences that entail their individual pedagogical approaches, motivations, ways, techniques and skills of using technologies on constructing learning. From these perspectives, teachers' internal capacities (Stoll, 1999). With this argument, it is hence signaled that contextual factors (discussed in 5.2.4) though significant, still have a secondary role to achieving technology integration in real classroom situation on developing learning. Besides, as the exemplary study teachers' classroom practices of technologies also signal a role of teachers' individual reflections as related to their personal experiences of motivations and

barriers regarding the use of individual technologies in class on constructing learning process, these variables are discussed hereafter.

5.2.3 Teacher Reflections Regarding the Use of Technologies in English Class

Along with the significance of teachers' practices of technology use on constructing the learning in real classroom practices that develop on teachers' individual principles, ways or skills, teachers' learning reflections are equally important or even essential to achieving technology integration in the English class. Its significance in some existing studies as based on phenomenological scheme following Kamylyis et al. (2015) is signaled relating its role to developing learning process. As the literature lends sight, significance of teachers' reflection is twofold. Pilkington and Kuminek (2004) explain that reflections as re-evaluating thought acting out communications on personal experiences express teachers' real encounters that in my study are related to pedagogical methodological uses of technology on constructing learning as innovative process (Wach, 2015). Second aspect is as elucidated by Liu, Navarrete, Maradiegue and Wivagg (2014). The researchers lend idea that teachers' reflections as self-explorative intellectual learning actions contribute to interacting teachers' existing perceptions and thereby lead to transformation of individual factors. This intellectual action thus, enables teachers to overcome the second order barriers to technology use (Ertmer, 1999) in class on developing learning as a digital, virtual and innovative skills enhancing process (Kamylyis et al., 2015).

Connecting the concept of reflections as transformative intellectual elements, van Lier (1996, p.14) drawing upon Dewey's (1933) concept, illuminates, "Teachers' reflections as related to their interactive pedagogical approaches, are related to improving critical thinking and creativity on reforming individual skills. These components play complementary role to reforming teacher's individual classroom practices on increasing learning interactions." From this perspective, teachers' reflections are explorative intellectual actions that express teachers' pedagogical approaches and experiences of technology use in teaching on increasing learning

interactions upon developing learning process. In this regard, existing studies inform teacher reflections as important aspects however, interpreting their meaning, significance, and association inconsistently as based on different focus or drawn upon different perspectives. For instance, literature on technological focus in line with Li, Snow, Jiang and Edwards (2014) associates technologically enriched environment to increasing technology use in class as accountable to improving teacher reflection regarding its role to achieving technology integration. On this perspective, teachers' pedagogical rationales of technology use on learning construction (Dcokstader,1999) as associated to increasing learning and teacher reflectivity is undermined.

In contrast to the technological reflections, the research relating technology in teaching English from the teacher's perspective in a comprehensive focus as in (Warschauer, 2010 ; Wach 2015) associates teachers' communicative pedagogical approaches and skills of using technology in class as accountable to improving teachers' reflections. In this regard, Pilkington and Kuminek (2004) note improving learning reflections in teachers in practice of teaching English on phenomenological as experiential learning model. In this model, a teacher reflects upon the use of various technology sources, platforms, communication tools as appropriated to enhancing classroom practices that contribute to improving communication skills on reforming learning reflections. Identically, Chao (2015) relays, communication skills enhancing classroom practices as supported by innovative media/technology use, frame with teachers' social constructivist approaches and skills of teaching in collaborations, critical thinking, problem-solving or in project models improve along with learners and teachers learning reflections (Tour, 2015; Pilten et al., 2017; Elsner, 2011; Aydin, 2016).

The theoretical literature reviewed above for a reference to understand meaning, concept and association lends idea that teacher reflection is a self-evaluative thought. It is an intellectual action that expresses teachers' personal post-experiences against the phenomenon

that in my study is related to teachers' classroom use of individual technologies in teaching English on constructing learning. The key theoretical idea as elaborated by Pilkington and Kuminek (2004) and Liu, Navarrete, Maradiegue and Wivagg (2014) is that teacher reflection plays vital role on developing learning process in real context. To this concept, the existing research relating the role and significance of teacher reflection though inconsistently captured, expresses positive result in teachers in practice of technology use in teaching English within phenomenological as communicative models on social construction. I adopt the existing research as a comprehensive line of thought as reviewed above in assessing the exemplary teachers in my study, Donna, George, Dave and Jane's post-teaching reflections regarding the use of technology use in English class as discussed in this section.

On comprehensive research focus, as following Cinakara's (2018) study, English teachers in substitute of general digital components, appropriate various online and ubiquitous media used to enhancing classroom practices. This study asserts that in enhanced English classroom practices as based on communicative approaches with comprehensive focus, the use of media contributes to transforming students' simple communication skills of listening, speaking etc. into advanced skills of disputing, discussing, negotiating, explorative talking (Pilkington & Kuminek, 2004). Teachers in this comprehensive classroom model are engaged in employing and inventing new pedagogical approaches, skills and strategies upon increasing learners and teacher's learning reflections. Teacher's increasing learning reflections as the studies claim further contribute to transforming teachers' existing approaches, perceptions, experiences and skills of technology use in real class on constructing learning (Killeavy & Moloney, 2010).

The stated research findings on teacher reflection are variously supported in the exemplary teachers, Donna, George, Dave and Jane in my study yet each teacher's reflections also noted as related to and developed on the learning principles of individual difference. The

differences in my study relate to the source of reflection and its role or significance in developing technology use in teaching English class upon constructing learning as a meta-cognitive skill of communication. In this regard, the exemplary teachers in general perceptions and practices, express mixed encounters regarding appropriation or use of technologies in English class. However, in contrast, their post-teaching reflections are significantly interactive, though these are based on individually adopted and explored on pedagogical principles, skills and experiences of using technologies in class. In assessing these, I draw the exemplary teachers' reflections in my study as expressed in context of technology use in English classroom practices being focused to construction of learning upon skills of communication. The teachers' reflections on the focus given in my study are developed within communicative approaches on blended-learning model. This model in line with Niess (2011) is significantly interactive to improving learners and teacher's, learning reflectivity in the enhanced classroom practices as formed to developing learners' meta-cognitive skills. Further elaborating Niess's (2011) research points to the fact that the class practices in blended model involve comprehensive implementation of teachers' technological, pedagogical and content knowledge (TPACK) in substitute of psychologically limited use of pedagogy. A comprehensive activity system within the blended-learning model according to Coughlan and Duff (1994) is significantly related to improving teacher reflections on increasing learning interactions.

Despite the common components of teacher reflectivity within the blended-learning framework, the existing literature in line with van Lier (1996) informs teacher reflections reforming and improving upon the principles of individual differences linking their sources and roles regarding the use of individual technologies in English class. This finding is explicitly reflected in case of the exemplary teachers i.e. Donna, George, Dave and Jane. This is evidenced in my study as synthesized in the finding chapter, where it shows. Each exemplary teacher reflects individual differences relating her/his post-teaching experiences, interpretations, and

skills of technology use in English class being focused to learning upon skills of multi-modal communications (Kaur et al., 2012; Lin, 2015). For instance, the exemplary teacher Donna reflects her practices of online technologies as related to increasing students learning motivation upon increasing learning interactions in the instructions as based on communication skills-based activities and projects. Donna's distinction is that she reflects these practices as based on the principle of learning by doing model (Tai, 2015) which in case of other exemplary teachers are reflected in different ways, even though in their use of online technologies in practice of instruction as based on skills focus and projects.

Assessing the features of distinction in case of Donna in my study, her reflection is significantly related to enhancing students learning skills and it is drawn in skills-focused and project-based classroom practices of technology use. These practices are reflected as developed and based on the principle of learning by doing model. These practices as reflected on Donnas' model following the existing research experience in line with Pilten et al. (2017) are described as being interactive models. In these interactive models, the researchers as following Kruk and Zawodniak (2018) agree upon the use of different online media and technologies integrated as self-learning resources. The uses as these enable students and teacher to invent new learning skills or techniques on increasing learning interactions in which teachers express improving learning reflections (Guichon, 2010). Supporting these points, her post-teaching communications as focused on the use of technology in skills-focused and project-based instructions, Donna reflected, "I select and give links on different items to my students to do projects." In the projects she reflected increased emphasis to using the online sources critically that helped students to bring arguments e.g. in their projects and make effective presentations individually and in group collaborations. In the post-teaching interview, Donna selectively reflected as group-project based use of technology as a successful practice. She reflected, "The

project was a successful lesson, students argued a lot, presented their work, I must say, they learned English.”

The outlined emphases from the exemplary teacher in my study come supported in some research communications that capture the phenomenon in the way of Ware and Kessler (2014) who define English instructions as based on projects quite successful models of learning English upon skills of collaboration. In these models, English teachers not only reflect the use of computer for word-based texts or digital components limiting transmission of textual information. Instead, as Ware and Kessler (2014) reflect various online learning sources and media such as blogs are used as the key means to promoting students and teachers' task-collaborations on increasing learning interactions and reflections. Donna in my study brings her reflections accordingly but distinguishes it in one way. In collaborated project practices, she reflects that instead of enabling free access to open online sources, her students better engage in learning when provided with teacher selected online links. She reflected, “There are material problems with online sources, but you can choose other materials.” Asserting these, teacher selected online technologies are reflected as better means to engaging students to practice English in activities of projects for enhancing critical thinking, creative reflectivity and communication skills defined in terms of 21st century skills (Lund, 2003).

In the selective use of online technology integrated in projects, improved teacher learning reflections as following Killeavy and Moloney (2010) come upon teachers' self-initiated collaborative approaches employed in a key intent. It is to increase learning engagements in students. These enable teacher to invent new ideas, techniques, skills or instructional strategies which is identically supported in my study as exemplified from Donna's post-teaching reflections upon project practices of technology use. In these, this teacher transforms her existing pedagogical perceptions and skills. In this regard, the reflections lend sight of teacher's priority as extended from using general technologies to integrating innovative

online tools and media on developing learning beyond class. Teacher's extended priority from using technology as general devices to technology as innovative media in agreement with Arnesen 's (2010) study leads to framing classroom practice in teaching English upon communications skills focus which in case of my exemplary teacher is reflected in practice of projects. Arnesen (2010) theorizes this teacher working within phenomenological approach on (social) construction (Phillips, 1971) as improving professionally as a reflective practitioner.

The concept of individual differences in forming teacher reflections related to developing technology use in class on learning as based on different principles as endorsed in research on comprehensive focus as in Killeavy and Moloney (2010), is further exemplified by exemplary teachers George, Dave and Jane in my study. In this regard, these teachers exhibit common evidences supporting Donna's reflections as triangulated with the research findings which positively associate reflections to increasing learning interactions in practice of English as based on skills of communication and projects. Yet their reflections exemplify some features of individual differences worth discussing as well.

Supporting the theme of individual differences regarding the sources and roles of teacher reflections upon the use of technology in English class in line with the existing research e.g. Yoon (2016), George in my study reflects the use of technologies as significantly interacted in inquiry-based projects. In this case, among others, the online sources, online communication tools or media and online language programs such as "your port of knowledge" etc. were reflected as interactively used. The given technological uses as based on the principle of learning by guided inquiry (MacKenzie & Bathurst-Hunt, 2011) were reflected as enablers for students to practice English in physical and virtual modes of collaboration upon skills of intercultural communication.

Inquiry-projects in teaching English as following Killeavy and Moloney (2010) are significant practices to increasing learning on meta-cognitive skills. The teacher in this practice

is reflected to vary roles from coach to collaborator. Besides, inquiry-projects significantly interact learning to enhancing critical thinking, problem solving and creativity skills as embedded in the use of new technologies on increasing learning interactions that improve teachers' reflectivity. The findings on George's learning reflections in my study come in support to Yoon's (2016) findings that say. In inquiry-based practices, teachers integrate various technologies as their use supports her/his approach to teaching. English teacher in inquiry approach as van Lier (1996) illuminates, integrates new technologies in creating new affordances that extend learning from input in which teacher's learning reflections improve in practices as based on problems posing method. On these, as Schein (1996) draws, use of technology shifts from teacher to students in increasing their agency and ownership of learning. These findings in the case of George in my study are partly supported, since this teacher in inquiry-projects enables students to use technologies and practice collaborations, critical thinking, explore ideas and present, yet guided by teacher. As such, George's reflections inform his practice of teaching and technology as based on guided inquiry.

On the scheme of individual differences regarding teachers' learning reflections, some researchers as following Kozar (2010) stress these components as positively improving in group projects that develop learning on the skills and principles of collaboration. This concept in my study is significantly supported in the exemplary teacher Dave regarding the source and role of teacher reflections in developing technology use in English class. For instance, in her post-teaching expressions, the teacher in my study reflects the use of various online sources, learning portals, online media including Facebook etc. These are reflected as interactively appropriated in practice of student-to-students teaching and student-collaborated projects that were based on multiple themes of learning characterizing, " skills and principle of collaborated actions (Liw & Bunn-Le Master, 2010)."

In student-collaborated projects, the researchers in line with Kozar (2010) reflects teacher roles variously extending from close -scaffolder to open and virtual collaborator. Supporting this research information relating teacher role, the exemplary teacher Dave in my study reflects the use of social media as Facebook along with school online communication system as significantly increased in increasing learning interactions between teacher and students beyond class. At this point assessing the use of online communication media as Facebook and school online system in student and teacher collaborated projects, Aydin (2014) says. Teachers in practices of teaching English within collaborative project methods use Facebook as a medium for developing learning within cooperative activity systems (Scott & Palincsar, 2014) which improves learning reflections. In case of this exemplary teacher in my study in collaborative reflective skills learning practices, as opposed to the idea of providing students with teacher selected online links, students are encouraged by the teacher to use various online sources of their choice. For instance, Dave reflected, “Well, I just see what they are doing while working online sources which are of students’ own choice.” This point is supported in the studies by Lapadat (2002), Godwin-jones (2010), Kessler and Bikowski (2010) with interpretations that suggest. Online sources and media of communication are to engage students in learning tasks which enhance their skills of collaboration, communication, critical and creativity skills. It is in the identical emphases that Dave in my study along with common components, provides an evidence that proves the principles of learning differences on which teacher’s learning reflections reform. Therefore, the teacher’s reflections are significantly improved in collaborated projects as interactive learning models that help inventing new ideas, strategies, skills and technique on increasing learning interactions upon growing learning reflectivity.

In exemplifying the principles of learning differences as approves Livingstone (2012) regarding teachers’ reflections with a role in developing technology use in teaching English

class, some studies in line with Peterson (2010) explore these components in teachers practice of instructions as based on games model along with projects. These experiences in my study are significantly supported in case of the exemplary teacher Jane also with some features of distinction. In this regard, Jane in her post-teaching expressions reflected the use of various kinds of downloaded digital materials and online links well integrated in English classroom practices which she formed in the activities and games integrated as well as in projects based on mixed cultural themes. In the given practices, the teacher reflected the outlined technologies used as the interactive sources of information, learning resources, media on communication and tools to working. The games-integrated classroom practices and also projects on multicultural themes as following Lan, Sung and Chang (2013) are designed with integration of language with games, or student undertaken tasks as based on multidisciplinary subjects learning. These are reflected as being interactive projects on increasing learning interactions that include learning virtual media skills of communication in promoting intercultural skills as positively associated to improving learning reflections (Kessler, Bikowski, & Boggs, 2012). These findings are supported in assessing the sources and roles of Jane's learning reflections that significantly develop in her teaching in classroom practices of games and projects as reflected on Thorndike's, "learning by trial and error principle (Bandura, 1969)." In these practices, technology use is reflected significantly related to enhancing students' creativity in English communications along with promotion of virtual skills on increasing teacher-students' learning interactions upon growing learning reflectivity. In the trial and error methods, as support Young (2009), teacher and learner invent new approaches and skills of self-exploring learning. This is well agreed in case of Jane in my study who reflects her increasing learning interactions and reflectivity as the main enablers that support her to invent new skills or techniques and technologies in games and projects.

Concerning a final assessment of the findings on exemplary teachers' reflections for a role to enhancing teaching and technology use in English classroom in triangulation with and different from the existing research experiences as discussed, the concept of increasing learning reflections in teacher in practice of activity-integrated and project-based instructions is supported variously in literature. In this regard, current studies on comprehensive focus as following van Lier (1996) explore and emphasize teachers' reflections as a significant role in improving the use of technologies in English classroom practices on developing learning process that frame within communicative approaches on blended-learning model of (social) construction (Lund, 2003). In these frameworks, teachers on increasing learning interactions along with reflectivity, are reported to overcome external barriers to technology use in real context (Ertmer et al., 2012). For instance, on a model of collaboration, Stiler and Philleo (2003) found English teachers interactively engaged in online collaborations via blogs which contributes to promoting learners and teachers' learning reflectivity. In collaborative engagements, teachers' individually increase learning participations on improving learning reflections as associated to enhancing skills of teaching and technology use.

Similar findings relating teacher reflections regarding use of technology in class for developing learning process are contributed as supported in Killeavy and Moloney (2010). The research finally informs that teachers teaching English within communicative approaches, enhance creative learning reflectivity. This finding is relatively evidenced in case of the exemplary teachers in my study. As following the given research with that the exemplary teachers' reflections in my study triangulate in many respects, following is the key argument:

That teachers in activity integrated and project based English instructions as developed within the communicative approaches on blended-learning model not only achieve technology integration in the increased use of technologies but in invented new approaches and skills of

using them on constructing learning upon skills of multimodal communication (Godwin-jones, 2010).

Following these findings, teachers' reflections, that Dewey (1933) theorized with communicative intellectual actions, are positioned as significant components to transforming teachers' existing pedagogical perceptions and skills of teaching and use of technologies to achieving technology integration on constructing learning (Lyons & Lyons, 2017). At this point, following the findings from the exemplary study teachers Donna, George, Dave and Jane's reflections that triangulate with some existing research experiences regarding development of technology integration in English class on constructing learning, it is finally concluded:

That English teachers in interactive pedagogical approaches in increasing learning interactions improve learning reflections. Supporting these, teachers' communicative approaches in improving learning reflections are associated to changing teachers' existing perceptions and skills in achieving technology integration on developing learning process, though technological factors as well related, yet in secondary role (Ertmer & Ottenbreit-leftwich, 2010).

Along with the variable teacher reflection as discussed, the cases in my study signal, the other variable termed as teachers' individual factors either as internal characters or external factors as related to developing technology integration in class of teaching English. These I discuss in triangulation with the existing literature below.

5.2.4 Teachers' Individual Factors with Technology Use in English Class

Teachers' individual factors are made upon personal attitudes or capacities (Stoll, 1999) and professional factors such as school's technological context or culture. Individual factors according to research on comprehensive learning focus as following Ertmer and Ottenbreit-

leftwich (2010) contribute variously to teachers' skills of using technologies in class on developing technology integration as a learning process. It is therefore, teachers' practices of technology use in individual class and their learning outcomes differ on individual basis (Levy et al., 2015).

In this regard, in contrast to research on merely technological focus representing different perspectives, the studies discussed above on comprehensive research framework account for individual factors in terms of internal capacities (Stoll, 1999) relating first order barriers (Ertmer, 1999) as a major factor that enables (deter) teachers to overcome external context barriers to technology use on constructing learning. Tondeur et al.(2017) reports teachers in social constructivist attitude in increasing learning efforts invent new skills of technology use to practicing student centered classroom instructions that too enable them to overcome external barriers. Li, Snow, Jiang and Edwards (2014) also project, teachers' individual educational approaches and capacities as developed on phenomenological background enable them to bring into use their context factors which otherwise are related as barriers to technology integration in teachers individual class contexts (Ertmer, 1999).

Linking the individual factors as internal characters or competences (Kampylis et al., 2015) for a supporting role to technology use in class, the studies in line with (Angers, 2005) associate these to developing teacher practices of technology use in developing learning on phenomenological model of social construction(Wang, 2008). These researchers inform that teachers individual factors are primarily constituted on teachers' individual pedagogical attitudes. These in case of teachers working upon phenomenological schemes develop into self-explorative and inventing capacities (Sandholtz & Haymore, 1997) as enhanced through their daily encounters in enhancing classroom practices of technology use (Borthwick & Gallagher-Brett, 2014).

The outlined research findings are quite supported in case of the exemplary teachers i.e. Donna, George, Dave and Jane in my study. The exemplary teachers in my study in general express their technology skills as self-explored and invented through daily encounters of teaching on constructing learning to that their communicative approaches to teaching and technology use is ascribed for a major role. As compared to their internal characters, the exemplary teachers in my study ascribe the technological factors related to students and school support system as only a secondary role which is informed and in agreement with research finding presented in Ertmer et al.(2012). In this regard, the exemplary teachers in common with the cited literature and also on distinctions, claim their own communicative approaches as the key enablers to enhancing individual skills and capacities regarding teaching English and technology integration. The teachers in my study assert their increasing learning interactions with students along with other different professional levels of school as supportive to enhancing their skills of using technologies. These findings as related with individual factors in case of the exemplary teachers in my study, are approved in a study by Bingimlas (2009) as being supporting factors in developing individual capacities. Following this information, teachers' self-exploring internal capacities (Stoll, 1999) in triangulation with Ertmer's (1999) idea, it comes asserted that teachers' interactive pedagogical attitudes as internal or first order factors are associated to interactive use of technologies in individual classes on developing learning process. The other idea as the research communications with those findings on the exemplary teachers' individual factors in my study triangulate, is that teachers in developing individual capacities succeed to overcome school context or technology factors related as the second order barriers to technology integration in class on constructing learning (Tondeur, Valcke, & van Braak, 2008).

As some examples from the exemplary teachers self-voiced expressions that support the outlined research experiences are cited here. These examples are in relating teachers' individual

factors as based on their pedagogical attitudes which are claimed to develop teachers' internal capacities. These are argued to contribute positively to teachers' technology use in class on developing learning process and that too help them overcoming external barriers to teaching English and technology integration in developing its learning process in real class. Regarding this the exemplary teacher Donna in my study informed, "I learned to use computer myself on job." Linking her individual habits with technology associated to developing internal capacity (Hrtoňová et al., 2015), Donna said, "I search everyday interesting materials from internet for teaching communication I love, students need communication skills to use English abroad." Partly, the exemplary teachers in their student-centric approaches (Gilis et al., 2016) acknowledged their students' varying digital interests related to learning motivation as encouraging factors to their use of technologies in class. Jane informed, "Well I use lots of online ICT for language games, my students learn English fast in games."

Regarding school factor, except for Jane, Donna, George and Dave in my study acknowledge their school being supportive in training to enhance technology skills. Dave informed, "The school sends us to seminars, conferences if related to our subject." Unlike others, Dave's school publishes online journal that engages teachers and students in authoring their projects for publication. Besides, approving the role of technology factors, the exemplary teachers exposed changes in their common attitudes which as noted are developed more flexible such as including student choices upon selection of individual materials or technologies for use in class. George said, "Well, sometimes, you have to use movies or music to warm up, students generally love them."

In this way, regarding the quest how individual factors contribute to exemplary teachers' use of technologies in English classes, it is revealed that their individual characters as constituted on qualitative pedagogical attitudes, student-oriented attitude and self-explorative skills contribute to overcoming external barriers to the use of technologies in their class. Though

supporting role of school and students' digital interests related to learning motivation is also partly approved.

5.3 Conclusion

This thesis, as based on phenomenological case study design, focused on exploring technology integration in teaching English in Czech elementary schools from the teacher's perspective with an overarching objective: to explore and describe how technologies are part of exemplary study teachers' every day in teaching English classes for constructing learning. This goal lent to comprehensively analyze teachers' pedagogical perceptions, practices and reflections that express their qualitative behaviors, skills and themes of using technologies in class. This overarching goal incepted partly due to personal encounters regarding the use of technologies in teaching this subject which sometimes work and sometimes not. It incepted more intensive upon increasing conflicts due to the identified gaps between potentials of technologies, theory and policy discourse surrounding them, and efforts to implement them with expectations on developing teacher's competence and field research information about inconsistent teachers' practices. Furthermore, due to technologies getting increasingly embraced in the fast digitalizing school contexts such as in Europe, therefore including Czech schools, as innovating social and cultural knowledge tools of didactic use, a fundamental and recurring assumption led this study. This was, how teachers appropriate these innovating technologies to achieve their educational potentials in teaching English and addressing skills of communication defined by intercultural communicative competence goal in Europe and so in Czech schools.

Phenomenological concept with subjective epistemology on (social) construction guides this phenomenon in teachers' qualitative or exemplary pedagogical behaviors and skills for using technologies on constructing learning, yet such studies both internationally and in

Czech schools context in my research, are very few. Thus, to explore this phenomenon on its complexity from exemplary teachers' phenomenological experiences, their perceptions, practices, reflections and associated individual factors were analyzed on phenomenological case-study design that brought the findings on the cases stated in chapter four. These findings as discussed in this chapter triangulate with literature that develops technology integration in English teaching on teachers' pedagogical behaviors, skills and cultural themes of using technologies on constructing learning. However, exemplary teachers' practices are still based upon the principles of individual differences that the teachers invent on individual encounters in real context.

Following the findings on the exemplary teachers' classroom practices of technology integration discussed in triangulation, and different in principles from the existing research, it is conclusive that exemplary teachers practices of technology integration are identified based on a common framework of communicative approach on blended learning models. Yet within the given models each teacher is exemplified in understanding and practice of technology integration in English class in learning related to and developed on the principles of individual differences that teachers create and employ in individual contexts. The individual principles as articulated are learning by doing, learning by guided inquiry, learning by collaborated action, and learning by game on trial and error method as discussed above in this chapter. Even within these principles, further still individual differences were noted. These were due to exemplary teachers' personal encounters and experiences that expressed their pedagogical actions and interpretations as quite progressive, yet differing significantly from current literature as pointwise discussed above. For an instance, literature like Erickson (1997) on intercultural competence scheme of learning in multi-contexts emphasizes the exclusive use of online media. Whereas, the exemplary teachers in my study decide these media on a purpose of blending, due to other way ineffectiveness in their class, hence not exclusively to teach nor learn on them.

There are other differences in the exemplary teachers regarding their perceptions, practices and reflections upon technology integration in English class on constructing learning upon skills of communication from the existing literature. Some studies on phenomenological (social) construction emphasize technologies in English class for intrinsic motivation. Whereas the exemplary teachers though working with qualitative pedagogical approaches and skills of using technologies for creating intrinsic motivation, partly their practices rest on the principles of extrinsic motivation, too. In this regard, as the exemplary teachers reflected, interactive online sources and media use in project learning supported their pedagogical intents and enabled teachers to come up with new skills on increasing learning, as one example of technology on the principle of intrinsic motivation. However, the exemplary teachers on some occasions used the media and downloaded items as films, music etc. in their classroom practices that centered on entertaining rather than teaching, though the purpose was to motivate students to engage in practice of language as grammar exercises present in the textbook.

Similarities and differences between the literature and exemplary teachers' pedagogical practices of technology use in class in my study move still further. The literature on the line of Davis (2009) claims teachers' perceived ease of technology use as significantly related to increasing use of technology in class. In contrast, in reflections, the exemplary teachers in my study expressively claimed that their self-explorative approaches to teaching as being based upon communication skills of those technologies perceived useful, apart from being easy to use and their interest to invent new skills associated to developing their digital competence to achieve technology integration in class. With this claim exemplary teachers lent secondary role to technological and school factors that though differed in each teacher's context. Then from the exemplary teachers' point of view, the argument is that in English it is the reflected usefulness upon teachers' communicative approaches to teaching not only perceived ease that

develops teacher's pedagogical motivation and skills for using technologies on constructing learning (Godwin-jones, 2010).

Besides, the findings on the exemplary teachers also enable a view of context factors as related to teachers use of technology but only at a basic level. Holding with this finding, the exemplary teachers' practices counter the literature e.g. Carstens and Pelgrum (2009) that emphasizes the role of technology induced school in innovative situation as a major factor on achieving technology integration. This is because in the case of the exemplary teachers school along with their students digital interest factors come but that only partly engaged to increasing use of technology in class (Jo Tondeur, Keer, Braak, & Valcke, 2008). Whereas the exemplary teachers' self-enhanced professional competence upon interactive pedagogical approaches and capacities (Stoll, 1999) and their classroom experiences in substitution for formally trained technology skills were noted as the key enablers on exploring qualitative skills and cultural themes of using technologies in developing learning in case of the exemplary teachers in my study.

On the matter regarding the barriers for teachers to use technologies in English classes as reflected by the exemplary teachers, the curriculum has been partly accountable. The curriculum is still with 70% native grammatical focus that comes heavy on Czech school children as for which technology use becomes more time consuming, preventing them on many occasions from integrating media. It limits teachers to engaging students in completing grammar exercises as given in the textbook. This in my study has come associated to a problem of structure or policy as faced by the exemplary teachers that stands partly barrier to technology use. Though exemplary teachers didn't fully agree with, barriers to the use of technologies as other teachers in my study encountered, underlies the problem of learning distractions and this relates to the use of online sources or media viewed as main channels of de-educating materials that affect child psychology.

Despite the findings of motivations and barriers related to their practices of technology use as perceived by the exemplary teachers, while exploring technology integration on learning principles of individual differences in real class encounters, my study argued that it is the role of exemplary teachers' reflective actions greater and vital to developing this phenomenon as a learning process. In this regard, in contrast to the research that captures this phenomenon as limited to increasing use of technologies in teaching irrespective of how teachers integrate in real class, technology integration in English class is achieved in exploring teachers' ways of appropriating technologies of their educational potentials (Godwin, 2015; Kamyliis et al., 2015). To this point, the exemplary teachers' creative reflections upon increasing learning interactions in my study helped them to explore new skills of technology use in class.

Following the discussions relating teacher reflections, it is here argued that technology integration in teaching English as a school subject is achieved comprehensively in teachers' qualitative pedagogical perceptions, skills, reflections and cultural themes of using them on developing learning. Along with this, my study as well supports the literature that affirms it. Technology integration in class develops on principles of individual differences as resulting from teachers' individual practices that differ in approaches, principles, ways, skills, techniques, purposes, functions, reflections and learning outcomes (Buabeng-andoh, 2012).

Furthermore, as based upon the findings on the exemplary teachers' perceptions, practices, reflections and individual factors in association, my study argues that teachers' either self-invented or enhanced pedagogical approaches and skills through their job-encounters in substitute of instrumentally trained technological knowledge, making significant contribution to technology use in classroom. Teachers' self-inventing attitudes and skills in the true bases that are significant to enhancing classroom practices leading to better learning outcomes (Carstens & Pelgrum, 2009). This is supported from the exemplary teachers self-explored professional skills in that technology skills were developed upon teaching English on skills of

communication unlike in case of teachers who as Angers (2005, p.787) asserts, “despite training, are still hesitant to adopt technologies.” Linking these arguments as prime, my study partly approves the centrally imposed formal, structural educational or pedagogical policy and curriculum used as the extrinsic motivational factors (Tour, 2015). These elements didn’t substantially motivate the exemplary teachers in my study to improve their practices, skills and themes of using technologies in class.

In contrast to the idea of technology integration as extrinsic means, the exemplary teachers’ reflections lead to supporting the literature claim as in Tour (2015) based on as discussed above, my study argues that teachers within the communicative approaches in developing classroom practices, on blended-learning models upon centering students in creative writing, problem solving, project etc. activities, voluntarily discover new ways, skills, techniques and technologies. It then follows that teacher’s self-invented skills are more sustainable in achieving educational potentials of technologies in teaching English upon skills of communication than technologically trained or other ways learnt and used technologies (Burston, 2014).

In concluding the thesis with unique examples of technology integration as contributed by the exemplary teachers discussed in my study, the findings also reveal some limitations in their practices as expressed in their own voice and also as implied in their covert language. From the reports that claim the exemplary teachers’ own learning interactions in substitute of school support on their professional development which enhanced their skills of using technologies, it is marked. That involvement of educational policy or management including research levels in this issue is still sparse. This means micro, meso and macro policy along with research levels have left English teachers in Czech schools without much support in inventing new ways of providing teachers learning opportunities or incentives for professional development to enable them to enhance classroom practices of technology integration. Hence,

these levels could extend support in increasingly organizing workshops, pedagogically integrated technology training on innovative skills focus, research exposure programs etc. yet designed to enhancing this subject teachers' didactic and media skills on integrated framework.

The other point of limitation noted is that the exemplary teachers' collaborative engagements with students at the classroom level are significantly interactive and contribute to increasing learning interactions, however, their professional level collaborations on teacher's learning are still poorly represented. At this point, this study argues, following the literature suggestion as in Clarke, Dede and Dieterle (2008), Drossel et al. (2017) that says. In addition to student-teacher collaboration, teachers' professional collaborative skills can bring online media potentials into use on exploring new opportunities and online platforms for actively engaging in peer-teacher collaborations upon enhancing professional skills. Or school level initiatives could help instead of sending teachers, as the exemplary teachers reported to one day or two-day seminars that rarely expose to learning these issues on comprehensive basis. Comprehensive pedagogical skills focused initiatives are expected to significantly support enhancing the exemplary teachers who are marked already guided by progressive pedagogical perceptions to honing their professional skills which lead to transformative teacher learning in addressing better student learning in teaching English within the emerging European framework or context.

Finally, as based on the literature and empirical findings and qualitative analyses as focused on exploring technology integration in teaching English in Czech elementary schools here discussed from exemplary teacher perspective, I conclude the thesis with its significance on three main dimensions outlined hereafter.

On a theoretical level: this thesis on phenomenological case-study contributes to phenomenological (social) constructivist concept as an interactive learning framework to study technology integration in English class from teacher perspective. It focuses on teachers'

interactive didactic approaches, skills and practices of technology use in class as linking teachers' phenomenological perceptions, practices, and reflections on developing learning. With this comprehensive concept, knowledge triangle as composed of three main components, EFL, ICT and didactics on intersection, is developed by teacher in practice of teaching English on skills of collaboration. In this model, the teacher enables the students to use technologies as an enriching social and cultural media of skills for constructing language in transformative learning practices. From this perspective, teaching practices that limit technologies on transmission from texts are argued as limited to yielding mechanical outcomes. Though phenomenological concept develops as an interactive learning process, my study claims that research regarding technology integration from the teacher's perspective is still insufficient (Warshauer, 2000). Thus, my study following phenomenological concept on (social) construction designed research on qualitative phenomenological case-study to explore the research phenomenon in complexity.

On a methodological level: my research explores the potential of qualitative phenomenological case-study design (Louis Cohen et al., 2013). In this design, dynamic methods of inquiry, researcher and participant roles, tools and techniques and skills of analysis are coherently developed bringing the phenomenon to knowledge in its complexity. This method is an interactive inquiry process on the educational issue as selected. There are several research projects in education regarding this paradigm. However, research on technology integration in teaching English from exemplary teacher perspective as conducted within phenomenological case study design is still limited since the major research focus is still limited to quantitative analysis on cognitivist paradigm. As a result, despite exploring educational potentials of technologies that modernize the process of teaching and learning English upon skills of communication, research with quantitative analysis limits achieving technology integration in teachers' mechanistic practices. Thus, as an alternative, in a phenomenological

case-study design my study extends the significance of qualitative research as a comprehensive knowledge constructing model to explore this phenomenon by exploring exemplary teachers' interactive pedagogical behaviors, skills and cultural themes for using technologies on constructing learning.

On empirical level: this study contributes to subject didactic field of English teaching regarding technology integration in class on developing learning process from the lived experiences of the exemplary practitioners. Practically, this study informs teachers integrating technologies in school classrooms for teaching English in the outer global circle as in Czech school context. In this circle, in contrast with the practices of technology use as limited to transmitting English from native linguistic system as inadequate model to non-native global citizens, my study from the exemplary teachers' practices of technology use, informs educational potentials of technologies for enhancing classroom practices based upon skills of communication. These in case of the selected exemplary teachers from the Czech elementary schools build in teaching within communicative approach on blended-learning model. Hence, from the exemplary teachers' practices, my study argues that Teachers' qualitative pedagogical perceptions or approaches, skills and themes of using technologies are significantly related to developing technology integration in teaching English for developing learning in patterns of change to address intercultural communication skills as aspired for developing global citizenship skills.

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Appendix 1

Findings on the Study Teachers' Technology Use in English Class

Teacher	Teacher's perceptions: Decisions regarding the use of individual ICT in class (perceived motivations and barriers)			Teacher's practices of ICT in class: Principles, ways, purposes, functions		Teacher's reflections on ICT use in classroom practices		Individual factors: Intrinsic and extrinsic factors contributing ICT use in classroom practices	
Donna	ICT types	Stimuli	Barriers	Teacher role	Role given to	Stimuli	Barriers	Personal Intrinsic factor	Professional Extrinsic factors
	<p>Offline iTOOL of textbook Word processor</p> <p>Downloaded audio-visuals (documentaries and movies) Content</p> <p>Photocopies</p> <p>Projector</p> <p>Online Google, Wikipedia, Websites YouTube</p>	<p>Useful to blend grammar/vocabulary with language skills</p> <p>Useful to integrate language skills with creative writing/reading group-activities</p> <p>Useful on big Projects to bring English embedded in native context and cultural skills</p> <p>Useful for creating learning under teacher's guidance (selecting materials and tasks for students)</p>	<p>Technical problems</p> <p>Entertaining more than learning</p> <p>Ineffective if frequently used</p> <p>De-educating materials</p> <p>Learning distractions</p>	<p>Sets Practices on learning by doing principles</p> <p>Explores and organizes varieties of activities on language skills integrated</p> <p>Entertains</p> <p>Assumes roles (coach, guide, facilitator)</p> <p>Selects ICT & materials for students to use and practice creative writing topics and projects on multiple subjects (history cultures etc.)</p> <p>Assesses students' language skills and knowledge</p>	<p>Engage in classroom tasks</p> <p>Practice language skills in group Interactions</p> <p>Use given ICT links Do projects</p> <p>Present</p> <p>Attempt tests, projects Assignments etc.</p>	<p>Useful for engaging students on language and skills integrated practices</p> <p>Useful for Extrinsic motivation</p> <p>Useful for creativity skills learning by self and collaborate d actions</p> <p>Useful on creative writing topics and projects on multiple subjects (native country history, cultures, other skills)</p> <p>Useful for creating intrinsic motivation</p> <p>Useful for language skills and knowledge assessment</p>	<p>Class Mgmt. problem</p> <p>Time consuming</p> <p>Distraction due to unverified materials affecting child psychology</p>	<p>Self-interested on ICT as tools for teaching-learning English in communication skills on learning by doing model</p> <p>Qualified and experienced teacher of English Communicative approach (learning by doing under teacher guidance)</p> <p>Interactive attitude toward students (also learns from students)</p> <p>Risk-taking to teach beyond the curriculum</p> <p>Perceives ICT for engaging students in learning English native cultural skills on learning by doing model under teacher's guidance</p>	<p>School system and teachers using ICT</p> <p>Regular Training</p> <p>Self-explored and school supported for seminars/conferences</p> <p>Students digital motivations</p>

Teacher	Teacher's perceptions: Decisions regarding the use of individual ICT in class (perceived motivations and barriers)			Teacher's practices of ICT in EFL class: Principles, ways, purposes, functions		Teacher's reflections on ICT use in EFL classroom practices		Individual factors: Intrinsic and extrinsic factors contributing ICT use in classroom practices	
George	ICT types	Stimuli	Barriers	Teacher role	Student role	Stimuli	Barriers	Personal Intrinsic factors	Professional Extrinsic factors
	<p>Offline</p> <p>iTOOL of textbook</p> <p>Word processor</p> <p>Downloaded audio-visuals, content on quiz/inquiry topics etc.</p> <p>Photocopies</p> <p>Projector</p> <p>Online</p> <p>Google,</p> <p>Choke.com</p> <p>Wikipedia</p> <p>Websites</p> <p>YouTube</p> <p>Online language program (port of knowledge)</p> <p>Online system for homework</p>	<p>Useful to blend grammar/vocabulary exercises with language skills practices</p> <p>Useful to integrate games, quiz and inquiry topics learning with textbook language/curriculum</p> <p>Useful on big Projects</p> <p>Useful to bring English embedded in international contexts and cultures</p> <p>Useful to teach collaboration skills</p> <p>Useful to communicate assignment</p>	<p>Technical problems (delayed class practices)</p> <p>Ineffective in increased use</p> <p>Cause in students inconsistent learning tendencies</p>	<p>Sets</p> <p>Practices on learning by inquiry/problem-solving principles</p> <p>Designs, explores & organizes activities to integrate with language skills for class to group practice</p> <p>Entertains</p> <p>Varies roles: coach, organizer, facilitator, judge and collaborator</p> <p>Enables students ICT to select information/materials to do projects</p> <p>Assess by oral skills</p> <p>Communicates materials on homework</p>	<p>Engage in classroom interactions</p> <p>Practice language in skills, quiz, games and inquiry/problem topics</p> <p>Do projects in groups</p> <p>Present</p> <p>Express choices on ICT and topics for change in class</p> <p>Attempt tests of oral skills and projects</p>	<p>Useful for engaging students on language and tasks integrated classroom practices</p> <p>Useful for Extrinsic motivation</p> <p>Useful for creative skills on inquiry topics & for projects on intercultural topics</p> <p>Useful for creating intrinsic motivation</p> <p>Useful to keep records and assess oral skills</p> <p>Useful to communicate assignment</p>	<p>Ineffectiveness in motivating students in increased use</p> <p>Technical errors</p> <p>Students copy and paste problems sometimes</p> <p>Possibilities of learning distractions</p>	<p>Skilled on ICT as innovative tools for teaching-learning English in communication skills on learning by inquiry principle</p> <p>Competent and experienced teacher of English</p> <p>Communicative approaches (guided inquiry on blended-model)</p> <p>Risk-taking to teach beyond curriculum</p> <p>Self-engaging to develop ICT on English teaching for skills</p> <p>Interactive Attitude toward students (accepts students choice)</p> <p>Perceives ICT for engaging students on learning inquiry skills, intercultural and technology skills of English for practical use</p>	<p>School advancing in digital system</p> <p>Regular Training</p> <p>Self-explored and school supported for seminars and out-exposure programs</p> <p>Students varying digital learning motivations</p>

Teacher	Teacher's perceptions: Decisions regarding the use of individual ICT in class (perceived motivations and barriers)			Teacher's practices of ICT in EFL class: Principles, ways, purposes, functions		Teacher's reflections on ICT use in EFL classroom practices		Individual factors: Intrinsic and extrinsic factors contributing ICT use in classroom practices	
Dave	ICT types	Stimuli	Barriers	Teacher role	Student role	Stimuli	Barriers	Personal Intrinsic factors	Professional Extrinsic factors
	<p>Offline</p> <p><i>iTOOL of textbook</i></p> <p><i>Word processor</i></p> <p><i>Downloaded audio-visuals,</i></p> <p><i>Music, Movies, Content related to different country and culture topics</i></p> <p><i>Photocopies</i></p> <p>Projector</p> <p>Online</p> <p><i>Google,</i></p> <p><i>Wikipedia</i></p> <p><i>Websites</i></p> <p><i>YouTube</i></p> <p><i>Online learning platforms (visit your teacher)</i></p> <p><i>Emails</i></p> <p><i>Facebook</i></p> <p>Online magazine</p>	<p>Useful to blend grammar/vocabulary exercises with activities on communication skills</p> <p>Useful to engage student-to-students teaching Topics</p> <p>Useful to design collaborated projects</p> <p>Useful to teach English embedded in new contexts and cultures</p> <p>Useful to communicate homework/projects online</p> <p>Useful for increasing students' creative writing skills</p>	<p>Not effective without activities</p> <p>Limited to classroom use only</p> <p>Technical problems</p> <p>Distraction due to too much information</p> <p>Time consuming</p> <p>Delay in curriculum</p>	<p>Sets Practices on learning by collaborated tasks/projects</p> <p>Introduces integrated activities for students to teach</p> <p>Explores and Engages groups on problem or creative writing topics</p> <p>Entertains</p> <p>Roles Monitor, facilitator, collaborator</p> <p>Enables students to select topics and ICT for materials/ to practice collaborated projects</p> <p>Assesses skills</p> <p>Communicates assignment</p> <p>Supports students to online publishing</p>	<p>Engage in pair and group interactions</p> <p>Practice language in skills, games and creative reading and writing topics-based activities</p> <p>Teach class on language skills-integrated topics</p> <p>Collaborate to do mini and big projects</p> <p>Present</p> <p>Attempt tests of oral and other language skills</p>	<p>Useful tools to engage students on language and tasks integrated group-activities</p> <p>Useful to enable students to learn English by learning to teach topics and language skills</p> <p>Useful for Extrinsic motivation</p> <p>Useful for creative writing on country and intercultural topics</p> <p>Useful on mini and big projects on different topics</p> <p>Useful to communicate and create intrinsic motivation with authentic tasks</p> <p>Useful for interactive assessment</p>	<p>Ineffective if used without tasks</p> <p>↓</p> <p>Technical barriers</p> <p>↑</p> <p>Students copy and paste problems in topics and projects</p> <p>Learning distractions if not monitored</p>	<p>Self-learned ICT as smart tools for communication, and for teaching-learning English in skills on learning by collaborated task/project principles</p> <p>Competent and experienced teacher of English</p> <p>Communicative approaches (learning by collaborated actions)</p> <p>Risk-taking to teach beyond curriculum</p> <p>Self-exploring technologies and teaching approaches</p> <p>Flexible and Collaborative Attitudes (mutual understanding between students and teacher)</p> <p>Perceives ICT for enabling students new topics, contexts, autonomy to enhance English skills in collaborative and intercultural skills practices</p>	<p>School advance in digital systems</p> <p>Regular exposure and training</p> <p>↓</p> <p>Self-explored online programs on teaching and school supported to participate in external projects on ICT</p> <p>↑</p> <p>Students digital learning motivations and growing competences</p>

Teacher	Teacher's perceptions: Decisions regarding the use of individual ICT in class (perceived motivations and barriers)			Teacher's practices of ICT in EFL class: Principles, ways, purposes, functions		Teacher's reflections on ICT use in EFL classroom practices		Individual factors: Intrinsic and extrinsic factors contributing ICT use in classroom practices	
Jane	ICT types	Stimuli	Barriers	Teacher role	Student role	Stimuli	Barriers	Personal Intrinsic factors	Professional Extrinsic factors
	<p>Offline</p> <p>Word processor</p> <p>iTOOL of textbook</p> <p>Downloaded audio-visuals,</p> <p>Movies,</p> <p>Language games,</p> <p>Content on topics relating national and international cultures, traditions, celebrations etc.</p> <p>Photocopies</p> <p>Projector</p> <p>Online</p> <p>Google,</p> <p>Wikipedia</p> <p>Websites</p> <p>YouTube</p> <p>Online games</p> <p>Facebook</p> <p>Online links of iTOOL for homework</p>	<p>Useful to integrate grammar/vocabulary with language skills-focused activities</p> <p>Useful to motivate students to practice communication in games</p> <p>Useful to engage students on creative writing or multiple topics learning</p> <p>Useful to practice projects bringing English embedded in local and country context and cultural skills</p> <p>Useful to assess skills</p> <p>Useful to communicate assignment</p>	<p>Not useful in every lesson</p> <p>Technical problems</p> <p>Learner distraction due to too much information</p>	<p>Sets Practices on learning by games principles on trial and error base</p> <p>Explores and organizes games and creative writing and topic-based activities for students to practice in groups</p> <p>Entertains</p> <p>Roles facilitator, collaborator</p> <p>Enables students to use ICT to explore information/materials to practice projects</p> <p>Assesses oral skills and projects</p> <p>Communicates materials on homework</p>	<p>Engage in group interactions</p> <p>Practice language skills in games and creative writing and multi-thematic topic-based activities</p> <p>Collaborate using ICT to explore materials,</p> <p>Do projects</p> <p>Present</p> <p>Attempt tests of language skills</p>	<p>Useful tools to engage students on language and tasks integrated group-based activities</p> <p>Useful for Extrinsic motivation</p> <p>Useful for creative writing on country and intercultural topics</p> <p>& for mini and big projects on multiple subjects</p> <p>Useful to assess oral skills</p> <p>Useful to communicate and create intrinsic learning motivation with real tasks</p>	<p>Ineffective in every lesson</p> <p>Technical barriers</p> <p>Students copy and paste problems in projects</p> <p>Learning distractions due to too much information</p>	<p>Self-interested and learning ICT as interactive tools for teaching-learning English in skills on learning by games principles (trial and error)</p> <p>Qualified and experienced teacher of English</p> <p>Communicative approaches (learning by games)</p> <p>Risk-taking to teach beyond curriculum</p> <p>Self-exploring language games via ICT</p> <p>Helpful attitudes toward Students</p> <p>Perceives ICT to enable students to learn creative skills and games to enhance English skills in intercultural skills & new technologies</p>	<p>School in early stage of digital systems</p> <p>Regularly learning profession</p> <p>Self-attending seminars,</p> <p>Formally studying ICT in pedagogy</p> <p>Students' growing digital learning motivations</p>

Appendix 2

Charts of Data Analysis on Study Teachers

Study Teacher 1 Donna

ICT + EFL items	Teacher Perceptions	Teaching-learning Practices (expressed/observed)	Activities, purposes and functions of ICT in EFL class	Post use reflections on ICT	Decision on use	Personal and professional factors	Teacher perceived Stimuli	Teacher experienced barriers
Offline ICT								
Laptop/data projector/itool/ data storage/ downloaded audio videos/ films	Usual tools for lesson preparation, teaching and learning in school Multimedia substitute of blackboard, books <i>Easy tools to present</i> <i>to draw attention</i> to display refreshing materials means or materials for language skills audio-video integration with content	Class use and other tasks teach lesson, project videos, audio lessons homework/ assessment records <i>Project textual data (word-meanings, syntax),</i> videos, films PPT presentations Student projects Teacher-class interaction on tasks Display on data projector	Usual Support materials, storage, class use for internet, presentation etc. support Project lessons, Special lesson presentation by teacher Refreshment purposes Audio-visual displays	Essential for daily work Tool for class attention Useful on projects Student presentations Reflective activities Refreshing Very useful materials for oral skills, learner-motivational tools Digital substitute of simple texts for occasional use <i>Simple to use</i>	School Teacher's purpose to build communicative lessons Students growing digital tendencies	School exposure to seminars Projectors in each class Teacher understanding e.g. substitute of blackboard	Portable, convergent uses Student attention to blend tasks Refresh class with videos, music, films etc. Refreshing, motivational to engage, essential to enhance skills Activate teacher to learn and prepare lessons (p.2) Easy to share teaching-learning materials	Keep busy, Preparing the materials is time consuming Technical problems, Student-side talk Noisy-entertaining Continuous use in the class unproductive

	Effective for student-present projects to	Textbook-exercises on digital screen		Skills-learning tool			among teachers	
		Cultural topics prepared and presented by students		Active learning materials				
Photocopies	Photocopy for group-tasks on grammar exercises intensive practices	Grammar, reading-writing pair works Prompts for listening and speaking Teacher facilitates one by one Blended exercises: watching-listening etc. followed by writing	Grammar in pair and Group work To facilitate in writing and reading	Essential for group learning of grammar and Reading-writing skills Formative assessment	Teacher's intent to combine grammar with other skills Students' positive performance and response on grammar learning with photocopy material	Teacher's perception on its effectiveness to draw student attention to solving grammar problems in pair	Easy to engage and facilitate students on grammar, writing etc. Effective material to blend content and language	Time demanding
Online ICT	Perception	Practices	Activities, purposes and functions of ICT	Reflections	Decision on use	Personal and professional factors	Teacher perceived Stimuli	Teacher perceived Barriers
Google, YouTube, Film videos, Documentaries Emails	Google and YouTube for online authentic materials to increase interactions in class helpful to creating awareness on English accent, context-skills etc. Emails for administrative and urgent communications with absentee students on assignment (p.5-6)	Blended activities: watch videos and listen, followed by read-write, speak practices Pictures from google (word meanings) (p.2) Project presentation by students Movies upload (p.3)	Find materials Blended activities: listening-speaking Warm up music English context and culture topics learning Teacher-facilitated pair works	Get ready real-materials (p.2) Useful for Native cultural topics (p.7) Increasing student argumentation on power Useful for extending interaction (p.4)	Teacher's blended-learning approach to English for communication (p.2) Projects-materials, class-based grammar or other reading-writing skills focused exercises	Critical and selective use attitude (p.2) Teacher's appropriation skills (p.2) Also shared peer teacher influence Self-activating attitude (p.2) Teacher's own initiated professional training etc. School support (seminars) Participation to exchange programs with	Flexible to be used for any purpose, Not necessary to stick to one method (p.2)	De-educating materials/content (p.2) Not very personal (p.2) Time consuming (p.9) Students lacking discretion on online material as main problems

EFL items	Perceptions	Practices	Activities, purposes, functions	Reflections	Decisions on use	Personal and professional factors	Teacher perceived stimuli	Teacher perceived barriers
Grammar/vocabulary	Basic but essential items	Grammar-content blended exercises on photocopy materials	Photocopy paper-based pair exercises Audios and video-based vocabulary practices For intensive learning	Grammar difficult items Required for writing tests, Words need to be written for memory	Curriculum Teacher Students like to learn words (mobile required)	Curriculum factor Teacher attitude: (Grammar and words are equally important as other skills)	Words learning is easier with media e.g. mobile and current textbook exercises	Students not interested
Speaking/listening/reading/writing skills	All important	Audio-video blended activities	Content, context and task blended exercises For skills practices	Oral skills in English easy to teach with films, documentary and f-to-f communication exercises	Curriculum Teacher and student preference to use English	Personal belief on English for communication	Interactive class learning Activate students	Preparation is time consuming, noisy
Writing projects	For learning communication in English cultural contexts highly important	Native English cities, cultural and geography lessons display on data	Cultural projects e.g. project on foreign dishes, fake news about a city etc. (p. 2)	Very essential for critical and argumentative skills Teacher-student interaction increases	Teacher and partly curriculum (textbook prescribes projects)	Teacher motivation Teacher training on project base) Mingling with students attitude	Research and Presentation skills and active learning	Demands effort from teacher tracking students on progress
Assessment								
Projects, homework, written class tests	Not for grammar accuracy but for understandability	General remarks, display errors on office word and blackboard	Assessment of learning	Necessary for checking communication skills	Teacher + curriculum	Curriculum and training provided, school policy and teacher belief on its effectiveness	It lets teacher proceed next steps	Teacher requires extra time marking

Study Teacher 2 George

ICT + EFL items	Teacher Perceptions	Teaching-learning Practices (expressed/observed)	Activities, purposes and functions of ICT in EFL class	Post use reflections on ICT	Decision on use	Personal and professional factors	Teacher perceived Stimuli	Teacher experienced barriers
Offline ICT								
Laptop Data projector, iTOOL, Choke.com, Downloaded audio-visuals, language content, games, science fiction movies	Tools for lesson preparation and class teaching For integrating new content and materials with textbook language <i>Easy for presentation</i> <i>Helpful to draw student attention</i> Useful for integrating language skills with activities Partly for entertainment	Prepare lesson on choke.com teach lesson, Display videos <i>Textual content and grammar in contexts</i> Science fiction movies PPT presentations Teacher-class interaction on language skills- (listening, speaking, reading and writing) activities Textbook-grammar and other exercises on iTOOL Native and local culture comparison activities	Integrate lessons on activities Add up materials for class use motivate students on skills practice Special lesson presentation by teacher Entertain students occasionally Demonstration purposes for student attention Create intrinsic learning motivation Multiply teacher role from coach to facilitator	Usual tools of daily work Tools student attention Useful for task-integration Student presenting Useful for creative reflection Entertainment Useful for oral skills <i>Easy to use, Active learning materials</i>	School/teacher Purpose to build communicative lessons Students growing digital interest Useful for reflection Entertainment Useful for oral skills <i>Easy to use, Active learning materials</i>	Self learnt factor School factor Laptop to each teacher and Projectors in class Teacher's personal interest in ICT (wanted to be program developer)	Easy to make convergent use Student attention to blend activities and entertain Engage to enhance skills Activate teacher to learn and prepare lessons Easy to share material/information	Technical problems Barrier to finishing the given curriculum

Photocopies	Pair or group-tasks on grammar, writing, reading, Vocabulary activities	Teacher facilitated pair-work on Grammar and vocabulary lessons Skills integrated class interaction activities, Homework tasks and materials	Grammar and vocabulary in integrated learning in pair or Group work method Intensive practice on writing and reading etc.	Usual materials on grammar Reading-writing activities Assessing	Teacher to combine grammar with skills Students' better engaging on grammar and writing lessons	Teacher experience on effectiveness to engage students on solving grammar problems, pair activities	Easy to engage and facilitate students on grammar, writing etc. or integrate activities	Time demanding Resource not available most often
Online ICT	Teacher Perceptions	Teaching-learning Practices (expressed/ observed)	Activities, purposes and functions of ICT in EFL class	Reflections	Decision on use	Personal and professional factors	Teacher perceived Stimuli	Teacher perceived Barriers
Google, Moodle, Youtube , Self-created language program (port of knowledge) Online sources wiki etc. emails	Inquiry or problem-based lessons and activities Student projects Student presentations Skills-integrated lessons, Intercultural topic-based projects Emails on homework communication	Blended activities-based lessons Inquiry topic-based class practices Videos and Pictures from google youtube Project presentation by students	Explore language programs, materials Blend skills focused activities: Entertain Integrate English language with international context and cultures Enable students to construct skills Enhance in students inquiry, project and	Inquiry lesson materials and activities Inter-cultural topics for tasks and projects Student projects and presentations	Teacher's inquiry and project approaches on blended-learning model	Teacher's innovative and Critical appropriation skills Self-activated Teacher's own initiated professional training School support (seminars) Participation in exchange programs	Rich sources of information and language programs for inquiry and project lessons	Planning problems due to rush teaching hours and work load Distractive factors, replace book learning habits

EFL items	Teacher Perceptions	Teaching-learning Practices (expressed/observed)	Activities, purposes and functions of ICT in EFL class	Reflections	Decision on use	Personal and professional factors	Teacher perceived Stimuli	Teacher perceived Barriers
Grammar vocabulary	Basic necessary skills	Grammar/vocabulary with content integrated exercises on photocopy papers	presentation skills Photocopy paper-based grammatical exercises for intensive learning	Usual items of language Learning by writing and tests Memory games	English Curriculum and Teacher	Curriculum factor Teacher attitude: Grammar and words and all skills needed	Word and grammar learning easier with media integrated with textbook	Memory problem
Speaking/listening/reading/writing	Important skills learnt in integrated activities	Audio-visuals from YouTube or downloaded integrated with reading or writing topics in groups facilitated by teacher	Integrated skills enhancement	Learning by watching, practice and use	Teacher and student preference on learning skills	Teacher believes Communication most important	Skills in practice to activate students	Preparing tasks and materials needs lot of resource
Writing inquiry topics and projects Student presentations	Metacognitive skills learnt in explorative method, online search, and tasks engagement	Pair activities online media and language program supported lessons on free and problem-based inquiry topics on various themes, cultural comparisons etc.	To develop metacognitive skills in English	Learning by participation critical and creative activities	Teacher on inquiry lessons, Curriculum on writing projects	Teacher guided by inquiry and project methods as key approaches to communicative teaching	Research, explorative and Presentation skills learning In inquiry and project practices	Problem of plagiarism
Recording for assessment And assessment in general	Beneficial for creating language awareness, not for accuracy but for skills development	Formative assessment on grammar, oral skills and projects	To scaffold and provide feedback to students to enhance skills practices	Digital record devices in language laboratory Necessary for checking communication skills	Teacher + curriculum.	Teacher's own perception on its effectiveness	Enhance oral skills/motivates students	Time consuming

Study Teacher 3 Dave

ICT + EFL items	Teacher Perceptions	Teaching-learning Practices	Activities, purposes and functions of ICT in EFL class	Post use reflections on ICT	Decision on use	Personal and professional factors	Teacher perceived Stimuli	Teacher experienced barriers
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		(expressed/ observed)						
Offline ICT								
Laptop Data projector, iTOOL, Downloaded audio-visuals, language content, Music, games, movies	Interactive tools for lesson preparation and class teaching integrating new materials and activities with textbook language and curriculum <i>for presentation</i> <i>to engage students in practice of language skills</i> For entertainment	Prepare lesson on laptop supported by other types of ICT teach lessons and classroom practices Audios on listening Display videos <i>Content on grammar exercises integrated</i> Music Movies PPT presentations Language skills-integrated student-to-student teaching activities	Usual lesson presenting Integrate language and its curriculum with other activities Add new materials for student activities Engage students in practice of communication skills Entertain students occasionally for a change Demonstration of tasks Create intrinsic learning motivation Increase teacher-student roles	Usual tools of daily work Tools for student attention Useful in task-integration Student teaching and presenting Useful for engaging students in practice of skills Entertainment <i>Easy to use materials</i>	School/teacher Appropriate to practice teaching in communicative approaches Students growing digital competences and interests	Self learnt School provides Laptop to each teacher and Projectors in class Teacher's personal interest on ICT	Easy to build convergent activities Effective means to engage students on learning communication skills Good to entertain Activate teacher and students to prepare and practice activity lessons	Not effective on daily use Time demanding Technical problems Delays in course completion
Photocopies	Group-tasks on grammatical class practices Testing grammar writing vocabulary etc.	Group works on Grammar lessons integrated Language skills integrated class activities Homework materials	Grammar and vocabulary in integrated learning in pair or Group work method Intensive practices on usual lessons	Usual materials on grammar Reading-writing activities Assessing	Teacher blend grammar lessons with activities with Students engaging	effectiveness to engage students in solving grammar problems, group activities	Easy to engage and facilitate students on grammar, writing etc. integrated activities	Time demanding Resource consuming

Online ICT	Teacher Perceptions	Teaching-learning Practices (expressed/observed)	Activities, purposes and functions of ICT in EFL class	Reflections	Decision on use	Personal and professional factors	Teacher perceived Stimuli	Teacher perceived Barriers
<p>Google, YouTube, Wikipedia</p> <p>Online learning platforms (Visit your teacher)</p>	<p>Problem topic-based class activities</p> <p>Student collaborated mini and big projects</p> <p>Student presentations</p> <p>Skills-integrated lessons,</p> <p>Facebook and Emails on homework communication</p>	<p>Blended activities-based lessons</p> <p>Inquiry topic-based class practices</p> <p>Videos and Pictures from google youtube</p> <p>Project presentation by students</p>	<p>Explore language programs, materials</p> <p>Blend skills focused activities:</p> <p>Entertain</p> <p>Integrate English language with international context and cultures</p> <p>Enable students to construct skills</p> <p>Enhance in students inquiry, project and presentation skills</p>	<p>Inquiry lesson materials and activities</p> <p>Inter-cultural topics for tasks and projects</p> <p>Student projects and presentations</p>	<p>Teacher's inquiry and project approaches on blended-learning model</p>	<p>Teacher's innovative and Critical appropriation skills</p> <p>Self-activated</p> <p>Teacher's own initiated professional training</p> <p>School support (seminars)</p> <p>Participation in exchange programs</p>	<p>Rich sources of information and language programs for inquiry and project lessons</p>	<p>Planning problems due to rush teaching hours and work load</p> <p>Distractive factors, replace book learning habits</p>
EFL items	Teacher Perceptions	Teaching-learning Practices (expressed/observed)	Activities, purposes and functions of ICT in EFL class	Reflections	Decision on use	Personal and professional factors	Teacher perceived Stimuli	Teacher perceived Barriers
Grammar vocabulary	Basic necessary skills	Grammar/vocabulary with content integrated exercises on photocopy papers	Photocopy paper-based grammatical exercises for intensive learning	Usual items of language Learning by writing and test Memory games	English Curriculum and Teacher	Curriculum factor Teacher attitude: Grammar and words and all skills needed	Word and grammar learning easier with media integrated with textbook	Memory problem
Speaking/listening/	Important skills learnt in	Audio-visually from YouTube or downloaded	Integrated skills enhancement	Learning by watching,		Teacher believes Communicat	Skills in practice to	Preparing tasks and materials

reading/writing	integrated activities	integrated with reading or writing topics in groups facilitated by teacher		practice and use	Teacher and student preference on learning skills	most important	activate students	needs lot of resource
Topic writing group activities Collaborated mini and big projects Student presentations	Metacognitive skills learnt in explorative method, online search, and tasks engagement	Pair activities online media and language program supported lessons on free and problem-based inquiry topics on various themes, cultural comparisons etc.	To develop metacognitive skills in English	Learning by participation critical and creative activities	Teacher on inquiry lessons, Curriculum on writing projects	Teacher guided by inquiry and project methods as key approaches to communicative teaching	Research, explorative and Presentation skills learning In inquiry and project practices	Problem of plagiarism
Online tools for skills assessment	Beneficial for creating language awareness, not for accuracy but for skills development	Formative assessment on grammar, oral skills and projects	To scaffold and provide feedback to students to enhance skills practices	Digital record devices in language laboratory Necessary for checking communication skills	Teacher + curriculum.	Teacher's own perception on its effectiveness	Enhance oral skills/motivates students	Time consuming

Study Teacher 4 Jane

ICT + EFL items	Teacher Perceptions	Teaching-learning Practices (expressed/observed)	Activities, purposes and functions of ICT in EFL class	Post use reflections on ICT	Decision on use	Personal and professional factors	Teacher perceived Stimuli	Teacher experienced barriers
Offline ICT								
Laptop Data projector, iTOOL, Choke.com, Downloaded audio-visuals, language content, games,	Tools for lesson preparation and class teaching For integrating new content and materials with textbook language <i>Easy for presentation</i>	Prepare lesson on choke.com teach lesson, Display videos <i>Textual content and grammar in contexts</i> Science fiction movies	Integrate lessons on activities Add up materials for class use motivate students on skills practice Special lesson presentation by teacher	Usual tools of daily work Tools student attention Useful for task-integration Student presenting	School/teacher Purpose to build communicative lessons Students growing digital interest	Self learnt factor School factor Laptop to each teacher and Projectors in class Teacher's personal interest in ICT (wanted to be program developer)	Easy to make convergent use Student attention to blend activities and entertain	Technical problems Barrier to finishing the given curriculum

science fiction movies	<i>Helpful to draw student attention</i> Useful for integrating language skills with activities Partly for entertainment	PPT presentations Teacher-class interaction on language skills- (listening, speaking, reading and writing) activities Textbook-grammar and other exercises on iTOOL Native and local culture comparison activities	Entertain students occasionally Demonstration purposes for student attention Create intrinsic learning motivation Multiply teacher role from coach to facilitator	Useful for creative reflection Entertainment Useful for oral skills <i>Easy to use, Active learning materials</i>			Engage to enhance skills Activate teacher to learn and prepare lessons Easy to share material/information	
Photocopies	Pair or group-tasks on grammar, writing, reading, Vocabulary activities	Teacher facilitated pair-work on Grammar and vocabulary lessons Skills integrated class interaction activities, Homework tasks and materials	Grammar and vocabulary in integrated learning in pair or Group work method Intensive practice on writing and reading etc.	Usual materials on grammar Reading-writing activities Assessing	Teacher to combine grammar with skills Students' better engaging on grammar and writing lessons	Teacher experience on effectiveness to engage students on solving grammar problems, pair activities	Easy to engage and facilitate students on grammar, writing etc. or integrate activities	Time demanding Resource not available most often
Online ICT	Teacher Perceptions	Teaching-learning Practices (expressed/observed)	Activities, purposes and functions of ICT in EFL class	Reflections	Decision on use	Personal and professional factors	Teacher perceived Stimuli	Teacher perceived Barriers
Google, Moodle, Youtube , Self-created language program (port of knowledge)	Inquiry or problem-based lessons and activities Student projects Student presentations	Blended activities-based lessons Inquiry topic-class practices	Explore language programs, materials Blend skills focused activities: Entertain	Inquiry lesson materials and activities Inter-cultural topics for tasks and projects	Teacher's inquiry and project approaches on blended-learning model	Teacher's innovative and Critical appropriation skills Self-activated	Rich sources of information and language programs for inquiry and project lessons	Planning problems due to rush teaching hours and work load Distractive factors, replace book learning habits

Online sources wiki etc. emails	Skills-integrated lessons, Intercultural topic-based projects Emails on homework communication	Videos and Pictures from google youtube Project presentation by students	Integrate English language with international context and cultures Enable students to construct skills Enhance in students inquiry, project and presentation skills	Student projects and presentations		Teacher's own initiated professional training School support (seminars) Participation in exchange programs		
EFL items	Teacher Perceptions	Teaching-learning Practices (expressed/observed)	Activities, purposes and functions of ICT in EFL class	Reflections	Decision on use	Personal and professional factors	Teacher perceived Stimuli	Teacher perceived Barriers
Grammar vocabulary	Basic necessary skills	Grammar/vocabulary with content integrated exercises on photocopy papers	Photocopy paper-based grammatical exercises for intensive learning	Usual items of language Learning by writing and tests Memory games	English Curriculum and Teacher	Curriculum factor Teacher attitude: Grammar and words and all skills needed	Word and grammar learning easier with media integrated with textbook	Memory problem
Speaking/listening/reading/writing	Important skills learnt in integrated activities	Audio-visuals from YouTube or downloaded integrated with reading or writing topics in groups facilitated by teacher	Integrated skills enhancement	Learning by watching, practice and use	Teacher and student preference on learning skills	Teacher believes Communication most important	Skills in practice to activate students	Preparing tasks and materials needs lot of resource
Writing inquiry topics and projects Student presentations	Metacognitive skills learnt in explorative method, online search, and tasks engagement	Pair activities online media and language program supported lessons on free and problem-based inquiry topics on various themes, cultural comparisons etc.	To develop metacognitive skills in English	Learning by participation critical and creative activities	Teacher on inquiry lessons, Curriculum on writing projects	Teacher guided by inquiry and project methods as key approaches to communicative teaching	Research, explorative and Presentation skills learning In inquiry and project practices	Problem of plagiarism

Recording for assessment And assessment in general	Beneficial for creating language awareness, not for accuracy but for skills development	Formative assessment on grammar, oral skills and projects	To scaffold and provide feedback to students to enhance skills practices	Digital record devices in language laboratory Necessary for checking communication skills	Teacher + curriculum.	Teacher's own perception of its effectiveness	Enhance oral skills/motivates students	Time consuming
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The End *

